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Computational approaches to multidimensional radiative transfer and the physics of radiative colliding flows

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Abstract

Two numerical methods for the solution of the multidimensional NLTE radiative transfer problem under optically thick and optically thin conditions for a prescribed density and velocity distribution are presented, along with first applications. The stability of radiative shock waves and the consequences for structure formation are investigated.

The first method has been developed for optically thick conditions. A generalized mean intensity approach is used for the solution of the transfer equation, whose advantages are the independence of the convergence properties on the grid spacing and the moderate memory requirements. An equidistant Cartesian grid is used and a first order finite difference scheme, together with upwinding. The rate equation part is solved by standard techniques and iteratively coupled to the transfer part. Sobolev coefficients, adapted to three dimensions, are used for the treatment of optically thick lines. The main difference to other existing methods lies in the solution of the transfer equation. We present extended tests for parts of the corresponding code TR3D as well as for the code as a whole.

The second approach has been designed under the simplifying assumption of nebular conditions. The corresponding code D3NEBEL can compute the ionization structure and optically thin, Doppler shifted emission line profiles. The three dimensional structure is caught by a set of one dimensional rays. The one dimensional solver applied to each ray features automatic adaptation of the step size in radial direction, a great number of atomic processes and atomic data, and a consistent temperature computation. In addition, if applicable D3NEBEL is much faster than TR3D. To demonstrate its capabilities for the investigation of binary star systems, D3NEBEL has been applied to several three dimensional model density and velocity distributions of symbiotic binaries.

In the third part of this thesis, the stability properties of radiative colliding flows are investigated. One and two dimensional numerical simulations of radiative shock waves have been performed, using Euler equations with a source term to account for radiative energy loss. We show that unstable behavior is rather the rule than the exception. The two dimensional simulations show a

subtle interplay between classical hydrodynamical instabilities, like Rayleigh-Taylor, Richtmyer-Meskov, and Kelvin-Helmholtz, the thermal instability of the cooling gas, and thin shell instabilities. These instabilities generate supersonic turbulence in the interaction zone and cause the formation of high density knots and filaments in a otherwise tenuous surrounding. In this way, radiative shock waves may considerably contribute to structure formation, causing, for example, cometary knots in planetary nebula or even the formation of entire stars. The complex behavior of the interaction zone probably puts its stamp on parts of the emitted spectrum from radio to X-ray.

Kurzzusammenfassung

Zwei numerische Methoden zur Lösung des multidimensionalen NLTE Strahlungstransportproblems unter NLTE Bedingungen werden vorgestellt. Die Strahlungstransportgleichung wird unter optisch dicken oder dünnen Bedingungen für eine vorgegebene Dichte- und Geschwindigkeitsverteilung gelöst. Erste Anwendungen werden vorgestellt. Die Stabilität von strahlenden Schocks wird untersucht und ihr Beitrag für die Strukturbildung im Weltraum wird diskutiert.

Die erste Methode wurde für optisch dicke Bedingungen entwickelt. Dabei wird für die Lösung der Transportgleichung ein 'generalized mean intensity approach' verwendet. Dessen Vorteile liegen in der Unabhängigkeit des Konvergenzverhaltens von der Diskretisierungslänge und in einem geringeren Speicherplatzbedarf. Ein äquidistantes kartesisches Gitter und ein finites Differenzen Schema erster Ordnung werden verwendet, zusammen mit sog. upwinding. Der Ratengleichungsteil wird mit Hilfe von Standardtechniken gelöst. Mit dem Transportteil ist er iterativ gekoppelt. Zur Behandlung optisch dicker Linien werden Sobolev Koeffizienten, angepasst an drei Dimensionen, verwendet. Der Hauptunterschied zu anderen Methoden liegt somit in der Lösung der Transportgleichung. Wir präsentieren ausgedehnte Tests für die einzelnen Teile wie auch für das ganze Programm TR3D.

Der zweite Ansatz nimmt Nebelbedingungen an. Das Programm D3NEBEL ist in der Lage, Ionisationsstrukturen und optisch dünne, dopplerverschobene Emissionslinienprofile zu berechnen. Die dreidimensionale Struktur wird durch eine Anzahl eindimensionaler Strahlen abgedeckt. Der für diese Strahlen verwendete eindimensionale Löser verfügt über eine automatische Schrittweitensteuerung in radialer Richtung, hat eine grosse Anzahl atomarer Prozesse und Daten implementiert und ist fähig, eine konsistente Temperatur zu bestimmen. Falls D3NEBEL angewendet werden kann ist dieses Programm viel schneller als TR3D und braucht viel weniger Speicherplatz. Um seine Möglichkeiten zu illustrieren, wurde D3NEBEL auf einige simulierte dreidimensionale Dichte- und Geschwindigkeitsverteilungen von symbiotischen Doppelsternen angewendet.

Im dritten Teil dieser Dissertation werden die Stabilitätseigenschaften von

strahlenden, kollidierenden Strömungen untersucht. Die Ergebnisse von ein- und zweidimensionalen numerischen Simulationen von strahlenden Schocks werden dargestellt. Zur Modellierung wurden Eulergleichungen verwendet, zusammen mit einem Quellterm, der den Energieverlust durch Strahlung berücksichtigt. Wir zeigen, dass instabiles Verhalten eher die Regel als die Ausnahme ist. Die zweidimensionalen Rechnungen zeigen eine subtile Wechselwirkung zwischen klassischen hydrodynamischen Instabilitäten wie Rayleigh-Taylor-, Richtmyer-Meskov- und Kelvin-Helmholtz-Instabilitäten, der thermischen Instabilität des kühlenden Gases und von Instabilitäten d"unner Schichten. Diese Instabilitäten erzeugen supersonische Turbulenz in der Wechselwirkungszone und führen zur Entstehung von sehr dichten Knoten und Filamenten in einer ansonsten dünnen Umgebung. Auf diese Art tragen strahlende Schocks beträchtlich zur Strukturbildung im Weltraum bei. Dies könnte beispielsweise zur Entstehung von 'cometary knots' (hellen Knoten) in Planetarischen Nebeln oder gar ganzen Sterne führen. Das komplexe Verhalten der Wechselwirkungszone drückt wahrscheinlich auch Teilen des emittierten Spektrums vom Radio- bis in den Röntgenbereich seinen Stempel auf.

Chapter 1

What this work is about

1.1 Radiation and its interaction with matter

Radiation and its interaction with matter provide the red thread for this thesis, which deals with computational aspects of this vast topic. The aim of this introduction is twofold. First, it should bring to mind the *importance of the topic* and, second, it should give an idea of the *present capabilities of numerical simulations in this field*. The examples touched below shall illustrate how omnipresent the problem is in astrophysics and how different the emphasis can be. It also should become clear that there is not one solution to the problem but many different solutions, depending on the specific application. Finally, attention shall be drawn to the importance of radiation in areas other than astrophysics.

A starry sky at night offers a hint at the importance of radiation in astrophysics: The photons reaching earth are the primary source of information we have of other objects in the universe. Consequently, at least for a final comparison with reality, radiation in some form has to be added to most models of astrophysical objects. Other everyday experiences with radiation and matter remind us, however, that this might not always be easy. Clouds passing in front of the sun, the blue sky itself, or cloths of different colors heating differently in the sun indicate that there is a mutual interaction between matter and radiation. Radiation may be absorbed, scattered, or emitted by matter while the state and dynamics of the matter can be influenced by the radiation field. Mathematically speaking, the equations governing the dynamics of the matter, the state of the matter, and the radiation field are coupled. The strength and kind of the coupling again depends on the object being investigated. One extreme is the case where a detailed coupling between radiation and matter is crucial and a careful treatment of the radiation field and the dynamics and

state of the matter is required, for example when studying the acceleration of stellar winds. On the other hand, there are cases where the dynamical description of the matter alone is the most important thing and radiation is included only in some parameterized form, for example when investigating the density and velocity distribution of the matter in binary star systems.

For the investigation of systems where matter and radiation interact there are two complementary approaches. One is to gather observational data to improve the knowledge about reality. The other is to build more or less simple models to better understand the physics of the objects. For some simple problems this can be done analytically, which has the advantage that analytical solutions often provide great physical insight. For more complex situations numerical simulations have become one of the most important tools nowadays for studying the interaction of radiation and matter. But despite the advances in numerical techniques and the increase in computer power also the numerical models have to be restricted in one way or the other. A tradeoff has to be made between geometry and physics. Within the latter, another tradeoff has to be made between the detailed treatment of radiation and hydrodynamics, additional physical processes, their interactions, and time dependence. Consequently, there is not one approach but a whole bunch of approaches, each of them emphasising other aspects, depending on the object under consideration. Not surprising, the numerical techniques applied are manifold as well. As far as multidimensional radiative transfer it may be pointed out here that the interest of applied mathematics in this problem has arisen only during the last few years.

Within this thesis three different aspects of the interaction of matter and radiation are emphasised and three different solutions are going to be presented, each of them with its particular advantages and shortcomings. The following examples, which are not intended as a complete survey, shall give an idea of present day work in the field and provide the framework this thesis has to be seen in.

The most detailed treatment of radiation processes is probably done in applications dealing with *stellar atmospheres* and, in particular, the *driving of stellar winds*. This requires some dynamical description of the matter as well and the necessary tradeoff is to restrict the geometry to 1D mostly. In addition, many approaches neglect the time dependence and consider *static atmospheres* only. Among the most prominent and widely used examples here are possibly the NLTE (non-local-thermodynamic-equilibrium) model atmospheres by Kurucz (see [80] and references therein) for main sequence stars of spectral type roughly between G and B. His code ATLAS12 uses plane parallel geometry and impresses by the inclusion of all ions of the elements up to Zn and the first five ions of the heavier elements up to Es. Assuming plane parallel or spherically symmetric geometry, NLTE atmospheres of other types of stars are being in-

investigated as well, for example those of hot white dwarfs (see e.g. Dreizler and Werner [31], Kubát [77], Lanz and Hubeny [83], Napiwotzki [101]), of central stars of planetary nebulae (see e.g. Kubát [78]), or of stars of spectral type from A up to O (see e.g. Pauldrach et al. [114], Santolaya-Ray et al. [122], Dreizler and Werner [30]). In Hubeny and Lanz [55] a detailed description of their numerical method can be found. It has to be stressed that such stellar atmosphere models nowadays usually agree incredibly well with observational data. Another, more complicated example from the general field of stellar atmospheres is the acceleration of Wolf-Rayet winds, a type of massive stars in a late stage of evolution with very heavy mass loss. Schmutz [130], for example, applies a numerical model which is spherically symmetric and includes a co-moving frame code for the computation of a H/He NLTE atmosphere, a Monte Carlo type solver allowing to solve the transfer equation for tens of thousands of spectral lines, and a CAK model (see Castor et al. [16]) for the computation of the force exerted by the photons on the matter. In particular, his model is capable of treating line-blanketing effects. A detailed description of the numerical model can be found in Schaerer and Schmutz [123]. In the last few years, substantial progress has been made also in this field. However, comparison with observational data is not yet as satisfying as for main sequence stars. Applying *time dependent models to stellar atmospheres* additional features can be investigated, as for example the existence of instabilities in hot stellar winds which lead to a 'clumping' of the wind, the question of disk formation in rotating hot star winds, or the radiative braking in colliding hot-star winds (see e.g. Owocki [111], Owocki et al. [112], and Gayley et al. [46]). However, the price to be paid for a time dependent model is that less detailed physics can be included as compared to the case of stationary stellar atmosphere models.

For other applications, geometry is of chief interest and, therefore, concessions have to be made to the physics. One may concentrate on the radiation field and the ionization state of the matter while assuming the density, velocity, and maybe temperature distribution of the matter to be known. As a particular subclass one may consider the work on modeling of *polarization effects in the presence of complex density distributions*. Schmid [128], [127] applies a Monte Carlo approach to investigate polarization due to Raman- and Rayleigh-scattering, especially in symbiotic double star systems. For his approach it is, however, necessary that the 3D density distribution can be described analytically. Monte Carlo simulations have also been applied to envelopes of young stellar objects (see e.g. Voshchinnikov et al. [153]), to accretion disks in AGNs (see e.g. Agol and Blaes [1]), or to dusty galaxies (see e.g. Bianchi et al. [13]). In the frame of his thesis, Dittmann [27] has presented an approach which is capable of computing polarized radiative transfer for arbitrary 3D geometries. He applies short characteristics, an ALI-scheme (Approximate-Lambda-Iteration), and an Orthomin algorithm for additional acceleration of convergence. Yet another approach, involving long characteristics, has been

suggested by Hillier [51]. The work on *unpolarized, multidimensional, optically thick radiative transfer* includes applications like the study of optically thick accretion disks (see e.g. Papkalla [113]), line formation in stellar envelopes (see e.g. Hummel and Hanuschik [56] for Be stars), emission of disks in AGNs (see e.g. Stenholm [140], Wehrse et al. [160]), or protostellar disks (e.g. Sonnhalter et al. [136], Men'shchikov and Henning [93]). The techniques employed range from short characteristic approaches, as described by Kunasz and Auer [79], to finite element approaches as described in Kanschat [68] and Turek [145]. As one of the approaches presented in this thesis deals with the numerical treatment of 3D optically thick radiative transfer a more comprehensive survey of presently employed techniques is given in Chapter 3 of this thesis. Simplifying the problem by assuming *mainly optically thin, nebular conditions* allows to include more atomic processes and data. The second approach to 3D NLTE radiative transfer presented in this thesis belongs into this category. It is similar to the 2D approach described in Vogel [152], Nussbaumer and Vogel [106], and Nussbaumer and Walder [108].

Focusing on time dependence again, reducing the treatment of radiation to mainly optically thin radiative transfer but including hydrodynamics, high level approaches designed for the investigation of the *evolution of planetary nebula* in 1D and 2D are feasible. The hitherto most comprehensive models in this field are probably those of Frank and Mellema [43], Mellema and Frank [91], and Marten and Szczerba [89], the last being 1D only. Their models are able to treat time dependent photo- and collisional ionization of gaseous nebula together with a consistent energy balance. At each timestep, this information is then used as a source term in the hydrodynamical equations governing the motion of the matter. The models reveal the importance of ionization fronts in the evolution of planetary nebulae. Simulations by Mellema [90] suggest that whether a planetary nebula is able to develop a bipolar shape depends also on the time needed to ionize the wind material of the AGB star.

Reducing, finally, the treatment of radiation to parameterized cooling but keeping the time dependence of the model leads to *applications where hydrodynamics and geometry dominate* the model. In some sense this may be regarded as the opposite extreme compared to the stellar atmosphere problems touched above. Again there is a wide variety of applications, reaching from 3D simulation of the distribution of circumstellar matter in double star systems as performed by Walder [154] to the study of galaxy formation (see e.g. Weinberg et al. [161] or Tissera et al. [144]). A particular example is the investigation of the stability properties of the collision zone of radiative colliding flows. The topic is of particular importance in connection with structure formation, for example the formation of cometary knots, stars, or galaxies (see e.g. [57], [41], or [33]). In addition, such unstable interaction zones can have a large impact on the emission of an object. The last part of this thesis deals with this topic,

where further references can be found as well.

To conclude this section a *quick glance beyond astrophysics* seems appropriate. The problem of radiation and its interaction with matter, and of radiative transfer in particular, occurs in such different fields as room climate engineering, temperature measurements of melts, the optimization of combustion devices, atmospherical sciences, or in connection with laser technology. Details and additional applications can be found, for example, in [92]. Unfortunately, this variety of applications seems to be much less well known than the variety of applications of hydrodynamics.

1.2 The contents of this work

The astrophysical topic laying at the beginning of this work was the investigation of double star systems. Being already able to perform 3D hydrodynamical simulations of colliding winds in such system (see Walder [154]) two questions, among many others, arose: What spectrum does such a model emit and what are the properties of the interaction zone itself? The first question led to the development of methods for the numerical solution of the 3D radiative transfer problem under NLTE conditions, while the second question led to the investigation of the stability properties of radiative, hypersonically colliding flows in one and two spatial dimensions. Both are relatively young topics in the sense that they have become accessible to numerical simulations only during the last decade. The reason for this are the strong increase in computer power during that time as well as new, efficient numerical techniques, in particular for radiative transfer. Although initiated by the investigation of binary star systems, both topics reach beyond the subject of double star systems.

A first part of this thesis deals with the numerical solution of the 3D NLTE radiative transfer problem under optically thick conditions for a given matter and velocity distribution. A second complex takes up the problem of NLTE radiative transfer for a given matter and velocity distribution under the simplifying assumption of nebular conditions. The last part of this thesis is devoted to the investigation of the stability properties of radiative colliding flows using numerical simulations. Seeming unrelated at first glance, the three topics can actually be regarded as complementary in the sense that they mutually provide input for each other. A brief survey of the contents and the results of all three parts is given in the following.

1.2.1 3D radiative transfer

Both approaches to be presented aim at computing the emitted spectrum of a complex 3D matter and velocity distribution under NLTE conditions. The

density and velocity of the matter are assumed to be known and unaltered by the radiation field while the ionization state and the level populations are computed. The temperature is assumed to be known in the first approach and is computed consistently with the radiation field in the second approach. An outline of the NLTE radiative transfer problem is given in Chapter 2. Some simplifying physical approximations are discussed in the same chapter.

The first approach, within which the code TR3D has been developed, is designed for fully 3D, optically thick, NLTE radiative transfer of moving media. A description of the approach is given in Chapter 4 to Chapter 6. A concise survey of other presently applied methods for multidimensional radiative transfer is given in Chapter 3.

The task is demanding in several ways. On the one hand, there is the sheer dimensionality of the 3D problem. The description of the radiation field requires three spatial dimensions, two dimensions describing the direction of propagation of the radiation, and a one dimensional frequency space. The atomic level populations are a function of 3D space as well. A challenge for nowadays computer resources. On the other hand, the physics to be included is, in principle, arbitrarily complex. A summary of the physics actually included in the approach presented here is given in Chapter 2.

The difference to previous approaches lies mainly in the solution of the transfer equation, described in Chapter 4. Unlike in one dimensional simulations, the solution of the transfer equation alone is already quite difficult in two or three spatial dimensions. A generalized mean intensity approach is applied, which is based on an idea by Turek [145]. The spatial discretization uses an equidistant Cartesian grid and first order finite differences together with up-winding. A discrete ordinate technique is applied to account for the different directions of propagation. The main advantages of the presented mean intensity approach are the only weak dependence of the convergence properties on the spatial discretization and the moderate memory requirements.

The solution of the rate equilibrium equations together with the conservation laws is not as elaborate. Non-linearities are handled by fix-point iteration. The remaining linear system is solved using Householder transformations.

For the treatment of optically thick lines Sobolev theory is applied (see Section 2.3). The expressions for the Sobolev coefficients in 3D, which are not found in standard text books, had to be derived. For this derivation, similar approximations and ideas were used as for the spherically symmetric case.

Although use has been made of existing ideas, this approach basically had to be developed from scratch. It is, therefore, still on a somewhat technical and experimental level although applications to 'real size problems' will soon be possible. Two major shortcomings of the present implementation are the lack of an adaptive grid and the mere iterative coupling between the transfer equation

and the statistical equilibrium equations. Among the intended applications are the investigation of H_α line profile variations in symbiotic systems and the modeling of the irradiation of the stellar atmosphere of one star by the other in a double star system.

The second approach, within which the code D3NEBEL has been developed, is applicable under nebular conditions only. It is described in Chapter 7. The code is capable of computing Doppler broadened emission line profiles as viewed by several observers as well as the ionization structure and temperature of the matter. Additional advantages are the great number of atomic processes and atomic data included and an adaptive spatial step size (see below).

The 3D structure is captured by several, individual, 1D rays, all emerging from the same central source of radiation, along which the transfer problem under the assumption of nebular conditions is solved. The contributions of these individual rays are then summed up. There is no other interaction between the rays, which led to the notion of 'quasi 3D' instead of full 3D. However, under nebular conditions 'quasi 3D' mostly is nearly as good as full 3D.

For the solution along each individual ray a previously existing 1D code is applied which automatically adapts step size in radial direction. The emission computed at a particular radius point along a ray is then weighted with the appropriate emission measure and Doppler shifted according to the location of the different observers. The existing 1D code and the physics contained in it are described in Nussbaumer and Schild [103], Vogel [152], and Schild [125].

The main advantage of this second approach lies in the comparably low computational costs, mainly due to the only 'quasi-3D' geometry and the assumption of nebular conditions, and despite the inclusion of a considerable amount of atomic data and the use of several thousand frequency points, which guarantee an excellent frequency resolution. Another advantage is the already mentioned automatic adaptation of the spatial step size along each ray which allows good resolution of spatially narrow structures. The major shortcomings of this method are its restriction to nebular conditions and the 'quasi-3D' geometry. The code in its present form provides a valuable tool for the investigation of symbiotic systems, as demonstrated in Chapter 8.

1.2.2 Stability of radiative colliding flows

The last part of this thesis, Chapter 9 to Chapter 11, is devoted to the investigation of the stability properties of radiative, hypersonic colliding flows by means of time dependent 1D and 2D hydrodynamical simulations. The main result of this part may be summarized in the observation that unstable behavior of such flows is rather the rule than the exception.

The difficulties of these investigations lay in the required spatial resolution,

in the presented calculations typically four orders of magnitude in 2D, the large number of timesteps necessary to follow the unstable evolution, and the post processing of huge data sets.

The physical model uses Euler equations including a source term to account for energy loss due to radiative cooling. In contrast to the rest of this thesis, radiation processes here are not considered in detail as this would be by far too costly. Instead, radiative cooling is accounted for by a parameterized radiative loss function. The simulations were performed with the AMRCART code by M. Berger and R. LeVeque (see e.g. Berger and LeVeque [7], [8]), which has been adapted to astrophysical purposes by Walder [154]. In particular, this adaptation included the extension to 3D and the introduction of source terms. It is an adaptive mesh refinement code on Cartesian grids for the solution of Euler equations with source terms.

The basic pattern of the collision zone consists of two shock waves which cool more or less efficiently, depending on post shock temperature and density, and a layer of cooled, dense gas separating the two shock waves. In this dense, cold layer the previously shocked and then cooled gas is accumulated.

Already the 1D simulations, described in Chapter 10, provide valuable insight. They demonstrate, for example, that the layer of cold, dense gas and the unstable cooling zones of the shocks have usually to be viewed as a couple systems. The instability of the cooling layer generates pressure waves in the cold, dense layer. In turn, the dynamics of this layer influence the rear boundary of the cooling layer. Also, some experience could be gained about the locations of different stability regions on a 'real' cooling curve. Finally, the 1D results impressively demonstrate the importance of the spatial resolution. The presented results could be obtained only due to the very high spatial resolution provided by the the AMRCART code.

More interesting, however, are the results achieved by the 2D numerical simulations presented in Chapter 11. The simulations reveal that shocks in hypersonic flow collisions are unstable, leading to a complexly structured, turbulent interaction zone. Due to the additional spatial degree of freedom, the results are more complex than in 1D and one may distinguish between two basically different situations. An asymmetric situation where only one of the two shocks confining the collision zone cools while the other is basically adiabatic, and a symmetric situation where both shocks cool. The symmetric case is characterized by strong global bending of the cold gas layer and by an often filamentary appearance of the cold layer. In the asymmetric case, discussed in more detail in Chapter 11, filaments and knots of cooled gas can break off the bulge of cold matter and drift into the adiabatic, shocked region where they lead to turbulent mixing of cold and hot gas. Due to the great computational effort numerical results here are still comparatively rare.

From an astronomical point of view, these results are particularly important

in connection with structure formation, for example in planetary nebula or supernova remnants. Radiative shocks may even trigger the formation of stars or galaxies. The instability of the collision zone probably also strongly affects the emitted spectrum of an object. In particular, the turbulent mixing of cold and hot gas possibly leads to efficient X-ray emission and the supersonic turbulence in the cold, dense layer may cause significant emission line broadening.

Part I

Radiation and matter: Some basic physics

Chapter 2

NLTE radiative transfer

The problem of radiative transfer under conditions of non-local thermodynamic equilibrium (NLTE) basically consists of determining consistent values for the radiation field and the state of the matter. In the frame of this work, the state of the matter includes only the ionization state of the matter, the atomic level populations, and possibly the temperature of the matter. The fact that the radiation field can alter the dynamics of the matter will not be considered in the following. In principle, the problem can then be regarded as being divided into two parts: the radiative transfer equation, which describes the transport of radiation in the presence of matter, and the statistical equilibrium equations together with some conservation laws, which describe the state of the matter in the presence of a radiation field.

Section 2.1 and 2.2 will focus on some aspects of the general problem of NLTE radiative transfer. Two simplifying approximations are outlined in Section 2.3. The intention is to provide some physical background and some basic formulas before discussing numerical solutions and results in later chapters.

Unless otherwise stated, the material presented in this chapter is taken from the classical books of Mihalas [96] and Jefferies [63] where further details can be found.

Notation: For the discussion of the atomic physics the following notation will be used. i , j , and k denote the level, ionization state, and chemical species of an ion. N_i , N_{ij} , or N_{ijk} are the corresponding NLTE level populations in part./cm^3 , N_i^* are the corresponding LTE (local thermodynamic equilibrium) populations as defined in Section 2.2. In bound-free transitions, the *index* κ denotes the continuum state following the bound levels i , and N_κ is the population of the ground level of this ionized state. In bound-bound transitions, the indices l and u denote the lower and upper level.

2.1 The radiative transfer equation

There are several ways to derive the equation of radiative transfer in the presence of matter. In astrophysics a somewhat phenomenological derivation is often encountered, where, roughly speaking, one considers the gains and losses for a directed beam of radiation, the specific intensity I . This derivation is going to be briefly outlined below. Another possibility is to derive the radiative transfer equation in the frame of kinetic theory using Boltzmann's equation. Here the system of matter and radiation is described by two species of particles, a species N for the photons and a species M for the matter, and their distribution functions. While the resulting description of such a two component mixture is very complex in general, it usually simplifies enormously for the case of photons and matter: The transport of photons in the presence of matter can (usually) be described by means of the linear Boltzmann equation. This kind of derivation shall now be sketched first.

Derivation by means of Boltzmann equation

The following is taken from the book by Cercignani [17]. Consider first a gas consisting of only one species with distribution function $g(x, \xi, t)$ where x , ξ , and t denote the position, velocity, and time respectively. The Boltzmann equation can then be written as

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} + \xi \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} = \int de' d\xi_* V \frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} (g' g'_* - g g_*). \quad (2.1)$$

The superscripts $'$ and the subscripts $*$ of g refer to the velocities ξ , for example $g_* = g(x, \xi_*, t)$. In particular, the superscript $'$ refers to the velocities after the collision. V is given by $V = |\xi - \xi_*| = |\xi' - \xi'_*|$, and e' is defined by $\xi' - \xi'_* = V \cdot e'$. The differential scattering cross-section $d\sigma/d\Omega$ is a function of e , e' , and V .

Next consider a two-component mixture of a species M (matter later on), with distribution function g_0 , and a species N (photons later on), with distribution function g_1 . The Boltzmann equations for the two distribution functions are

$$\frac{\partial g_j}{\partial t} + \xi \frac{\partial g_j}{\partial x} = \sum_{i=0}^1 \int de' d\xi_* V \frac{d\sigma_{ji}}{d\Omega} (g'_j g'_{i*} - g_j g_{i*}) \quad j = 0, 1. \quad (2.2)$$

Assume now that collisions of particles of species N with each other are negligible compared to collisions between particles of species N and species M. Assume further that these later collisions are again negligible compared to collisions of particles of species M with each other. For general species M and N this may be the case if species N has much lower density than species M.

For the particular case of photons (species N) and matter (species M), the case we are aiming at, these assumptions can be justified by the observation that photons hardly interact with each other, that they sometimes interact with matter particles, and that the matter particles among themselves collide very frequently.

If these assumptions about the frequency of different collision are fulfilled the distribution function g_0 of species M is not influenced by the distribution function g_1 of species N while the later is influenced by species M. If, in addition, species M is in equilibrium and hence has a Maxwellian velocity distribution G_0 , the Boltzmann equation describing the distribution function g_1 of species N becomes linear in g_1 . It can be written in the form (see p.165-167 in Cercignani [17])

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial t} + \xi \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial x} &= \int de' d\xi_* V \frac{d\sigma_{10}}{d\Omega} (g'_1 G'_{0*} - g_1 G_{0*}) \\ \iff \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial t} + \xi \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial x} &= \int K(\xi', \xi) g_1(\xi') d\xi' - \zeta(\xi) g_1(\xi). \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

Here $K(\xi', \xi)$ is the scattering kernel and $\zeta(\xi)$ is the collision frequency. Cercignani [17] points out that the linear collision operator appearing on the right hand side of eq. 2.3 has only one eigenfunction corresponding to the eigenvalue $\lambda = 0$, which physically means that there is just one conservation law in a collision. In fact, only the mass is conserved while energy and momentum may be exchanged between particles of species M and N.

One physical realization of such a system is obtained, as already mentioned, by identifying species N with photons and species M with general matter particles like electrons and ions. (Other possibility would be neutrons (N) in a gas moderator (M), or electrons (N) in a solid (M).) For the particular case of photons the velocity vector ξ has to be replaced by a direction vector $n = \xi/c$, where c is the speed of light. The distribution function g_{phot} is a function of x, n, t and the photon energy $h\nu$, h being the Planck constant: $g_{phot} = g_{phot}(x, n, \nu, t)$. Assuming that the photon energy is conserved in a scattering process one obtains

$$\frac{\partial g_{photo}}{\partial t} + cn \cdot \frac{\partial g_{photo}}{\partial x} = c\sigma_s \int K(n', n) g'_{photo} dn' - c(\sigma_a + \sigma_s) g_{photo} + S. \quad (2.4)$$

σ_a and σ_s denote the differential absorption and scattering cross-section. To account for emission which is not proportional to the photon distribution function g_{photo} an extra source term S has to be included in the Boltzmann equation.

Derivation using the specific intensity

More common in astrophysics is the description of the radiation field in terms of the specific intensity I . The specific intensity is defined such that the amount of

energy $d\mathcal{E}$ transported by radiation of frequencies $[\nu, \nu + d\nu]$ across an element of area dS into solid angle $d\omega$, associated with direction n , in a time interval dt is

$$d\mathcal{E} = I(x, n, \nu, t) dS \cos\theta d\omega d\nu dt \quad (2.5)$$

where θ is the angle between the direction of propagation n of the photons and the normal to the area dS . From this definition it can be seen that $I(x, n, \nu, t)$ is the energy at position x , traveling in direction n , with frequency ν , at time t . It has dimensions $\text{ergs cm}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ hz}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$. The radiative transfer equation can now be derived by studying the gains and losses the specific intensity $I(x, n, \nu, t)$ undergoes on a distance dx . In this way one finds that the radiative transfer equation for the time independent, unpolarized, and non-relativistic case in terms of $I(x, n, \nu, t)$ can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} n \nabla_x I(x, n, \nu) + \chi(x, n, \nu) I(x, n, \nu) = \\ \lambda(x, n, \nu) \int_0^\infty \int_{S^2} P(n, \nu; n', \nu') I(x, n', \nu') d\omega' d\nu' + f(x, n, \nu). \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

From left to right the four terms in eq. 2.6 represent: The transport of $I(x, n, \nu)$ in the direction of n , losses due to absorption and scattering out of direction n or frequency ν , gains due to scattering from directions n' and frequency ν' into direction n and frequency ν , gains due to atomic emission processes or external sources. The dimensions of the corresponding coefficients are cm^{-1} for χ and λ , and $\text{ergs cm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ hz}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$ for f .

Although not explicitly stated in eq. 2.6 it should be noted, for later use, that the coefficients χ , λ , and f depend on the atomic population numbers which, in turn, are determined by the radiation field. Detailed formulas for χ , λ , and f are given below.

The two descriptions of the radiation field, either in terms of a distribution function g or by the specific intensity I , are completely similar. The connection is obtained by observing that the number of photons crossing an element dS in time dt can be expressed as $g_{\text{phot}} c dt n dS d\omega d\nu$, so that the energy transported is $d\mathcal{E} = (ch\nu) g_{\text{phot}} dS \cos\theta d\omega d\nu dt$. Comparison with eq. 2.5 then yields

$$I(x, n, \nu, t) = (ch\nu) g_{\text{phot}}(x, n, \nu, t). \quad (2.7)$$

2.1.1 Coefficients of the transfer equation

The coefficients χ , λ , and f of the radiative transfer equation contain contributions from different interaction processes between radiation and matter. For given atomic level populations all contributions can, in principle, be computed. Some of the most important contributions to these coefficients are discussed

in the following and the corresponding formulas are given. As in the frame of this work the radiative transfer equation is solved for *continuum radiation only*, this discussion is restricted to such processes. The spatial variable x is omitted, although all but the atomic quantities may depend on x .

The scattering term

Scattering usually alters the direction of propagation of a photon as well as its frequency. Typical examples of continuum scattering processes are the scattering of photons by a free electron (Thomson or Compton scattering), the scattering by dust (Mie scattering) if the temperature is low enough, or the interaction of a photon with two bound states of an atom or an ion (Rayleigh scattering). As an opacity source scattering, compared to absorption, becomes important only for densities higher than about 10^{10} part./cm³. This is due to the usually much smaller scattering cross-sections compared to absorption. However, in high density environments such as atmospheres of hot stars, electron scattering is one of the most important opacity sources.

The changes in frequency and direction of propagation due to scattering are described by a redistribution function

$$P(n, \nu; n', \nu') d\nu' d\nu (d\omega'/4\pi)(d\omega/4\pi) \quad (2.8)$$

which gives the joint probability of a photon being scattered from direction n' and associated solid angle $d\omega'$ and frequency range $[\nu', \nu' + d\nu']$ into solid angle $d\omega$ in direction n and frequency range $[\nu, \nu + d\nu]$. For *coherent* scattering and together with a frequency dependent scattering cross-section $\sigma(\nu)$ this yields an emissivity per particle

$$\eta^S(x, n, \nu) = \sigma(\nu) \int_{S^2} P(n; n') I(x, n', \nu) d\omega' / (4\pi). \quad (2.9)$$

For continuum scattering the assumption of coherent scattering can be justified by observing that the frequency distribution of continuum radiation is smooth and essentially constant over a typical frequency shift occurring in a scattering process. If the scattering is further assumed to be *isotropic* this expression simplifies to

$$\eta^S(x, \nu) = \sigma(\nu) \int_{S^2} I(x, n', \nu) d\omega' / (4\pi). \quad (2.10)$$

The scattering term used in eq. 2.6 is then obtained by replacing $\sigma(\nu)$ in eq. 2.10 by

$$\lambda(\nu) = \sum_l N_l \sigma_l(\nu), \quad (2.11)$$

where the sum runs over the different scattering processes and N_l is the corresponding number density of scatterers.

In TR3D only Thomson scattering is included, whose cross-section $\sigma(\nu)$ and corresponding coefficient $\lambda(\nu)$ are independent of frequency,

$$\lambda = N_e \sigma_e = N_e 8\pi e^4 / 3m^2 c^4 = N_e 6.65 \cdot 10^{-25}. \quad (2.12)$$

However, Thomson scattering is actually not isotropic but has an angle dependent redistribution function $P(n, n') = 3/4(1 + \cos^2\Phi)$, where $\Phi = n \cdot n'$.

The extinction term

The specific intensity $I(x, n, \nu)$ can be reduced either due to absorption of photons by matter or due to scattering of photons out of frequency ν or direction n . This yields an extinction coefficient $\chi = \kappa + \lambda$, where κ denotes the absorption coefficient and λ the scattering coefficient described above. Absorption may be distinguished from scattering by saying that in an absorption process, in contrast to a scattering process, at least a significant part of the energy and momentum of the absorbed photon is transferred to the matter. That this distinction between absorption and elastic as well as inelastic scattering is not always as clear as it may seem now is nicely illustrated in Mihalas [96].

Probably the most important continuum absorption process is the ionization of an atom by a photon. Although there are other continuum absorption processes only photoionization is included in TR3D and will be considered in the following. Let $\alpha_{i\kappa}(\nu)$ denote the cross-section for photoionization from level i . The frequency dependent absorption coefficient due to photoionization is then given by

$$\kappa_{ion}(\nu) = \sum_i N_i \alpha_{i\kappa}(\nu). \quad (2.13)$$

Part of these absorptions are compensated by stimulated radiative recombination whose coefficient is given by

$$\zeta_{stim}(\nu) = \sum_i N_\kappa \left(\frac{N_i}{N_\kappa} \right)^* \alpha_{i\kappa}(\nu) e^{-h\nu/kT}. \quad (2.14)$$

κ in eq. 2.6 includes both contributions,

$$\kappa(\nu) = \sum_i \left(N_i \alpha_{i\kappa}(\nu) - N_\kappa \left(\frac{N_i}{N_\kappa} \right)^* \alpha_{i\kappa}(\nu) e^{-h\nu/kT} \right). \quad (2.15)$$

For the cross-sections $\alpha_{i\kappa}(\nu)$ different fit formulas depending on the particular element and transition have been suggested (see e.g. by Koester [74], Mihalas [95], Seaton [133], or Osterbrock [110]). For example, for the ground level of hydrogen $\alpha_{1\kappa}(\nu)$ may be approximated by

$$\alpha_{1\kappa}(\nu) = \alpha_{1\kappa}(\nu_0) \left(\frac{\nu_0}{\nu} \right)^3 g, \quad (2.16)$$

where $\alpha_{1\kappa}(\nu_0) = 6.3 \cdot 10^{-18} \text{ cm}^2$, g is a gaunt factor of order unity, and $\nu_0 = 3.29 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ is the threshold frequency.

The emission term

The emission term in eq. 2.6 accounts for atomic continuum emission. Atomic continuum emission can be caused by several mechanisms, among them radiative recombination, dielectronic recombination, or three-body-recombination. The first of them can be split into two parts actually. One is spontaneous radiative recombination, leading to a continuum emission coefficient

$$f_{spont}(\nu) = N_\kappa \left(\frac{N_i}{N_\kappa} \right)^* \alpha_{i\kappa}(\nu) \frac{2h\nu^3}{c^2} e^{-h\nu/kT}. \quad (2.17)$$

The other is stimulated radiative recombination, leading to a continuum emission coefficient

$$f_{stim}(\nu) = N_\kappa \left(\frac{N_i}{N_\kappa} \right)^* \alpha_{i\kappa}(\nu) J(\nu) e^{-h\nu/kT}, \quad (2.18)$$

where J_ν denotes the zeroth moment of the radiation field, its mean intensity at frequency ν ,

$$J_\nu = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{S^2} I_\nu(n) d\omega. \quad (2.19)$$

However, the influence of stimulated emission has already been included in the absorption coefficient $\kappa(\nu)$ in eq. 2.15. Therefore, it must not be included again in f .

Under LTE conditions there exists a simple relationship between the continuum emission and absorption coefficient, known as Kirchhoff's law:

$$f^*(\nu) = \kappa^*(\nu) B_\nu(T). \quad (2.20)$$

$B_\nu(T)$ denotes the Planck function.

2.2 Statistical equilibrium equations and conservation laws

While Section 2.1 dealt with the problem of computing the radiation field once the atomic level populations N_i are known the present section is devoted to the determination of the NLTE populations N_i for a given radiation field. Consider first the level populations under LTE conditions. There the state of the gas is specified uniquely by two thermodynamic variables, for example temperature

and particle density, via the equilibrium equations of statistical mechanics. In particular, the same temperature applies in the calculation of the velocity distribution functions of atoms, ions, and electrons (Maxwellian distribution), the distribution of atoms and ions over all states (Boltzmann-Saha equations), and the distribution of thermal emission (Planck function). The microscopic requirement for thermodynamic equilibrium is that for all processes the rate at which each process occurs is exactly balanced by the rate at which its inverse occurs.

The population of level i of an atom of species k in ionization state j is then determined by a Boltzmann-distribution

$$(N_{ijk}/N_{0jk})^* = (g_{ijk}/g_{0jk})e^{-\chi_{ijk}/kT}. \quad (2.21)$$

χ_{ijk} denotes the excitation energy relative to the ground state of the atom and g_{ijk} is the statistical weight. Successive states of ionization are linked via the Saha ionization equation,

$$N_{ijk}^* = N_{0,j+1,k}^* N_e^* (g_{ijk}/g_{0,j+1,k}) C_\kappa T^{-\frac{3}{2}} e^{(\chi_{\kappa jk} - \chi_{ijk})/kT}. \quad (2.22)$$

$\chi_{\kappa jk}$ denotes the ionization potential of ion j of species k , T is the common temperature of the matter and the radiation field, and C_κ is a constant given by $2.07 \cdot 10^{-16}$ in cgs units.

Also under NLTE conditions the equations describing LTE level populations are used. More precisely, they are used to facilitate the computation of NLTE recombination rates, as for example in eq. 2.29, where ratios $N_{0,j+1,k}^*/N_{i,j,k}^*$ of LTE populations appear. Under LTE conditions, eq. 2.22 provides these ratios as a function of N_e^* and T . Under NLTE conditions, eq. 2.22 is used to *define* these LTE ratios by replacing N_e^* by its NLTE value N_e and T by the temperature of the matter.

2.2.1 Statistical equilibrium equations

Radiative processes, like photoionization, are in detailed balance only if the radiation field is isotropic and has a Planck distribution at the correct temperature $T_{rad} = T_{matter}$. If this is not the case deviations from LTE occur and it is no longer possible to express the atomic level populations in terms of the temperature and particle density alone. Instead it becomes necessary to go to a somewhat more basic level, the rate equations or statistical equilibrium equations, together with some conservation laws. For an atomic state r the statistical equilibrium equations basically look like

$$\frac{dN_r}{dt} = \sum_{s \neq r} (R_{sr} + C_{sr}) N_s - (R_{rs} + C_{rs}) N_r. \quad (2.23)$$

R_{sr} and C_{sr} denote the radiative and collisional transition rates from state s to state r where both s and r may be bound or free. It should be noted that collisionally dominated processes, like the velocity distribution of electrons or even radiative recombination, usually still occur at their equilibrium values. Before providing detailed formulas for these transition rates a few remarks on the system of rate equations seem appropriate.

In the stationary case this system of equations is singular if the number of particles for each species is conserved (no chemical reactions, fission, or fusion). A regular system can be obtained again if one equation for each species is omitted. But then the system can be solved for ratios of populations only and not for the populations themselves. Another possibility is to replace one of the rate equations for each species by the conservation law for the total number of particles of this species. The resulting system of equations can then be solved for the populations.

The collisional transition rates C_{rs} depend on the electron density N_e . Usually, N_e itself will be an unknown which has to be determined such that charge conservation is fulfilled (see below). This introduces a non-linearity.

In the stationary case, one may also require the populations to be in accordance with the temperature of the matter. For a given population one can compute the amount of cooling and heating of the matter due to atomic transitions. For example, collisionally excited lines lead to a loss of thermal energy of the matter. Photoionization, on the other hand, will convert energy of the radiation field into thermal energy of the electrons and, finally, of the matter as a whole. So, on the one hand, the level populations depend on the temperature of the matter but, on the other hand, they also determine the amount of cooling and heating. This introduces another non-linearity.

Atomic transitions

In contrast to the transfer equation where only continuum radiation and continuum processes were considered, the *inclusion of line processes*, i.e. bound-bound transitions, is crucial for the determination of the atomic level populations. On the other hand, free-free processes have no influence on the level populations and are not considered in the following. It can be shown that for bound-free processes between states i, j, k and $i, j + 1, k$ it is sufficient to consider recombination from the ground state $1, j + 1, k$ into any excited state i, j, k and ionization from any state i, j, k into the ground state $1, j + 1, k$.

Radiative transitions

Bound-bound transitions: Bound-bound transition rates may be written in terms of Einstein transition probabilities B_{lu} , B_{ul} and A_{ul} where

$$\begin{aligned} B_{ul} &= (c^2/2h\nu_{ul}^3)A_{ul} \\ B_{lu} &= g_u/g_l B_{ul}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.24)$$

In terms of Einstein transition probabilities, the number of absorptions ($N_l R_{lu}$), of stimulated emissions ($N_u R_{ul,stim}$), and of spontaneous emissions ($N_u R_{ul,spont}$) in a line are given by

$$N_l R_{lu} = N_l B_{lu} \int_0^\infty \phi_\nu J_\nu d\nu \quad (2.25)$$

$$N_u R_{ul,stim} = N_u B_{ul} \int_0^\infty \phi_\nu J_\nu d\nu \quad (2.26)$$

$$N_u R_{ul,spont} = N_u A_{ul}. \quad (2.27)$$

Here ϕ_ν denotes the line profile function which is assumed to be the same for absorption and emission. It is necessary to introduce such a function as the upper and lower energy level of the transition, and therefore the line, are not infinitely sharp. The function ϕ_ν then describes the fact that different parts of the broadened line interact at different strength with the radiation field J_ν . As J_ν usually considerably varies over the profile function ϕ_ν the integrals cannot be simplified. (See also Section 2.3.)

Bound-free transitions: In the following, the radiative rates from a bound level i into the continuum κ are considered. Let $\alpha_{i\kappa}(\nu)$ denote the corresponding photoionization cross-section at frequency ν . The number of photoionizations ($N_i R_{i\kappa}$), spontaneous emissions ($N_\kappa R_{\kappa i,spont}$), and stimulated emissions ($N_\kappa R_{\kappa i,stim}$) are given by

$$N_i R_{i\kappa} = N_i 4\pi \int_{\nu_0}^\infty \alpha_{i\kappa}(\nu) (h\nu)^{-1} J_\nu d\nu, \quad (2.28)$$

$$N_\kappa R_{\kappa i,spont} = N_\kappa \left(\frac{N_i}{N_\kappa} \right)^* 4\pi \int_{\nu_0}^\infty \frac{\alpha_{i\kappa}(\nu)}{h\nu} (2h\nu^3/c^2) e^{-h\nu/kT} d\nu, \quad (2.29)$$

$$N_\kappa R_{\kappa i,stim} = N_\kappa \left(\frac{N_i}{N_\kappa} \right)^* 4\pi \int_{\nu_0}^\infty \frac{\alpha_{i\kappa}(\nu)}{h\nu} J_\nu e^{-h\nu/kT} d\nu. \quad (2.30)$$

As the integrand in eq. 2.28 and 2.30 depends on the radiation field J_ν these integrals cannot be parameterized and have to be evaluated numerically. More details on this point are given in section 5.3.

Collisional transitions

Bound-bound transitions: Consider transitions from lower level l to upper level u where both levels are bound. Let $\sigma_{lu}(\xi)$ denote the cross-section for excitation from level l to level u due to electrons with kinetic energy ξ . If $f(\xi)d\xi$ represents the fraction of electrons with kinetic energy in the range $[\xi, \xi + d\xi]$ the rate of excitation due to electron collisions is given by

$$C_{lu} = N_e \int_{\xi_0}^{\infty} \sigma_{lu}(\xi) \sqrt{\frac{2\xi}{m}} f(\xi) d\xi, \quad (2.31)$$

where ξ_0 denotes the kinetic energy corresponding to the excitation energy. For the reverse process of collisional de-excitation one obtains

$$C_{ul} = N_e \int_0^{\infty} \sigma_{ul}(\xi - \xi_0) \sqrt{\frac{2(\xi - \xi_0)}{m}} f(\xi - \xi_0) d(\xi - \xi_0). \quad (2.32)$$

It can be shown (Jefferies [63]) that for all $\xi \geq \xi_0$ the cross-sections for collisional excitation and de-excitation are related through

$$\xi \sigma_{lu}(\xi) = \frac{g_u}{g_l} (\xi - \xi_0) \sigma_{ul}(\xi - \xi_0). \quad (2.33)$$

For a Maxwellian distribution at temperature T

$$f(\xi) = \frac{2\pi}{(\pi kT)^{3/2}} \sqrt{\xi} e^{(-\xi/kT)}, \quad (2.34)$$

and making use of eq. 2.33 the above collisional rates become

$$C_{lu} = N_e \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi m}} \left(\frac{2}{kT} \right)^{(3/2)} \int_{\xi_0}^{\infty} \sigma_{lu}(\xi) \xi e^{(-\xi/kT)} d\xi, \quad (2.35)$$

$$C_{ul} = C_{lu} \frac{g_l}{g_u} e^{\xi_0/kT}. \quad (2.36)$$

What remains is the difficult task of determining the cross-sections $\sigma_{lu}(\xi)$. Several fit formulas have been suggested for $\sigma_{lu}(\xi)$ and the corresponding integral. For optically permitted transitions (i.e. electric dipole transitions) a so-called dipole approximation, given by Seaton [134] and van Regemorter [148], is possible for $\sigma_{lu}(\xi)$. For neutral atoms the excitation rate in cgs units can be expressed as, following again van Regemorter [148],

$$C_{lu} = 2.16\alpha^{-1.68} e^{-\alpha} T^{-3/2} f N_e, \quad (2.37)$$

where f is the oscillator strength for the corresponding optical transition. For positive ions this formula is modified to

$$C_{lu} = 3.9\alpha^{-1} e^{-\alpha} T^{-3/2} f N_e. \quad (2.38)$$

For transitions which are optically forbidden, the dipole approximation cannot be used. Instead, Burgess [15] has studied such transitions by using a classical approximation which treats the electron-atom collision as a binary encounter between two electrons. For TR3D further fit formulas have been taken from the papers of Berrington et al. [11] and Benson and Kulander [5].

Bound-free transitions: Similar to the case of bound-bound transitions described above, the rate of collisional ionization due to electrons having a Maxwellian velocity distribution is given by

$$C_{i\kappa} = N_e \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi m}} \left(\frac{2}{kT} \right)^{3/2} \int_{\xi_0}^{\infty} d\xi \int_0^{\xi - \xi_0} \sigma_{i\kappa}(\xi, \zeta) \xi e^{-\xi/kT} d\zeta, \quad (2.39)$$

where $\sigma_{i\kappa}(\xi, \zeta)$ is the cross-section for the process in which an electron of energy ξ produces an ion together with a pair of electrons of energy ζ and $\xi - \xi_0 - \zeta$, where ξ_0 is the ionization potential of the atom in state l . Jefferies [63] gives for the formula an approximation which, in cgs units, reads

$$C_{i\kappa} = N_e 1.55 \cdot 10^{13} T^{-1/2} \bar{g} a(0) e^{-\alpha} \alpha^{-1}, \quad (2.40)$$

where $a(0)$ is the photoionization cross-section at threshold, $\alpha = \xi_0/kT$, and $\bar{g}$ lies between 0.1 and 0.3, depending on the charge of the ion.

Dielectronic recombination and autoionization

Schematically, dielectronic recombination can be described as

where nl denotes the bound electron in its ground state and $n'l'$ and $n''l''$ denote bound electrons in an excited state. The upper index m denotes the net charge of the ion. Competing with the second, stabilizing transition of dielectronic recombination is the process of autoionization,

Although important in many cases these processes are not included in TR3D and are, therefore, not discussed here any further. More details can be found, for example, in Nussbaumer and Storey [105].

2.2.2 Conservation laws

On physical grounds, the total number of particles N_k^{tot} of a species k and the total charge of all particles together have to be conserved. This means that for

n species plus the unknown electron density N_e there are $n+1$ conservation laws which have to be fulfilled, together with the statistical equilibrium equations described above.

If the total number of particles N_k^{tot} of species k other than hydrogen is given as the fraction y_k of the number of hydrogen atoms N_H^{tot} (including protons),

$$y_k = N_k^{tot} / N_H^{tot}, \quad (2.43)$$

the particle conservation law for one species reads

$$\sum_{i,j} N_{ijk} - y_k \left(\sum_i N_{i,H} + N_p \right) = 0. \quad (2.44)$$

The conservation law for hydrogen ($k = 1$) itself can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_i N_{i,H} + N_p &= N^{tot} - \sum_{k \neq 1} N_k^{tot} \\ &= N^{tot} \cdot \left(\sum_k y_k \right)^{-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.45)$$

which allows to introduce the total particle density N^{tot} . In principle, any species l could be used to obtain a relation to the total number of particles,

$$N_l^{tot} = N^{tot} - \sum_{k \neq l} N_k^{tot}. \quad (2.46)$$

However, due to the overwhelming abundance of hydrogen, the sum on the right hand side may differ from N^{tot} only by a factor of 10^{-6} or less and the numerically computed difference of the two may become very inaccurate.

For the case of zero initial charge the requirement of charge conservation can be reformulated as an equation for the total number of electrons,

$$N_e = \sum_{j,k} j \sum_i N_{ijk}. \quad (2.47)$$

As the transition rates C_{rs} in the rate equations depend on N_e , the system then would become non-linear in N_e this leads to a non-linearity in N_e .

2.3 Simplifying approximations

In this section, two different, simplifying approximations for the NLTE radiative transfer problem are briefly outline. The purpose is to provided the most important ideas and formulas, as both approximations are going to be used later on in this thesis. More complete discussions can be found in the text books cited below.

Sobolev approximation

Radiative transfer in spectral lines is important not only with respect to the resulting line profile but it is also very essential for computing the populations of the atomic energy levels. The problem is that line transitions often have a much greater optical thickness (possibly 10^4 times) than the continuum. Therefore, a spatial grid taking into account these line opacities would be much too fine for the continuum and, more important, much too costly. If applicable, Sobolev theory allows to treat the transport of photons in spectral lines locally in terms of escape probabilities, instead of actually solving the radiative transfer equation for them.

Roughly speaking, the Sobolev approximation may be used in a moving media where the velocities of neighboring points differ strongly enough, either in magnitude or in direction. More precisely, a necessary condition for Sobolev theory to be applicable is that locally the interaction region of a photon emitted in a spectral line, which is on the order of the Sobolev length $L = v_{th}/(dv_{flow}/dr)$, is small compared to the length scale H for any flow variations. v_{th} here denotes a typical thermal velocity and is a measure of the Doppler broadening of the line, while (dv_{flow}/dr) is a measure of the Doppler shift due to the motion of the flow. In addition, as Sobolev theory is a *local* theory, regions located at different positions in space should not have the same velocities as this would lead to multiple interaction zones. One may say that the interaction zone has to be singly connected. This then allows to work with escape probabilities β for line photons, which are comparatively easy to compute, instead of solving the full transfer equation.

A detailed description of the Sobolev approximation for spherically expanding stellar atmospheres can be found in Mihalas [96]. For full 3D geometry, the formalism is very similar. The relevant formulas for this case are given in the following. It is assumed that $L \ll H$ holds and that there is only one interaction zone with a particular velocity. Frequencies are going to be measured as frequency displacements from line center in Doppler units, $x = (\nu - \nu_0)/\Delta\nu_D$, where $\Delta\nu_D = \nu_0 v_{th}/c$.

The probability $\beta(r_0)$ that a line photon emitted at point r_0 and frequency x leaves its origin for good and travels in direction n towards an observer at infinity is given by

$$\beta(r_0) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{S^2} d\omega \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx \phi(x) e^{-\tau(x, r_0, n)}. \quad (2.48)$$

Here $\phi(x)$ denotes the line profile function. The optical depth $\tau(x, r_0, n)$ towards an observer at infinity contains yet another integral which, however, can

be somewhat simplified for $L \ll H$:

$$\tau(x, r_0, n) = \int_{r_0}^{\infty} \chi(r', x') dr' = \int_{r_0}^{\infty} \chi_L(r') \phi(x') dr' \approx \chi_L(r_0) \int_{r_0}^{\infty} \phi(x') dr'. \quad (2.49)$$

$x' = x(r')$ denotes the Doppler shifted frequency at point $r'(n)$, corresponding to frequency x at point r_0 . $\chi(r', x')$ is the absorption coefficient at point r' for a photon having frequency ν at point r_0 . It depends on the state of the matter at point r' and on x' . $\chi_L(r')$ denotes the total absorption coefficient of the considered line at point r' , which for $L \ll H$ can be approximated by $\chi_L(r_0)$.

The basic idea now is to replace $\int_{r_0}^{\infty} \phi(x') dr'$ by a function $F(x)$ and then to carry out the integral $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx \phi(x) e^{-\tau(x, r_0)}$ analytically. This leaves only the integral over Ω to be carried out numerically. With the Doppler shift between point r_0 and r' given by

$$\nu(r') = \nu(r_0) \left[1 - \frac{|v(r_0)| \cos \alpha_{r_0} - |v(r')| \cos \alpha_{r'}}{c} \right], \quad (2.50)$$

where $\cos \alpha_* = (v(r_*) \cdot n) / (|v(r_*)| \cdot |n|)$, and making use again of $L \ll H$ the integral in eq. 2.49 can be replaced by

$$\int_{r_0}^{\infty} \phi(x(r')) dr' \approx T^{-1}(r_0, x, n) \int_{x(r_0)}^{x(\infty)} \phi(x') dx' \quad (2.51)$$

where $T(r_0, x, n)$ is given by

$$T(r_0, x, n) = \left. \frac{dx(r')}{dr'} \right|_{r_0} \quad (2.52)$$

$$= \frac{1}{v_{th}} \left(\frac{d|v(r')|}{dr'} \cos \alpha_{r'} - |v(r')| \sin \alpha_{r'} \frac{d\alpha_{r'}}{dr'} \right) \quad (2.53)$$

It should be noted that $T^{-1}(r_0, x, n)$ can become singular for a particular direction n if there is no change in velocity in this direction. Physically this means that the photon cannot escape in this particular direction and that this direction does not contribute to the total escape probability. Strictly speaking, for such a direction the Sobolev condition $L \ll H$ is violated. As there is hardly any frequency dependence of T within a line it is sufficient to consider $T(r_0, x_0, n)$, where x_0 is the central line frequency. Defining a function $\Phi(\bar{x})$ as

$$\Phi(\bar{x}) = - \int_{\bar{x}}^{x(\infty)} \phi(x') dx' \quad (2.54)$$

with

$$\Phi(\infty) = \begin{cases} 1 & dv/dr > 0 \\ 0 & dv/dr < 0 \end{cases} \quad \Phi(-\infty) = \begin{cases} 0 & dv/dr > 0 \\ -1 & dv/dr < 0 \end{cases} \quad (2.55)$$

allows to reformulate the expression for $\tau(x, r_0, n)$ as

$$\tau(x, r_0, n) = \chi_L(r_0)T^{-1}(r_0, x, n)\Phi(x(r_0)). \quad (2.56)$$

Substituting eq. 2.56 in eq. 2.48, making use of $d\Phi = \phi(x)dx$, and defining

$$F(r_0, x_0, n) = |\chi_L(r_0)T^{-1}(r_0, x_0, n)| \quad (2.57)$$

finally leads to the desired expression for the escape probability $\beta(r_0, x_0)$,

$$\beta = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{\Omega} d\omega \frac{1 - e^{-F}}{F}. \quad (2.58)$$

This expression for β is formally the same as in the case of a spherically symmetric, expanding stellar atmosphere. And for an appropriate velocity field eq. 2.58 can indeed be reduced to the well known formulas given, for example, in Mihalas [96]. However, the above expressions for F or, more precisely, for T do not yet contain any assumptions about the geometry or the velocity field, except for the basic assumption of Sobolev theory that $v_{th}/(dv_{flow}/dr) = L \ll H$, where H is the length scale for any flow variations. This makes them applicable to general 3D situations.

The price to pay is that, for general situations, the evaluation of β becomes much more expensive. A spherically symmetric expanding atmosphere allows to evaluate several quantities analytically, even β itself, if the velocity increases linearly with the radius.

The escape probability of a line photon also influences the continuum radiation field. For an escape probability $\beta \approx 0$ the continuum radiation field coming from outside cannot penetrate the interaction zone of the line around r_0 . For $\beta \approx 1$ the opposite is true. It can be shown (see e.g. Mihalas [96]) that for this reason the continuum radiation field at a particular line frequency has to be corrected to

$$\bar{J}_{\beta_c} = \int_{\Omega} I(n)\tilde{\beta}(n)d\omega, \quad (2.59)$$

where $\tilde{\beta}(n) = (1 - e^{-F(n)})/F(n)$.

This corrected continuum radiation field as well as the escape probabilities β itself then are inserted into the statistical equilibrium equations, changing them to

$$\sum_{i < j} [N_j(\beta_{ij}A_{ji} + B_{ji}J_{\beta_c ij}^- + N_e q_{ji}) - N_i(B_{ij}J_{\beta_c ij}^- + N_e q_{ij})] + \quad (2.60)$$

$$\sum_{i > j} [N_j(B_{ji}J_{\beta_c ij}^- + N_e q_{ji}) - N_i(\beta_{ij}A_{ij}B_{ij}J_{\beta_c ij}^- + N_e q_{ij})] = 0. \quad (2.61)$$

Nebular approximation

A typical nebula is rather tenuous, has a moderate temperature of maybe ten thousand degrees, and possesses a relatively strong UV radiation source. When investigating such nebular structures the radiative transfer problem often can be greatly simplified. The purpose of this section is to give a general idea of the most important simplifications possible under such conditions, mostly as a general basis for Chapter 7 and 8. Therefore, the following picture is oversimplified in some points. More details on radiative transfer under nebular conditions can be found, for example, in Osterbrock [110].

Consider first the atomic level populations. As the probability of ionization or excitation is much smaller than the probability of spontaneous de-excitation the populations of excited levels can be neglected and *all ions can be assumed to be in the ground state*. Any transition into a higher lying level will immediately lead to a downward transition into the ground level. This greatly simplifies the rate equation part, as only the ground state of each ion has to be considered. It also allows, for example for radiative recombination, to *use total recombination cross-sections*, which are a function of temperature and density only, instead of numerically computing integrals as in eq. 2.29.

As far as the transfer of the radiation field is concerned, things become simpler as well. Most lines can safely be assumed to be optically thin. This means that each emitted line photon just escapes freely to infinity, *no transfer equation has to be solved for line photons*. Looking at the continuum, transfer effects are important for wavelengths smaller than about 1000 Å. And here absorption is usually more important than scattering, which means that there is *hardly any coupling between different directions*. For longer wavelengths, transfer effects in the continuum may be neglected at all.

Part II

Radiative transfer: Numerical solution

Introduction

This part of the thesis is devoted to the numerical solution of the multidimensional NLTE radiative transfer problem. While the one dimensional problem can be handled quite well nowadays, the multidimensional case is a relatively new topic and there is currently much interest for this topic not only among astrophysicist. Although some attempts have been made, the interest among numerical mathematicians for this problem is still somewhat limited.

The numerical solution of the optically thick NLTE radiative transfer problem for moving media is the major topic of this part. It is assumed that the problem is stationary, non-relativistic, and unpolarized. For this purpose the code TR3D has been developed. Much less room is given to the second code, D3NEBEL. It has been developed for the case of NLTE radiative transfer in moving media under the simplifying assumption of nebular conditions.

There are two main reasons for the unequal distribution of room to the two approaches. First, the problem of optically thick NLTE radiative transfer is much more difficult to solve than the radiative transfer problem under nebular conditions. Second, the starting point for TR3D was the realization that this topic is of great interest in connection with existing work of the astrophysics group at ETH Zürich and that it is one of the central problems in numerical astrophysics. For several reasons, the idea of using generalized mean intensities for the solution of the radiative transfer equation as suggested in a paper by Turek [145] was taken up. Starting from this paper TR3D finally went well beyond the paper lying at its beginning. For D3NEBEL, on the other hand, use could be made of an existing one dimensional code. Assuming nebular conditions this code could be taken to three dimensions at quite low costs.

In Chapter 3 a brief survey of the work on numerical radiative transfer, in particular in multidimensions, is given. A description of the solution of the transfer equation in TR3D is given in Chapter 4, the solution of the rate equation part is given in Chapter 5. Chapter 6 gathers these pieces and discusses TR3D as an integrated whole. D3NEBEL is described in Chapter 7, and Chapter 8 outlines the possibilities it offers for the investigations of binary star systems.

Chapter 3

Previous approaches

The numerical solution of the optically thick NLTE radiative transfer problem presented in this thesis has to be viewed in the context of the huge amount of work that has already been done in the field of numerical radiative transfer, mainly, however, in 1D. In this chapter, some current solution strategies for the optically thick NLTE radiative transfer problem or parts of it are briefly outlined and references are given. The chapter is not intended as a comprehensive survey and detailed formulas are mostly omitted. The aim is to give some idea of where the work in this field generally stands today.

The solution techniques for the optically thick NLTE radiative transfer problem nowadays contain three or four basic elements: A solver for the transfer equation, a solver for the rate equation part, a strategy for coupling these two parts, and, occasionally, an accelerator technique combining several previous iteration steps. In fact, having solution techniques for the transfer equation and the rate equations the skillful coupling of these two parts lies at the heart of the numerical schemes for optically thick NLTE radiative transfer.

3.1 One dimensional problems

Although the present work focuses on multidimensional radiative transfer, a quick look at the solution of the 1D problem seems appropriate as several ideas have been carried over to multi dimensions. Over the last thirty years one dimensional numerical radiative transfer, in spherical or plane parallel geometry, has developed into a highly sophisticated tool. The numerical techniques have been greatly refined allowing, together with improved computer resources, the inclusion of a huge amount of physics. On the numerical techniques alone there exists a huge amount of literature. A survey can be found, for example,

in Hubeny [54] and references therein.

For the solution of the transfer equation the Feautrier algorithm (Feautrier [37]) and its improved variants are widely used in one dimensional computations. Nowadays it is often combined with an adaptive mesh. Extensive reviews can be found in Mihalas [96], [97] and Mihalas and Kunasz [98]. The basic idea behind the Feautrier algorithm is to rewrite the transfer equation as a second-order differential equation. The resulting two-point boundary value problem is then solved by means of finite differences.

For the solution of the system of rate equations several techniques are in use. If the rate equations are linear in the level populations N_i , Gaussian elimination or LU-decomposition are widely used while fix-point iteration is applied for the electron density. Kaushik and Hagelstein [69] propose the application of preconditioned biconjugate gradient or conjugate gradient squared algorithms for this case. The use of an ALI or MALI scheme (see below) can lead to nonlinearities in the atomic level populations N_i . The use of Newton's method is then quite common. Koesterke et al. [75] suggest to use Broyden's method instead which they claim to be cheaper and capable of handling more atomic levels.

The coupling methods are commonly summarized under the notation of ALI (Accelerated or Approximated Lambda Iteration) or MALI (Multilevel Accelerated Lambda Iteration) schemes. It should be noted that the term multilevel here refers to the fact that these methods are capable of handling optically thick line transitions in atoms with more than two energy levels. It has no relation to numerical multilevel techniques. A survey of the earlier evolution of ALI techniques can be found in Kalkofen [67], a more recent review has been given by Hubeny [53]. The MALI schemes were introduced by Rybicki [118], [119], [120] and are described there. The basic idea behind these approaches is to include the linear response of the radiation field to perturbations of the source function and possibly of the opacity when determining the source function or the atomic level populations. The solution of the transfer problem employing fix-point iteration (known as Λ -iteration) can formally be written as

$$J_{new} = \Lambda[S_{old}] \quad (3.1)$$

where J_{new} is the newly computed mean intensity. S_{old} is the so called source function computed from the atomic populations of the previous iteration step. $S = \eta/\chi$ where η is the emission coefficient and χ the total absorption coefficient. Λ is an appropriate operator representing the transfer equation. In contrast, ALI and MALI methods can formally be written as

$$J_{new} = (\Lambda - \Lambda^*)[S_{old}] + \Lambda^*[S_{new}], \quad (3.2)$$

where Λ^* is an approximation to the actual Λ -operator. If Λ is written in matrix form, Λ^* typically is the diagonal of Λ in most of today's schemes.

Finally, many schemes nowadays apply an additional acceleration technique to the global iteration process, such as Ng [102] or Orthomin, originally developed by Vinsom [149]. The idea behind these techniques is to make use of the information contained in several of the previous iteration steps. A review on the application of these techniques can be found in Auer [4].

As far as the development and improvement of numerical techniques are concerned hardly any work has been done on the solution of the 1D transfer equation over the past few years. In contrast, a lot of effort has been spent on the ALI and MALI coupling techniques and also the rate equation problem has obtained some attention while the topic of additional acceleration techniques like Ng or Orthomin seems still to be in its infancy.

3.2 Multidimensional radiative transfer

The four basic elements of the solution strategy as a whole remain the same in multi dimensions as described above for the one dimensional case. In contrast to the one dimensional situation, the solution of the transfer equation, once its coefficients are known, now requires much attention, too. The fact that one has a much greater number of spatial grid points compared to 1D and the absence of spherical or plane parallel geometry forces the use of spatially localized schemes for the solution of the transfer equation. Presently there exist many different ideas for the solution of the transfer equation competing with each other and things are not yet as settled as in 1D.

For the solution of the transfer equation the short characteristic method introduced by Kunasz and Auer [79] and variants of this method are widely used today. The term short characteristics refers to the fact that for the computation of the intensity at a particular grid point only data from the neighboring grid points is used. ZEUS-2D, described in Stone et al. [142], the codes described in Fabiani Bendicho et al. [34], Steiner [138], and the work by Hauschildt et al. [49] are all based on short characteristics for the solution of the transfer equation. A second, much smaller, class of approaches employs finite elements for the solution of the transfer equation. Among them ALTAIR, described in Dykema et al. [32] and references therein, the work by Kanschat [68], or the work by Turek [145]. Many of these approaches make use of adaptive grids. However, the higher spatial resolution gained in this way has usually to be paid for by decreasing convergence speed, due to the directional derivative in the transfer equation. To cope with this problem the use of multigrid techniques, first applied to multidimensional radiative transfer by Steiner [137], has become more and more popular and is part of several of the above mentioned codes.

The rate equations are generally solved with the same techniques as used in 1D.

For the coupling of the radiative transfer equation and the statistical equilibrium equations the use of ALI and MALI schemes is state of the art also in multidimensions. One of the most recent approaches in this field for multidimensional radiative transfer is the MUGA scheme described in Fabiani Bendicho et al. [34]. They also give references to other approaches. However, with respect to coupling most codes still rely on basically the same techniques as already known from 1D.

The same additional accelerator techniques as described in the previous section, Ng and Orthomin, are applied in multi dimensions as well. In fact, most of them have been introduced in the context of multidimensional radiative transfer.

The increase in geometry also allows for more freedom concerning the prescribed density and velocity distribution which, however, can lead to conflicts with physical approximations like the Sobolev approximation.

Most of the remainder of this part is devoted to the presentation of yet another approach to optically thick 3D NLTE radiative transfer which features a new approach to the solution of the transfer equation. Short characteristics are applied in the sense that only nearest neighboring coupling is used. The statistical equilibrium equations are solved using standard techniques. Iteration is applied for the electron density and the remaining linear system is solved using Householder transformations. Up to now, there is no additional accelerator technique and, probably the biggest drawback, no coupling technique similar to ALI, MALI, or MUGA.

Chapter 4

TR3D: Solution of the transfer equation

In this chapter the numerical solution of the transfer equation in TR3D is presented, including some error estimates. The transfer equation to be considered describes non-relativistic, stationary, frequency decoupled, and unpolarized radiative transfer (see also Section 2.1). It is given by

$$\begin{aligned} n \nabla_x I(x, n, \nu) + \chi(x, \nu) I(x, n, \nu) = \\ \lambda(x, \nu) \int_{S^2} P(n, n') I(x, n', \nu) d\omega' + f(x, \nu) \\ \text{in } D_1 \times S^2 \times D_2 \end{aligned} \quad (4.1)$$

with boundary conditions (see also Section 4.1.1)

$$I(x, n, \nu) = I_0(x, n, \nu) \quad \text{on } \Gamma_n^- = \{\nu \in D_2, x \in \partial D_1 | n_x \cdot n < 0\}. \quad (4.2)$$

Here $D_1 \subset R^3$, S^2 is the unit sphere in R^3 , $D_2 \subset R^1$, n is the unite vector in the direction of propagaion of I , $d\omega$ is the solid angle element associated with n , and n_x is the outward normal unit vector to ∂D_1 at point x .

The idea for the solution of the transfer equation used in TR3D is taken from Turek [145], [146]. He suggested to solve for a generalized mean intensity instead of directed intensities and made some suggestions about the technical realization of this approach, among them the use of BiCGStab.

In a first section, boundary conditions are discussed and the discretization of the transfer equation including the transformation to generalized mean intensities is given. In Section 4.2 the iterative solution of the resulting system of equations using BiCGStab is discussed. Error estimates for two different problems are given in Section 4.3.

4.1 Boundary conditions, discretization, and succeeding rearrangement

4.1.1 Boundary conditions

To obtain a specific solution of the radiative transfer equation on a given domain, the specific intensities I directed inwards of this domain have to be prescribed along the domain boundaries as well as conditions for the outgoing directions. Obviously, the physical boundary conditions to be applied depend strongly on the problem under consideration. In the following, only artificial boundaries are going to be considered, i.e. boundaries which are present due to modeling purposes (finite domain) rather than for physical reasons (e.g. a reflecting wall). The presented discussion is far from complete. The intention is to give an idea of the problem in general and to present the boundary conditions actually applied at the moment.

General considerations

Consider first the case of an artificial boundary in the absence of any matter, which means that there is no absorption, emission, and scattering. In this case there is no coupling between incoming and outgoing directions and they can be treated separately. Appropriate boundary conditions are to prescribe the incoming radiation field along the boundary, while one has free outflow for outgoing directions. The same boundary conditions may be applied if matter is actually present, but with a sufficiently small density. Absorption, emission, and scattering, although present in principle, may then be neglected. Such a situation is encountered, for example, at the outer boundaries of a nebula.

Next look at the problem of an artificial boundary laying in the outer parts or close to the atmosphere of a star, where the matter density is still high and NLTE-effects are important. Absorption, emission, and scattering coefficients then can no longer be assumed to be zero. Moreover, they are influenced by the radiation field while at the same time, they affect the radiation field. In this sense, the boundary conditions become dependent on the solution in the interior of the domain. In particular, scattering couples the incoming and outgoing directions. The incoming radiation field now is enhanced by contributions from scattered, outgoing radiation and is weakened due to outward backscattering at the boundary. The outgoing radiation which indeed leaves the computational domain changes the mean radiation field and the state of the matter *outside* the computational domain. These changes would again affect the incoming radiation field. However, as this effect takes place outside the computational domain, it cannot be exactly included. If the boundary is indeed to be taken at such a location, additional assumptions have to be made with respect to the boundary conditions.

What is actually used: Vacuum boundary conditions

The boundary conditions applied at the moment are, strictly speaking, appropriate only in the absence of matter. It is assumed that there is no scattering, emission, or absorption at the boundary. For outgoing directions free outflow is assumed. For incoming directions the specific intensity I is prescribed:

$$I(x, n, \nu) = I_0(x, n, \nu) \quad \text{for} \quad x \in \Gamma_n^-, \quad (4.3)$$

where

$$\Gamma_n^- = \{\nu \in D_2, x \in \partial D_1 | n_x \cdot n < 0\} \quad (4.4)$$

and (see also eq. 4.1) $D_1 \subset R^3$, $D_2 \subset R^1$, and n_x is the outward normal unit vector to ∂D_1 at point x . At present, these boundary conditions are implemented by reducing the transfer equation to

$$\chi(x, n, \nu)I(x, n, \nu) = f(x, n, \nu), \quad \text{on} \quad \Gamma_n^-, \quad (4.5)$$

which makes χ and f dependent on angle again.

4.1.2 Discretization

Frequency discretization

The transfer equation as given in eq. 4.1 is decoupled in frequency. Consequently, the frequency discretization can be done independently of the other discretizations. The choice of discrete frequency points is guided by the physics. As the transfer equation is solved for continuum radiation only, the discrete frequency points should allow for a good resolution of important features of the continuum radiation field. In particular, the most important ionization edges should be captured by the frequency grid. If desired, additional frequency points at particular line frequencies are set automatically.

Due to the decoupling of the transfer equation with respect to frequency, the frequency indices will be omitted in the following. One should bear in mind, however, that χ , λ , and f actually depend on frequency.

Discretization of S^2

Next consider the discretization of the integral over S^2 . One of the most simple things which comes to mind is to use the parameterization of S^2 over $[0, 2\pi] \times [0, \pi]$ together with some Newton-Cotes-quadrature formula. For the Trapezoidal rule, using $K + 1$ support points on $[0, \pi]$ and $L + 1$ support points

on $[0, 2\pi]$, this results in a quadrature rule of the form

$$\int_{S^2} P(n, n') I(n') d\omega' = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi P(\phi, \theta; \phi', \theta') I(\phi', \theta') \sin\theta' d\theta' d\phi' \quad (4.6)$$

$$\approx \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} c^{lk} (P) I(\phi^l, \theta^k), \quad (4.7)$$

where use has been made of $I(0, \theta) = I(2\pi, \theta)$ and $\sin 0 = \sin \pi = 0$. For the special choice of $P(n, n') = 1/4\pi$ one obtains

$$c^{lk} = \frac{\pi}{2KL} \sin\theta^k. \quad (4.8)$$

The sums may then be rewritten in terms of a single sum from $m = 1$ to $m = (K - 1)L \equiv M$, using appropriate coefficients:

$$\int_{S^2} P(n, n') I(n') d\omega' \approx \sum_m^M c^m (P) I^m. \quad (4.9)$$

A similar discretization and quadrature rule was used by Turek. It is known, however, that there are several disadvantages to this kind of discretization. It introduces two distinct directions, namely the two poles of the sphere at $\theta = 0$ and $\theta = \pi$. They are artificial constructs and have nothing to do with the physics. At these poles, the cells generated on S^2 by the discrete ordinate directions become degenerated. Another disadvantage is the physically unnecessary concentration of discrete ordinate directions near these poles.

If one sticks to this discretization one has to live with the artificially introduced poles. But the number of discrete ordinates near the poles may be reduced. At a given latitude θ half of the ordinates in ϕ -direction may be omitted if the intervals between ordinates in ϕ -direction have become less than half the size the intervals have on the equator of the sphere. Considering only the integration in ϕ -direction this does not lead to a decrease in accuracy as the error of the applied trapezoidal rule is proportional to $\Delta\phi^3$ and $\Delta\phi$ is at most equal to $\Delta\phi_{equator}$. Including the θ -direction, a mathematical error estimation is no longer as straightforward. However, one may argue that omitting some polar directions should not greatly affect the overall accuracy as there is no guarantee that the high resolution at the poles is really needed there — and not at the equator instead. In this way, the number of ordinates can be reduced, for example, from 684 (36 for ϕ and 19 for θ) to 476. It is this kind of ordinate discretizations which are used in the TR3D.

Another approach to the integration over S^2 can be found in Kanschat [68]. He suggests using a refined icosahedron to determine the discrete ordinate

directions. The quadrature points are taken to be the cell centers of the refined icosahedron, projected onto S^2 . This method has the advantage that there are no more artificially introduced distinct directions and no more degenerated cells. This property also simplifies the application of finite element methods and error estimates. As a disadvantage of this approach one may regard that only certain numbers of discrete ordinates can be chosen. In this respect, the straightforward approach presented above seems to be a bit more flexible.

The transfer equation can now be discretized with respect to ordinate space using the discrete ordinate directions n^m defined by one of the quadrature rules given above. Writing I^m instead of $I(n^m)$ the transfer equation becomes

$$n^m \nabla_x I^m(x) + \chi^m(x) I^m(x) = \lambda(x) \sum_{m=1}^M c^m(P) I^m(x) + f^m(x). \quad (4.10)$$

Spatial discretization

For the spatial discretization a Cartesian grid is used. The transport part is discretized using a first order finite difference scheme. As in the pure transport case the specific intensity I^m propagates only into direction n^m , upwinding is used. Figure 4.1 illustrates the discretization of the transport term at point x_0 in 3D. Denoting by I_*^m the discrete approximation to I^m at point x_* , where $*$ = {0, 1, 2, 3, 4}, the discretization of the transport term is given by

$$\begin{aligned} n^m \nabla_x I^m(x_0) &= \frac{I_0^m - I_{12}^m}{d} + \mathcal{O}(h) \\ &= \frac{I_0^m - g_1 I_2^m - g_2 I_1^m}{d} + \mathcal{O}(h) \quad (2D) \quad (4.11) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} n^m \nabla_x I^m(x_0) &= \frac{I_0^m - I_{1234}^m}{d} + \mathcal{O}(h) \\ &= d^{-1} [I_0^m - \\ &\quad I_1^m (1 - g_1 - g_2 + g_1 g_2) - \\ &\quad I_2^m (g_1 - g_1 g_2) - \\ &\quad I_3^m (g_1 g_2) - \\ &\quad I_4^m (g_2 - g_1 g_2)] + \mathcal{O}(h) \quad (3D) \quad (4.12) \end{aligned}$$

Now let I_h^m denote the vector containing the specific intensity of direction n^m at each discrete grid point. The transfer equation for one frequency point can then be written as

$$T_h^m I_h^m = L_h \sum_{m=1}^M c^m(P) I_h^m + f_h^m. \quad (4.13)$$

Figure 4.1: Spatial discretization of the transport term illustrated in 2D (left) and 3D (right).

Here T_h^m describes the discretized transport term as well as the discretized loss coefficient $\chi^m(x_0)$. L_h and f_h^m stand for the discretized scattering and emission coefficients at point x_0 on the right hand side of eq. 4.10.

The equation may now be solved in this form for each I_h^m , applying iteration to account for the sum over all m . However, there are some disadvantages to this approach. One of them is due to the transfer operator on the left hand side. As it is first order in space the convergence of the solution will deteriorate with decreasing grid spacing h if the equation is solved in the form of eq. 4.13. There are means to cure this problem, e.g. by using multigrid algorithms as mentioned in Chapter 3. Another possibility is to reformulate eq. 4.13 such that it becomes an equation not for I_h^m but for the generalized mean intensity $\tilde{J}$ to be introduced in the next section.

However, before going on to the generalized mean intensity approach a closer look at the spatial discretization just presented is advisable. For this purpose, consider the special case of a one dimensional transfer equation where λ and f are both zero while χ has a constant value greater than zero, $\partial I / \partial x + \chi I = 0$, with $\chi = \text{const.}$. Given the intensity I_0 at point x_0 the analytical solution of this equation is $I(x) = I_0 \cdot e^{-\chi x}$, where $h = x - x_0$. The above discretization, however, would yield $I(x) = I_0 / (1 + \chi h)$. Obviously, the two solutions are close to each other only for small enough values of χh . For $\chi h = 0.4$ already a 10% error occurs, for $\chi h = 0.6$ the error is already roughly 30%. This means that for a given value of χ the spatial discretization h has to be chosen sufficiently small. This result carries over to the directional derivative used in the multidimensional case. From this one can concluded that **this spatial discretization gives good results only for χh considerably smaller than 1.**

4.1.3 The generalized mean intensity approach

The *generalized mean intensity* is given by

$$\tilde{J}(x) = \int_{S^2} P(n, n') I(x, n') d\omega' \quad (4.14)$$

or, in its discrete version, by

$$\tilde{J}_h = \sum_{m=1}^M c^m(P) I_h^m, \quad (4.15)$$

where now $\tilde{J}_h$ denotes the vector containing the discrete generalized mean intensities at each spatial grid point. Remembering that the redistribution function $P(n, n')$ can depend on angle (for Thomson scattering $P(n, n') = 3/4(1 + \cos^2\Phi)$, where $\Phi = n \cdot n'$) it can be seen that $\tilde{J}_h$ deviates from the physical mean intensity, defined in eq. 2.19,

$$J(x) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{S^2} I(x, n') d\omega' \quad (4.16)$$

by the term $P(n, n')$ in the integral if $P(n, n') \neq 1/4\pi$, i.e. if the redistribution function is not isotropic.

Eq. 4.13 can now be rewritten in terms of the discretized generalized mean intensity $\tilde{J}_h$. For this purpose the discretized integral in the equation is replaced by $\tilde{J}_h$ and the operator T_h^m is inverted and taken to the right hand side. Performing now a discrete integration of the entire equation over all ordinate directions, using again the function $P(n, n')$, leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{J}_h &= \sum_{m=1}^M c^m(P) (T_h^m)^{-1} L_h \tilde{J}_h + \sum_{m=1}^M c^m(P) (T_h^m)^{-1} f_h^m \\ &= T_h L_h \tilde{J}_h + F_h. \end{aligned} \quad (4.17)$$

Taking all $\tilde{J}_h$ terms to the left one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - T_h L_h) \tilde{J}_h &= F_h \\ A_h \tilde{J}_h &= F_h. \end{aligned} \quad (4.18)$$

where $A_h = 1 - T_h L_h$. As will be shown below, the convergence of the solution now hardly depends on h anymore. Note that for the special choice of $P(n, n') = 1/4\pi$ this is an equation for the discrete counterpart of the *physical* mean intensity. **It is eq. 4.18 which is solved in TR3D.**

For an efficient inversion of T_h^m it is essential that the matrix representation of T_h^m can be brought to lower triangular form. This can be achieved due to the upwinding requirement and by an appropriate renumbering of the grid points, depending on the ordinate direction. Note that an efficient inversion of T_h^m is also advantageous if eq. 4.13 is solved directly.

4.1.4 Properties of the resulting matrix A

Unfortunately, the structure of matrix A is rather complicated and analyzing the properties of A is no easy task. Apart from the general structure of A , its eigenvalue distribution would be of particular interest with regard to an iterative solution. However, the construction process of A is quite complex and in practice only applications of A to a vector are known. In this sense, A itself is never computed. In principle, it is possible to determine the eigenvalues of A numerically for a given problem. But as there is no obvious guarantee that to compute a few eigenvalues will do and with regard to the size of the matrix A this is probably not the first thing to do. Nevertheless, two general properties of the matrix A are rather obvious when looking at its construction. One is that A is rather full, the other that it is not necessarily symmetric. However, Turek [146] pointed out that eq. 4.18 can be rewritten in symmetrized form if for each discrete ordinate direction its discrete counterpart pointing to the opposite direction is taken into account as well.

Turek further claimed that due to the use of the exact inverse of the combined transport and absorption operator T_h^m in eq. 4.18 the convergence properties should hardly depend on the grid spacing h . However, there seems to be no proof, or at least investigation, of this claim so far.

Some properties of the matrix A , in particular its dependence — or independence — on h are going to be investigated in two different ways. First, in the remainder of this section, a simplified model of the matrix A is investigated. Then, in the next section, numerical test are carried out. Both ways do indeed confirm that the convergence properties are essentially, although not totally, independent of h .

Simplified approximation: As the matrix A itself is too complicated a simplified approximation, matrix B , will be studied in the following. The aim is to obtain some insight into the general behavior of A . For simplicity, only the case is considered where χ and λ are both constant over the entire computational domain.

For the *construction of B* the matrix T_h^m is approximated by a lower triangular matrix R of the form

$$\begin{aligned} r_{ii} &:= \frac{1}{h} + \chi \\ r_{ij} &:= -\frac{1}{h} \quad , \quad i > j \\ r_{ij} &:= 0 \quad , \quad i < j \end{aligned} \tag{4.19}$$

R deviates from T_h^m in mainly two aspects. R is a full lower triangular matrix while T_h^m is sparse and in T_h^m the actual distance from the grid point to the

next cell boundary would occur in the entries instead of h . This makes the entries of R generally bigger than those of T_h^m . For this simplified matrix R it is easy to show that its inverse S has entries

$$\begin{aligned} s_{ii} &= \frac{h}{1 + \chi h} \\ s_{ij} &= \frac{h}{(1 + \chi h)^2} \left(\frac{2 + \chi h}{1 + \chi h} \right)^{i-j-1}, \quad i > j \\ s_{ij} &= 0, \quad i < j. \end{aligned} \quad (4.20)$$

Defining the matrix $B = 1 - SL$, where $L = \text{diag}(\lambda, \dots, \lambda)$, it then follows that

$$\begin{aligned} b_{ii} &= 1 - \frac{\lambda h}{1 + \chi h} \\ b_{ij} &= -\frac{\lambda h}{(1 + \chi h)^2} \left(\frac{2 + \chi h}{1 + \chi h} \right)^{i-j-1}, \quad i > j \\ b_{ij} &= 0, \quad i < j. \end{aligned} \quad (4.21)$$

For later use it should be noted here that the term $\lambda h/(1 + \chi h)$ in b_{ii} is always greater than 0 and less than 1, the later because $\chi \geq \lambda$.

What are the differences between the matrix B and the original matrix A ? Looking at the construction of both matrices the following answers can be given. First, B is based on a full lower triangular matrix R rather than a sparse matrix as T_h^m is. Second, although the entries of R have the right dependence on h (e.g. $-1/h$) they are in general somewhat too big in norm. Third, the entries in R correspond to entries from regular cells only. Boundary cells are neglected. Fourth, B includes only one ordinate direction which means that the summation over all ordinates and the reordering of the grid points is not included in B .

Comparing now the entries and the structure (symmetric, triangular, etc.) of A and B these differences have the following consequences. The main *effect of reordering* would be to destroy the lower triangular structure of B . Including the *sum over all ordinate directions*, on the other hand, would not change too much in the following sense. As the sum is weighted with the total sum of the weights being one, the diagonal elements would remain between zero and one even if the sum were performed. Furthermore, the absolute value of the diagonal elements would hardly change as for them and for the form of the transfer equation considered here χ and λ are independent of the direction. The off-diagonal elements would become smaller or at most remain of the same size. As T_h^m is sparse compared to R , the power $(i - j - 1)$ in the off-diagonal elements of S , and therefore their size, is overestimated. Finally, there is the

neglect of the boundary cells. Within this work, the specific intensities I_0 for incoming directions are prescribed by reducing the radiative transfer equation to $\chi I = f$, and χ and f for these incoming directions are then chosen such that $f/\chi = I_0$. Although this case is basically covered by the formalism of matrix B , the values that χ and λ take in the boundary cells can be quite different from the values they take in the regular cells, which may change the properties of the matrix considerably. However, this effect may be small as the number of boundary cells is usually small compared to the total number of cells.

In summary, this means that the diagonal elements of B reflect quite well the diagonal elements of A . The off-diagonal elements of B are likely to be much bigger than those of A , due to the missing reordering of grid points and the difference between R and T_h^m . Also, the off-diagonal elements in B are all in the lower triangular part whereas in A they can be anywhere off the diagonal. The eigenvalue structure of A and B should not be too different as long as the off-diagonal elements are small compared to the diagonal elements.

Limiting cases of the simplified approximation: Looking at eq. 4.21 suggests to investigate the dependence on χh and λh , rather than on h , χ , and λ , to analyze the properties of matrix B further. The following four limiting cases are considered:

Case I, $\chi h = \lambda h \ll 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} b_{ii} &\approx 1 - \lambda h \\ b_{ij} &\approx -\lambda h 2^{i-j-1} \end{aligned} \quad (4.22)$$

Case II, $\chi h \gg 1 \gg \lambda h$:

$$\begin{aligned} b_{ii} &\approx 1 - \epsilon \\ b_{ij} &\approx -\epsilon \end{aligned} \quad (4.23)$$

Case III, $\chi h = \lambda h = 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} b_{ii} &\approx \frac{1}{2} \\ b_{ij} &\approx -\frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{i-j-1} \end{aligned} \quad (4.24)$$

Case IV, $\chi h = \lambda h \gg 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} b_{ii} &\approx \frac{1}{\chi h} \\ b_{ij} &\approx -\frac{1}{\chi h} \end{aligned} \quad (4.25)$$

ϵ in eq. 4.23 denotes a number much smaller than 1 and in all cases $i > j$.

From a linear algebra point of view, all these four limiting cases make perfectly sense. However, for the solution of the transfer equation only those cases are of interest where χh is sufficiently small compared to 1, as already discussed at the end of Section 4.1.2. This leaves only case I and possibly a 'milder' version of case III ('milder' meaning that χh may be 0.4 or so), while case II and case IV are of no further interest.

What can then be learned from case I and case III for the matrix A ?

Conclusions for the matrix A : Remembering what has been said about the differences between matrix A and B the following conclusions can be drawn. The fact that the diagonal elements of B are always between zero and one carries over to A . In general, the diagonal elements become smaller as χh and λh both increase and they remain close to one if only χh increases while λh stays small. For the off-diagonal elements there is no such general tendency.

For case I, i.e. if both χh and λh are much smaller than one, the off-diagonal elements of A finally become dependent on h through the factor 2^{i-j-1} in eq. 4.22, where $(i - j - 1)$ increases as h decreases. However, the factor λh in eq. 4.22 describing the off-diagonal elements reduces the norm of these elements. Also, the dependence will not occur as fast as suggested by this equation because the factor 2^{i-j-1} is based on the assumption of a full lower triangular matrix S . Consequently, only for a very fine grid spacing h the off-diagonal elements will catch up in norm with the diagonal elements.

For case III, i.e. as both χh and λh increase towards 1, the off-diagonal elements also increase. But again the increase is less strong than suggested by eq. 4.24 because again the exponent $(i - j - 1)$ is based on the assumption of a full lower triangular matrix. However, in this case the factor λh in the off-diagonal elements is no longer much smaller than one. Consequently, the norm of the off-diagonal elements in case III will grow much faster with decreasing grid spacing h than they do in case I. Note that if $\lambda h \ll 1$ one ends up again basically with case I even if χh tends to one.

In summary, this means that the iteration procedure applied to $AJ = F$ should converge quite fast if either $\chi h = \lambda h \ll 1$ or if at least $\lambda h \ll 1$. Convergence should deteriorate as $\lambda h \rightarrow \chi h$ and χh approaches one. In physical terms this means that the solution should converge fast in the pure transport case or in a pure absorption case where still $\chi h < 1$, while the convergence should slow down if the loss term becomes dominated by scattering, i.e. $\lambda h \rightarrow \chi h$. The numerical tests to be presented in Section 4.2.2 indeed confirm this prediction.

Before leaving this section, it has to be pointed out that **here it was always assumed that χ and λ are constant over the entire computational**

domain. In most practical applications this will not be the case. The limiting cases just presented, therefore, will hardly ever occur in their pure form.

4.2 Iterative solution using BiCGStab

For the solution of eq. 4.18, the BiCGStab algorithm developed by Van der Voerst [147] is used. There are two main reasons for the choice of this algorithm. First, it is applicable also to non-symmetric problems as the one presented here, a property which only a few other solvers share. Second, its memory requirements are rather small compared, for example, to those of GMRES. Apart from this, BiCGStab usually shows a rather smooth convergence. As it works reasonably well for the problems considered up to now no other solver has been tested.

In the following, a few results considering the convergence of BiCGStab as a function of h , χ , and λ are given. A solution of the transfer equation is considered to have converged if the l_2 -norm of the BiCGStab residual becomes smaller than a prescribed tolerance ϵ . It should be noted here that the BiCGStab residual computed in the iteration process is not the real residual and, at least theoretically, can deviate considerably from the real residual. However, some tests have been carried out on this point and they all indicated that the real residual was very close in l_2 -norm to the BiCGStab residual. In the frame of this work, convergence studies have been performed for the following two examples.

Test example 1: The computational domain is given by $[0, 1]^3$. A square shaped beam is considered, entering the computational domain at the boundary $x = 0$. It is directed along the discrete ordinate direction ($\phi = 0, \theta = \pi/2$) which is parallel to the positive x-direction. Its axis goes through the point $(x, y, z) = (0, 0.5, 0.5)$ and it has a cross-section of 0.41×0.41 (see Figure 4.2). The specific intensity I of the beam is set to 10^4 at the incoming boundary. $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (24, 13)$ ordinates have been used. If not otherwise stated, the error bound for BiCGStab was set to $\epsilon = 10^{-10}$. χ , λ , and h are variable and given along with the individual test cases. Diagonal preconditioning is used unless otherwise stated.

Test example 2: The same as test example 1, but using $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (16, 7)$ ordinates instead.

4.2.1 Preconditioning

Preconditioning generally is difficult here for several reasons. First, one has only a matrix free representation of the problem, i.e. only applications of A on a vector are computed while A itself is never computed explicitly. This makes

Figure 4.2: **Right:** Schematic setting of test example 1 in Section 4.2. **Left:** Schematic illustration of the angles θ and ϕ relative to the x -, y -, and z -axis.

it not only difficult to analyze but also difficult to extract parts of A for use as a preconditioner. Second, A is neither necessarily diagonally dominant nor is it symmetric. And third, A is rather full with many entries being of roughly the same size. In a first attempt, diagonal preconditioning is used and BiCGStab is applied to the preconditioned system $D^{-1}AJ = D^{-1}F$ where D is the diagonal of A . The reason for choosing the diagonal is that it is relatively easy obtainable. However, Figure 4.3 indicates that the reduction in the number of iterations obtained in this way is not very big. Considering the additional computational costs for building and applying the preconditioner Figure 4.3 also shows that this may even slow down the convergence, at least for low values of $\chi h = \lambda h$. It should be noted here that the test case illustrated in Figure 4.3 with $\chi h = \lambda h$ is the worst possible, as will be discussed in more detail in Section 4.2.2.

4.2.2 Convergence behavior of BiCGStab

This section aims at illustrating the convergence properties of diagonally preconditioned BiCGStab as a function of χ , λ , and h .

Figure 4.3: Influence of preconditioning for test example 1. Shown is the number of BiCGStab iterations as a function of $\chi h = \lambda h$ with $h = 0.02$. The dashed line denotes the unpreconditioned result while the solid line denotes the preconditioned result.

Convergence as a function of λ for $\lambda h \rightarrow \chi h$: Figure 4.4 shows the convergence behavior of preconditioned BiCGStab as a function of λh for fixed χ and h with $\chi h = 1$. The picture clearly confirms what the analysis in Section 4.1.4 had predicted, namely that the convergence properties depend strongly on the value of λh . Even if $\chi h = 1$ the convergence is fast as long as λh is small enough. The figure also shows that the convergence starts to deteriorate strongly only above approximately $\lambda h = 0.7$. In physical terms this means that the convergence properties are quite good as long as scattering contributes less than about 70% to the total losses. However, Figure 4.4 shows that if this limit is exceeded convergence deteriorates rapidly even if λh is still far away from one.

Convergence as a function of $\chi h = \lambda h$: As could be seen in the previous paragraph and in Figure 4.4, the case where $\chi h = \lambda h$ is particularly bad in terms of convergence. In addition, Figure 4.5 now indicates that the number of iterations increases quite rapidly already for relatively small values of $\chi h = \lambda h$. Physically speaking this means that the convergence properties deteriorate already for a small extinction term χ if this extinction is mostly due to scattering.

Convergence as a function of h : As already indicated by the analysis in Section 4.1.4 the convergence properties of $AJ = F$ depend only slightly on h . Figure 4.6 confirms this prediction, at least for the above test example

Figure 4.4: Convergence of BiCGStab as a function of λh for fixed $\chi = 50$, $h = 0.02$, for test example 2. The value of χ is chosen such that $\chi h = 1$. Only for $\lambda h \gtrsim 0.7$ the number of iterations increases considerably.

Figure 4.5: Number of iterations of preconditioned BiCGStab as a function of $\lambda h = \chi h$ for test example 1 and two different grid spacings. The solid line denotes $h = 0.02$, the dashed line $h = 0.1$. Note that for the same χh the value of χ is much bigger for $h = 0.02$ than for $h = 0.1$.

and for the 'worst case' $\chi = \lambda$. While the grid spacing is reduced by a factor of 5, from $h = 0.1$ to $h = 0.02$, the number of iterations increases at most by 36%. Although present, the h dependence seems not to be troublesome. However, more important for practical applications is the question of how the number of iterations changes as χ and h change, while their product χh remains constant. Figure 4.5 shows that for constant χh but increasing χ the number of iterations increases as well, at least for the test case where $\lambda = \chi$. If, finally, a non-uniform mesh were used, the convergence behavior would possibly be determined by the smallest cells present.

Figure 4.6: Number of iterations of preconditioned BiCGStab as a function of $\lambda = \chi$ for test example 1 and two different grid spacings. The solid line denotes $h = 0.02$, the dashed line $h = 0.1$.

Convergence for non-constant χ and λ : In all the convergence studies just presented it was assumed that χ and λ are constant over the entire domain. In most practical application χ and λ will vary over the computational domain. What will happen? One additional test was performed with test example 1 for the following choice of non-constant χ and λ : $\chi = \lambda = 5$ for $x < 0.5$ and $\chi = \lambda = 50$ for $x \geq 0.5$. In this case 26 iterations were needed to achieve an accuracy as prescribed in test example 1. For comparison, the same example but with $\chi = \lambda = 5$ in the entire domain requires 10 iterations, for $\chi = \lambda = 50$ in the entire domain 38 iteration were needed.

Conclusions: The convergence properties of BiCGStab are strongly determined by the ratio λ/χ . If for constant χ and λ the ratio λ/χ is greater than about 0.7 convergence will be slow even for relatively small values of χh . For small ratios convergence will be fast even for $\chi h = 1$. If the ratio varies over the

computational domain between some maximum and minimum value the number of iterations needed will lie somewhere between the number of iterations required for the maximum and minimum ratio alone. In addition, if $\lambda \approx \chi$ the number of iterations increases with increasing χ for constant χh .

4.3 Error estimation

Using finite differences for the discretization of the transfer equation instead of finite element methods limits the possibilities for error estimation greatly. One way to get an idea about the quality of the solution all the same is to compare the numerical result with an analytical one for some simple test case.

4.3.1 Beam widening in the pure transport case

In the following, the situation of a monochromatic, square shaped beam is considered, which is directed parallel to one discrete ordinate direction. In the absence of absorption or scattering this beam should preserve its shape over the entire computational domain. The numerical solution, however, results in a spreading of the beam. The intensity within the analytical beam cross-section is reduced while the intensity outside this cross-section is no longer zero.

Although not very physical (there are hardly any square shaped beams in nature) this example is very popular among astrophysicists as it is a 'visible' measure for the numerical diffusion of the transport scheme in the direction transverse to the beam.

Test example: The computational domain is given by $[0, 1]^3$. The spatial discretization is equidistant with grid spacing h . The ordinate discretization consists of $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (24, 13)$ ordinates. A square shaped beam with a cross-section of 0.41×0.41 is considered. Its axis goes through $(x, y, z) = (-h, 0.3, 0.3)$. The direction the beam is aligned with the discrete ordinate direction at $\phi = \pi/12$ and $\theta = \pi/2$. ($\phi = 0$ corresponds to the positive x-axis, $\theta = \pi/2$ corresponds to the x-y-plane.) The intensity of the beam at the boundary is set to $I_0 = 10^4$. To obtain a pure transport case χ has been set to 10^{-20} , λ has been set to 10^{-21} , and f has been set to zero. That this choice of small but non-zero χ and λ does not pollute the pure transport solution can be seen from the fact that the results remain the same if both quantities are enlarged by a factor of 10^{10} . Setting the two parameters identically to zero leads to problems in the BiCGStab algorithm. The error bound for BiCGStab is set to $\epsilon = 10^{-4}$.

Figure 4.7: Beam widening for the test example described in the text for a grid spacing $h = 0.0125$. Shown is a cut parallel to the x, y -plane at height $z = 0.5$.

Error estimation: The numerically computed intensity $I^{num}(x_i)$ is compared with the analytical result, mapped onto the discrete mesh. For the mapped analytical solution $I^{anal}(x_i)$, a grid point lying within the analytical beam cross-section is assigned the value I_0 , while a point outside the beam is assigned $I^{anal}(x_i) = 0$. On this basis, the l_1 -error $\mathcal{E}_{l_1}$ and the l_∞ -error $\mathcal{E}_{l_\infty}$ are computed, given by

$$\mathcal{E}_{l_1} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |I^{num}(x_i) - I^{anal}(x_i)| \quad (4.26)$$

$$\mathcal{E}_{l_\infty} = \max_{i=1, \dots, N} |I^{num}(x_i) - I^{anal}(x_i)|. \quad (4.27)$$

Here $N = N_x \cdot N_y \cdot N_z$ denotes the total number of grid points, N_i the number of grid points in direction i . The l_1 -error is a measure of the mean error made within the entire computational domain. The l_∞ -error gives information about the local quality of the solution.

In addition, a plane perpendicular to the x -axis is considered. The plane is located at a distance $h \cdot [N_x/2]$ from the source of the beam, where $[N_x/2]$ denotes the largest integer smaller than $N_x/2$. Within this plane, the mean

h	$\mathcal{E}_{l_1}$	$\mathcal{E}_{l_\infty}$	$\bar{I}_{beam}$	$\bar{I}_{tot}$
0.125	502	7321	8384	1322
0.1	511	7321	9112	1479
0.0625	385	6077	8634	1357
0.05	391	7321	9185	1531
0.04	306	5359	8720	1276
0.03125	292	6077	8929	1380
0.025	286	7321	9305	1563
0.02	258	7321	9355	1570
0.015626	221	6077	9225	1506
0.0125	206	7321	9452	1581

Table 4.1: Error analysis for the test example of a square shaped beam directed along the discrete ordinate $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (2, 7)$, i.e in the equatorial plane at an angle of $\pi/12$ to the x-axis. Given are the l_1 -error $\mathcal{E}_{l_1}$ and the l_∞ -error $\mathcal{E}_{l_\infty}$. For the explanation of the quantities $\bar{I}_{beam}$ and $\bar{I}_{tot}$ see the text.

intensity of I^{num} over the analytical beam cross-section F^{beam} is computed,

$$\bar{I}_{beam} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K I^{num}(x_k) \quad , \quad x_k \in F^{beam}. \quad (4.28)$$

K stands for the number of grid points within F^{beam} . Also the mean value of I^{num} over the entire plane is computed,

$$\bar{I}_{tot} = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L I^{num}(x_l) \quad , \quad x_l = h \cdot \left[\frac{N_x}{2} \right], \quad (4.29)$$

where $L = N_y \cdot N_z$ denotes the number of grid points in this plane. $\bar{I}_{tot}$ has to be constant along the x-axis as long as neither the beam itself nor the intensity numerically diverted out of the beam have left the domain. Computing $\bar{I}_{tot}$ from the numerical results shows that this is indeed true. $\bar{I}_{tot}$ also indicates how well the analytic beam cross-section can be mapped onto the discrete grid. Ideally one should have $\bar{I}_{tot} = 10^4 \cdot 0.41^2 \cos \pi/12 = 1623$. $\bar{I}_{beam}$, on the other hand, in some sense measures the leaking of the beam due to the numerical scheme. Ideally, $\bar{I}_{beam}$ should be equal to $I_0 = 10^4$. Table 4.1 gives a summary of these quantities for several grid spacings h .

Looking at the l_1 -error, the quality of the numerical simulation in terms of the above quantities clearly increases with decreasing grid spacing h . However, looking at the triangles in Figure 4.8 it seems as if the l_1 -error would not tend

Figure 4.8: l_1 -error for the example of a square shaped beam for the pure transfer case. Triangles denote errors obtained by TR3D, crosses denote errors computed using the analytic expression for the numeric solution as given in Eq. 4.30. For details see text.

to zero as h goes to zero. The behavior improves if h is reduced further, i.e. below the value of $h = 0.01$ listed in Table 4.1. Due to the large memory requirements this can no longer be done by applying TR3D. However, for this particular test example and for the pure transport case (i.e. $\chi = \lambda = f = 0$) it is possible to give an analytical expression for the numerically computed value $I_{i,j,k}^{num}$ at each grid point with coordinates (x_i, y_j, z_k) . For the above example one obtains

$$I_{i,j,k}^{num} = \sum_{l=0}^i \binom{i}{l} g_1^{i-l} g_2^l I_{0,j-l,k}^{num} \quad (4.30)$$

with $g_1 = 1 - g_2$ and $g_2 = \tan\pi/12$. $I_{0,j-l,k}^{num}$ are the boundary values of I at the incoming boundary which are set either to 0 or to 10^4 . The formula can be proved by induction. Evaluating Eq. 4.30 for some additional values of h yields $\mathcal{E}_{l_1}(h)$: $\mathcal{E}_{l_1}(0.00625) = 147$, $\mathcal{E}_{l_1}(0.005) = 132$, $\mathcal{E}_{l_1}(0.004) = 118$. These errors are plotted in Figure 4.8 together with the errors obtained using the TR3D.

For this example, the l_1 -error is not monotonically decreasing with the grid spacing h and the mean intensity $\bar{I}_{beam}$ is not monotonically increasing. The reason for the *non-monotonic behavior* is that the beam cross-section fits more or less accurately on the discrete grid, depending on h . Shifting, for example, the center of the beam to $(x, y, z) = (0.0, 0.32, 0.32)$ for a grid spacing of $h = 0.04$ leads to $\mathcal{E}_{l_1} = 355$, $\mathcal{E}_{l_\infty} = 7321$, $\bar{I}_{beam} = 9196$, and $\bar{I}_{tot} = 1543$.

4.3.2 Boundaries for a spherical source

Many astrophysical applications require a spherical radiation source within the computational domain. In this section the quality of one implementation of such a source on a Cartesian grid is investigated. The implementation is rather crude and could be improved substantially, possibly by following the general ideas of Berger and LeVeque [9], [10] and Forrer [42] on the treatment of irregular boundaries. For each grid point lying within the source the specific intensity is set to the same fixed value for all directions. As in the interior of the source the absorption is so huge that there is no more transfer between neighboring points this effectively results in a source radiating with the same strength in all outwards directions. Only the pure transport case is investigated.

Test example 1: The computational domain is given by $[0, 1]^3$. The spatial discretization is equidistant, with grid spacing h . $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (24, 13)$ ordinates are used. A spherical source with a radius $R_{sou} = 0.2005$ is placed at $(x, y, z) = (0.5, 0.5, 0.5)$. Its monochromatic emission is modeled by setting $\chi = 10^5$, $\lambda = 10^{-11}$, $f = 1^9$ within the source. This choice results in a specific intensity of $I^0 = 10^4$ for all ordinate directions at points within the source. Outside the source χ and λ are set to 10^{-10} and 10^{-11} respectively, while f is zero. As in the beam widening example discussed above, this choice leads to a pure transport case. The error bound for BiCGStab is set to $\epsilon = 10^{-4}$.

Test example 2: The same as test example 1 with the exception of the radius of the source which here is $R_{sou} = 0.2205$.

Error estimation: For the error estimation the mean intensity $J^{num}(x_i)$ obtained from numerical simulations is compared to the analytical solution mapped onto the computational grid $J^{anal}(x_i)$. The comparison is done over the entire computational domain, i.e. also the interior of the source and the regions towards the edges are compared. To obtain the analytical value $J^{anal}(x_i)$ it is assumed that at the surface of the source the specific intensity I^0 is 10^4 for all directions pointing outwards of the source. The mean intensity $J^{anal}(x_i)$ at a point P outside the source is then given by

$$J^{anal}(P) = \frac{\Omega(P)}{4\pi} I^0 \quad (4.31)$$

where $\Omega(P)$ is the solid angle subtended by the source as seen from point P .

Again the l_1 -error $\mathcal{E}_{l_1}$ and the l_∞ -error $\mathcal{E}_{l_\infty}$ with respect to the analytical solution have been computed. In addition, the quantities

$$\mathcal{E}^+ = \max_i \frac{J^{num}(x_i) - J^{anal}(x_i)}{J^{anal}(x_i)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{E}^- &= \min_i \frac{J^{num}(x_i) - J^{anal}(x_i)}{J^{anal}(x_i)} \\ \bar{\mathcal{E}} &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \left| \frac{J^{num}(x_i) - J^{anal}(x_i)}{J^{anal}(x_i)} \right|\end{aligned}\quad (4.32)$$

are determined where N is the total number of grid points. They give the maximum relative errors greater and smaller than zero and the mean relative error. All these quantities are listed in Table 4.2

As can be seen, the $l1$ -error does not decrease monotonically. Also, it seems that it does hardly decrease any further once the mesh has become fine enough. The same is true for the relative errors.

The reason for the non-monotonicity is that the spherical source fits differently on differently spaced grids. A comparison between test example 1 and test example 2 in Table 4.2 shows that while a source with radius $R_{sou} = 0.2005$ produces a small $l1$ -error on a grid with $h = 0.05$ it produces a large error on a grid with $h = 0.04$. For a source with radius $R_{sou} = 0.2205$ the opposite is true.

Figure 4.9 illustrates what is happening in the vicinity of the source in two dimensions. Assume that each surface element of the source emits the same specific intensity I^0 in all directions pointing outwards of the source. Those directions pointing inwards to the source will be blocked immediately. For a point outside the source the physically correct situation would then be that the angle subtended by incoming specific intensities which are non-zero were less or equal to 2π . Point Q in Figure 4.9 illustrates this situation.

In the numerical simulation and for the present implementation of the source, however, the assignment of constant, non-zero I for each point within the source leads to a different result, as illustrated by points P and R in Figure 4.9. Point P can get non-zero contributions to $J^{num}(P)$ even from directions pointing inwards of the source. On the other hand, as illustrated by point R, there may be less directions contributing I^0 to $J^{num}(R)$ than there should be on physical grounds. Depending on whether the additional non-zero contributions or the lack of I^0 contributions dominate, $J^{num}(x_i)$ will become bigger or smaller than $J^{anal}(x_i)$.

Reducing the grid spacing h will change the quality of the fitting onto the Cartesian grid, but not in a monotonic way. It will also reduce the ratio of boundary cells to the total number of cells. The reduction of this ratio, however, will become slower and slower the finer the grid already is. This qualitatively explains why the errors seem to decrease more slowly as the grid becomes finer and finer.

Figure 4.9: *Boundary effects of spherical source as described in the text. Point P and R illustrate the numerical situation, point Q the physically correct situation. The grey shaded regions around the points denote the ordinate range of non-zero incoming specific intensity I^0 for points Q and R and the range of non-zero incoming intensity for point P. For details see text.*

h	test example 1				test example 2			
	$\mathcal{E}_{l_1}$	$\mathcal{E}_{l_\infty}$	$\mathcal{E}^+$	$\mathcal{E}^-$	$\mathcal{E}_{l_1}$	$\mathcal{E}_{l_\infty}$	$\mathcal{E}^+$	$\mathcal{E}^-$
0.125	46.5	275	0.25	-0.69	70.5	443	0.37	-0.12
0.1	35.2	301	0.33	-0.72	84.5	1344	0.094	-0.71
0.0625	61.2	654	0.30	-0.56	35.3	443	0.20	-0.13
0.05	27.7	285	0.20	-0.61	55.4	582	0.23	-0.020
0.04	58.9	722	0.25	-0.0043	31.1	811	0.14	-0.17
0.03125	52.5	815	0.20	-0.54	30.9	502	0.14	-0.58
0.025	29.4	509	0.15	-0.58	44.5	712	0.15	-0.059
0.02	33.8	614	0.16	-0.56	36.7	721	0.15	-0.56
0.015626	33.2	721	0.15	-0.48	36.9	746	0.16	-0.086
0.0125	31.4	739	0.15	-0.48	34.3	765	0.17	-0.086

Table 4.2: Error analysis for spherical source, test example 1 and test example 2. $\mathcal{E}_{l_1}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{l_\infty}$ denote the l1-error and the maximum norm error respectively. $\mathcal{E}^+$ and $\mathcal{E}^-$ are the biggest relative errors greater and smaller than zero. The relative error at point x_i is computed as $(J^{num}(x_i) - J^{anal}(x_i))/J^{anal}(x_i)$ where $J^{num}(x_i)$ and $J^{anal}(x_i)$ denote the numerical and the analytical solution respectively.

Chapter 5

TR3D: Solution of the statistical equilibrium equations

The second big task in optically thick NLTE radiative transfer is the determination of the atomic level populations at each spatial grid point. Once known they are used for the determination of the coefficients of the radiative transfer equation. The populations are determined from a non-linear system of equations, consisting of the actual rate-equations or statistical equilibrium equations and several conservation laws. The physics contained in this system of equations has already been discussed in Section 2.2.

The solution procedure applied to this non-linear system in TR3D is not very elaborate and nearly no work has gone into here, apart from coding. However, the solution of this non-linear system can be rather delicate and more work should be invested also in this part. First, the resulting population numbers may easily differ by more than ten orders of magnitude. Second, the non-linearity not only requires an iterative solution but, possibly more important, may also allow for more than one stationary solution. A first analysis of the problem of multiple solutions for the case where molecules are considered can be found in Bourlot et al. [86], [85], or Flower and Pineau des Forêts [40]. Finally, the methods applied nowadays in astronomy are mostly traditional methods, like standard Newton's method or Broyden's method. There are more modern and efficient methods in numerical mathematics which only begin to find their way into astrophysics where efficiency is a key issue, as a system of rate equations has to be solved at each spatial grid point.

5.1 Analysis of the problem

Written in matrix form, the rate equations themselves have block structure. Coupling them to the conservation laws for charge and particle numbers destroys this block structure partly. For physical reasons, this coupled system of equations is non-linear in the electron density. If techniques similar to ALI or MALI (see Section 3.2) are applied, the system may become non-linear in the actual level populations as well.

Rate equations: Consider first the rate equations on their own. In particular, assume that the electron density is already known and that, therefore, the system is linear. Using the physics and notation described in Section 2.2 the equation for the population N_{ijk} of level i of ionization state j of species k can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dN_{ijk}}{dt} = & \sum_{l \neq i} (R_{lik} + C_{lik})N_{ljk} - N_{ijk}(R_{ilk} + C_{ilk}) \\ & + (R_{\kappa ik} + C_{\kappa ik})N_{1,j+1,k} - (R_{i\kappa k} + C_{i\kappa k})N_{ijk}. \end{aligned} \quad (5.1)$$

The index κ denotes the continuum state following the bound levels i . The terms on the right hand side of the first line stand for gains and losses due to bound-bound transitions, those on the second line for gains and losses due to bound-free transitions. As stated in Section 2.2.1, for bound-free transitions it is sufficient to consider transitions from and to the ground level of the higher lying ion. The coefficients R_{lik} denote radiative transition rates and depend on the mean radiation field J , while the coefficients C_{li} denote collisional transition rates, which can be written as products of the electron density N_e and a temperature dependent function, $C_* = N_e \tilde{C}_*(T)$. It has to be kept in mind that due to the different transition probabilities for different transitions the coefficients R_{lj} and C_{lj} can differ by several orders of magnitude, even if the electron density and the radiation field are the same. Denoting by N the vector containing all level populations, the rate equations may be written in matrix form,

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = PN. \quad (5.2)$$

The general structure of matrix P is illustrated in Figure 5.1. It consists of decoupled blocks, each block describing a single species. Each of these blocks is again built up of sub-blocks, each sub-block representing one ionization stage. These sub-blocks correspond to different ionization stages and are coupled via one row and one column to account for ionization and recombination processes.

Because of the complex physics involved it is difficult to make any general statements about the size of the entries of each sub-block. The following four

extreme cases may help to obtain an impression. For a weak radiation field and low electron densities spontaneous emission and recombination terms, described by the R_{li} coefficients for $l > i$, are dominant. Therefore, the matrix is dominated by the entries in the upper triangular part of each block and the diagonal entries themselves, except for the first diagonal entry at top left of each block. This entry, and all entries in the lower triangular part, are many magnitudes smaller than the others. While in this first case the matrix is dominated by the entries describing downward transitions both upward and downward transitions are important in the remaining three cases. For a weak radiation field and very high electron densities the collisional terms described by the coefficients C_{li} are dominant. For the case of a vary strong radiation field and low electron density, the matrix will be dominated by radiation induced upward and downward transitions described by the coefficients R_{li} . Finally, if the radiation field is strong and the electron density is high both R_{li} and C_{li} are important for all l and j . In all three cases the entries of the matrix P differ mainly because of the different atomic transition probabilities.

Figure 5.1: Schematic representation of a possible matrix representation for the statistical equilibrium equations. Shaded regions indicated non-zero entries. Dark shaded regions mark the rows and columns needed for coupling the different ionization stages within one species.

Particle number conservation: The conservation of the total number of particles is, in the absence of transport effects, a physical requirement. If, in

addition, no chemical reactions and no fusion or fission occurs, even the total number of particles N_k^{tot} of each species k should be conserved,

$$\sum_{i,j} \frac{dN_{ijk}}{dt} = 0 \quad (5.3)$$

or

$$\sum_{i,j} N_{ijk} = N_k^{tot} \quad (5.4)$$

The sum runs over all levels of species k . This makes the block corresponding to species k in the rate equation matrix $\mathbf{P}$ singular.

To obtain a regular problem again one can either omit one equation per species and solve for ratios of population numbers instead of the population numbers themselves, or one can replace one equation per species by the corresponding conservation law. The latter variant allows again to solve directly for the population numbers and not only for ratios, but it changes the block structure of the matrix. If implemented in the form of eq. 5.4 it changes the right hand side of the system of equations. Another possibility is to use the relation

$$\sum_{i,j} N_{ijk} - y_k \sum_{i,j} N_{ij1} = 0 \quad (5.5)$$

where the species $k = 1$ denotes hydrogen and $y_k = N_k^{tot}/N_H^{tot}$. This variant couples all blocks to the block describing hydrogen. For hydrogen itself, eq. 5.4 still has to be applied.

Charge conservation: Charge conservation is again, in the absence of transport processes, a physical requirement. It links the level populations N_{ijk} discussed so far to another unknown, the electron density N_e ,

$$N_e = \sum_{i,j,k} j \cdot N_{ijk}. \quad (5.6)$$

Unlike particle number conservation, it destroys the linearity of the system of equations and it couples the blocks of all species. Linearity is lost because charge conservation determines the number of electrons N_e as a function of the level populations (see eq. 2.47) while at the same time the coefficients $C_* = N_e \tilde{C}_*(T)$ in the rate equations, which govern the level populations, depend on N_e . Decoupling is lost as all species together contribute to N_e .

The resulting system: Specializing now to the stationary case, what results is a system of algebraic equations for the level populations and the electron

density N_e , which is non-linear due to N_e :

$$\begin{aligned}
 0 &= \sum_{l \neq i} [(R_{lik} + C_{lik})N_{ljk} - N_{ijk}(R_{ilk} + C_{ilk})] + \\
 &\quad (R_{\kappa ik} + C_{\kappa ik})N_{1,j+1,k} - (R_{i\kappa k} + C_{i\kappa k})N_{ijk}, \\
 &\quad \forall k, \forall j, i \text{ except one per } k \\
 N_k^{tot} &= \sum_{i,j} N_{ijk}, \forall k \\
 N_e &= \sum_{i,j,k} j \cdot N_{ijk} \tag{5.7}
 \end{aligned}$$

It should be noted here that, although one is looking for a stationary solution, it is not a priori clear whether it is best in this case to look at the algebraic equations instead of the differential equations. In particular, it is not clear whether there exists only one steady state solution or whether different initial conditions lead to different solutions. In fact, if molecules are included in the computations and if chemical reactions are allowed it has been shown that there exists more than one steady state solution. (See e.g. Bourlot et al. [86], [85], or Flower and Pineau des Forêts [40].)

5.2 Solution strategies

The solution applied in TR3D: Only stationary situations are considered in TR3D. The rate equations are taken in their algebraic form as given in eq. 5.7 rather than in their differential form. Although the data structure is more general, TR3D at present treats hydrogen only. As described above, one of the rate equations is replaced by the particle conservation law for hydrogen. Charge conservation is taken into account iteratively, by computing N_e for given level populations, then computing new coefficients C_* for the rate equations, and so on. The remaining linear system of algebraic equations is solved using Householder transformations.

A glance beyond TR3D: Although not implemented in TR3D at present it seems worthwhile to look briefly at some other techniques for the solution of the rate equations and conservation laws.

Like in TR3D, the conservation law for the electron density is often split from the rest of the rate equations and is satisfied iteratively. Also, the electron density is often estimated on the basis of hydrogen and helium alone, neglecting the contributions of other elements which greatly reduces the amount of work. This proceeding is justified as these two elements contribute most to N_e . Once

a good approximation to N_e has been obtained in this way, all other elements are included again for the final determination of the electron density.

If the system of rate equations and particle conservation laws is linear, Gaussian elimination and LU-factorization are popular solution techniques. Kaushik and Hagelstein [69] suggest the use of biconjugate gradient or conjugate gradient square algorithms. If the system is non-linear Newton's method or Broyden's method are often applied. In the frame of astrophysics, one may call these 'traditional' approaches.

There are other solution techniques, seemingly less well known in astrophysics, which may do a better job. Among them are variants of the standard Newton method or other iterative solvers for linear systems.

5.3 Numerical computation of transition probabilities

The coefficients R_{li} and C_{li} of the rate equations are not fixed and have to be computed for each transition at each spatial grid point. Some of them are obtained rather easily, provided the atomic data is known. In this category fall all radiative bound-bound transitions, which can be described by Einstein transition probabilities, as well as all collisional rates where approximate formulas like those given in eq. 2.37, 2.38, and 2.40 can be used. Other coefficients require more work. In the frame of TR3D these are the coefficients describing radiative bound-free transitions. It is these coefficients the present section is devoted to.

As can be seen from eq. 2.28, 2.30, and 2.29 the coefficients for radiative bound-free transitions require the evaluation of integrals over frequency space. Obviously, the integrals for photoionization and stimulated emission cannot be 'pre-calculated' and stored in parameterized form as they depend on the mean intensity J and have to be evaluated numerically for each transition at each spatial grid point. The integral describing spontaneous emission depends only on the temperature and its values for each transition may be tabulated as a function of temperature. However, in TR3D it is computed as well.

At first glance, it may seem reasonable to use Gauss quadrature with $\exp(-h\nu/kT)$ as weight functions for the integrals in eq. 2.29 and 2.30. However, there are two obstacles to this approach. First, this would require a substitution $x = -h\nu/kT + h\nu_0/kT$, where ν_0 is the ionization frequency for a particular atomic level. With this substitution the cross-section $\alpha_{i,\kappa}(\nu)$ would become a function of the temperature T and the threshold frequency ν_0 . Therefore, for fixed integration support points x as required by Gauss-quadrature, these cross-sections would have to be recomputed for each new temperature.

This can become quite costly as the formulas describing these cross-sections can be rather complex. Second, it turns out to be better to use the same integration formula for the computation of the stimulated emission coefficients and the photoionization coefficients. However, the integrand for the photoionization coefficients is not appropriate for the use of Gauss-quadrature. Why the same integration formula should be used may be illustrated as follows. For a strong radiation field these coefficients become very large. For a fixed transition, they enter the rate equations with opposite sign and become multiplied by different level populations. And although their contributions nearly cancel their difference may still dominate some level populations. If now both coefficients are computed with the same integration formula one can hope that the quadrature errors of the two integrals mutually cancel and that the difference between the two coefficients reflects the physical difference quite well. Although this is by no means guaranteed.

Instead of Gauss quadrature a Newton-Cotes quadrature formula of order four is used, which with the same support points is applicable to all three integrals. The support points for each ion are now fixed in frequency space and the cross-sections $\alpha_{i,\kappa}(\nu)$ have to be computed only once. As the integrand depends very strongly on temperature two fixed sets of support points have to be chosen for each atomic level. A 'special' set for low temperatures with $h\nu/kT \gtrsim 10$, where the integrand decreases very steeply near the ionization frequency ν_0 , and a 'regular' set of support points for higher temperatures. If for very high temperatures $h\nu/kT$ is close to zero for a wide frequency range, the integrand decreases nevertheless with increasing frequency due to the decrease of $\alpha_{i,\kappa}(\nu)$. The integration at a particular grid point usually makes use of only part of all support points.

For the 'regular' set, the integration interval $[\nu_0, \nu_{max}]$ is divided into several subintervals of size $[10^i, 10^{i+1}]$. Each of these subinterval is covered by $4n + 1$ equidistant support points, interval boundaries included, corresponding to a summed Newton-Cotes quadrature formula of order four. For $4n + 1 = 13$ points this leads to a quadrature error for the spontaneous emission rate which is smaller than 1%. The upper integration boundary ν_{max} is temperature dependent and is chosen such that the truncation error remains smaller than a prescribed tolerance.

For temperatures with $h\nu/kT \gtrsim 10$ the integrand decreases very steeply near the threshold frequency ν_0 and the support points in this case are distributed equidistantly in the vicinity of ν_0 . As in this regime the integrand is very sensitive to the values of ν and T , the quadrature rule using fixed support points may not be appropriate for all transitions at all grid points.

Chapter 6

TR3D as a whole

Having solvers for the transfer equation and the rate equation part the two now have to be brought together. In the frame of this work only pure iteration between the two parts is applied. The simulation is assumed to have converged if between succeeding iterations the relative changes of all level populations and of the radiation field are smaller than a given global tolerance. As mentioned earlier, mere iteration between the transfer equation and the rate equation part often fails. Instead some sort of ALI and MALI scheme as mentioned in Chapter 3 should be used.

Section 6.1 and 6.2 focus on the error analysis for the entire code, which is much more difficult than the error analysis presented for the transfer equation. Although only hydrogen is included only certain aspects of the solution can be compared with analytical results. Other aspects have to be compared with the results of other codes. Evaluating which part of the solution can be identified with an analytical result is a task on its own. And also the comparison itself, with analytical or other computational results, is often not straightforward. The physical assumptions, the physics included, and the numerics applied in another code will usually not be the same. Consequently, the results will usually differ for several reasons and it is crucial to pin these reasons down to either numerical or physical differences or to 'real errors'.

In Section 6.3 some remarks will be made on the parallelization of TR3D. Conclusions with regard to TR3D are presented in Section 6.4.

6.1 Error analysis for nebular conditions

In the following, the behaviour of TR3D under nebular conditions is investigated. A brief description of the nebular approximation has already been given

in Section 2.3. Roughly speaking, one may say that under nebular conditions basically all ions are in their ground state and that for most lines the emitted radiation escapes freely. Although applying TR3D under nebular conditions is like breaking a butterfly on the wheel, this is a valuable and comparatively easy test for part of the physics and numerics of TR3D. In particular, part of the physical data, the numerical evaluation of transition probabilities, the continuum absorption, and the interplay between the transfer part and the rate equation part can be tested.

Test examples: In the following, two similar test examples will be discussed in greater detail. The basic set up of the two examples consists of a (spherical) black body source, a star, which is located at a distance of a homogeneous matter distribution. The matter has a prescribed temperature and density which is such that the matter is nearly completely ionized by the radiation of the black body. The matter consists of hydrogen only. In TR3D the hydrogen atom is restricted to its first ten levels. The substructure of the levels is ignored. The Lyman lines, i.e. the bound-bound transitions to the ground state, are assumed to be completely optically thick, while all other bound-bound transitions are assumed to be completely optically thin. Consequently, each radiative recombination must finally end in the $n = 2$ level from where it is assumed to decay to $n = 1$ by two-photon-decay.

The actual parameters for the black body source are $T^* = 80000$ K and $R^* = 10^9$ cm. The distance from the star to the matter distribution is 10^{14} cm. This gives the incoming specific intensity at $x = 0$, in the direction parallel to the x-axis and in the equatorial plane. The matter distribution has a spatial extension of 10^{16} cm. Its density and temperature are $N = 7 \cdot 10^5$ part/cm³, $T = 10000$ K in *example 1* and $N = 4 \cdot 10^5$ part/cm³, $T = 5000$ K in *example 2*. For these parameters hydrogen is ionized to more than 90%.

The cell size is 10^{15} cm and the errors for BiCGStab and global convergence have both been set to 0.01. A total of $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (24, 13)$ ordinates and 95 continuum frequency points have been used. Figure 6.1 and Figure 6.2 show the corresponding spectra computed with TR3D.

6.1.1 Comparison with analytical results

Although even under nebular conditions the problem of radiative transfer as a whole is too complex to be solved analytically, some quantities can be computed or at least approximated to a high degree of accuracy by analytical formulas. Among them are the direct recombination coefficients into the different energy levels of the hydrogen atom, the line strengths of the hydrogen Balmer lines relative to H_β , and the effective recombination coefficients for these transitions.

Figure 6.1: *Emitted spectra computed with TR3D for example 1. Shown is the entire computed spectrum (left) and a zoom (right) in flux (in $\text{ergs/cm}^2 \text{s} \text{Å}$) against wavelength (in Å).*

Figure 6.2: *Emitted spectra computed with TR3D for example 2. Shown is the entire computed spectrum (left) and a zoom (right) in flux (in $\text{ergs/cm}^2 \text{s} \text{Å}$) against wavelength (in Å).*

T	n	α_n	$R_{\kappa n}/N_\kappa$	rel. error
5000	1	$2.28 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$2.27 \cdot 10^{-13}$	0.004
	2	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$1.16 \cdot 10^{-13}$	0.008
	3	$7.33 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$7.31 \cdot 10^{-13}$	0.002
	4	$5.02 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$5.05 \cdot 10^{-13}$	-0.005
10000	1	$1.58 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$1.58 \cdot 10^{-13}$	< 0.001
	2	$7.69 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$7.66 \cdot 10^{-14}$	0.003
	3	$4.55 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$4.54 \cdot 10^{-14}$	0.002
	4	$2.96 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$2.96 \cdot 10^{-14}$	< 0.001

Table 6.1: Comparison of analytically computed direct recombination coefficients α_n in units $\text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$ and of the corresponding quantity $R_{\kappa n}/N_\kappa$ computed in TR3D, for the first four energy levels of hydrogen for temperatures of 5000K and 10000K.

In the following, the analytical values of these quantities will be compared to the results of TR3D.

Direct recombination: Analytical expressions for the direct recombination coefficients $\alpha_1(T)$ to $\alpha_4(T)$ into one of the first four energy levels of hydrogen as a function of temperature can be found, for example, in Osterbrock [110]. Multiplying these coefficients with the number of electrons and ions gives the number of recombinations into a particular level per cm^3 and per second. In the frame of TR3D the number of recombinations into level n is given by $N_\kappa R_{\kappa n}$ and computed according to eq. 2.28 to 2.30. Having only fully ionized hydrogen it follows that the direct recombination coefficients α_n should be compared with $R_{\kappa n}/N_\kappa$. In Table 6.1 $\alpha_1(T)$ to $\alpha_4(T)$ are listed for 10000K and 5000K along with the coefficients $R_{\kappa n}/N_\kappa$ computed in TR3D. Comparison shows that the coefficients agree quite well. For TR3D this means that *the numerical evaluation of the integrals in eq. 2.28 to 2.30 is very accurate* for all considered transitions at the same time, at least for this test example.

Despite the good agreement of the direct recombination coefficients for each level, the total radiative recombination in TR3D will usually be too small. This is due to the fact that only a few energy levels are taken into account. For a ten level hydrogen atom TR3D yields

$$\alpha_{10}^{tot} = \sum_{n=1}^{10} \alpha_n = 3.77 \cdot 10^{-13} \quad T = 10000K \quad (6.1)$$

$$\alpha_{10}^{tot} = \sum_{n=1}^{10} \alpha_n = 5.93 \cdot 10^{-13} \quad T = 5000K. \quad (6.2)$$

	T=5000,N=10 ⁴	T=10000,N=10 ⁴	T=10000,N=10 ⁶
$\alpha_{H\beta}^{eff}$	5.44	3.03	3.07
$j_{3,2}/j_{H\beta}$	3.00	2.85	2.81
$j_{5,2}/j_{H\beta}$	0.460	0.469	0.471
$j_{6,2}/j_{H\beta}$	0.253	0.260	0.262
$j_{7,2}/j_{H\beta}$	0.155	0.159	0.163
$j_{8,2}/j_{H\beta}$	0.102	0.105	0.110
$j_{9,2}/j_{H\beta}$	0.0714	0.0734	0.0786
$j_{10,2}/j_{H\beta}$	0.0520	0.0533	0.0590

Table 6.2: Balmer line intensities relative to $H\beta$ for different temperatures and densities (taken from Osterbrock [122]). The effective recombination coefficient $\alpha_{H\beta}^{eff}$ is given in units $10^{-14} \text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$.

Comparing this with the analytical result

$$\alpha_{\infty}^{tot} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_n = 4.18 \cdot 10^{-13} \quad T = 10000K \quad (6.3)$$

$$\alpha_{\infty}^{tot} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_n = 6.82 \cdot 10^{-13} \quad T = 5000K \quad (6.4)$$

one obtains relative errors $(\alpha_{\infty}^{tot} - \alpha_{10}^{tot})/\alpha_{\infty}^{tot}$ of 10% and 13% respectively. As will be seen later on, this reduced total recombination leads to a reduced continuum absorption below 912 Å.

Line emission: Here the goal is to test the atomic level populations computed in TR3D, at least for nebular conditions. Line emissions allow to investigate the atomic level populations assuming that the tabulated transition probabilities for bound-bound transitions are correct. However, as only fully ionized hydrogen and only recombination lines are studied, this test for the level populations in some sense is not much more than another test for the correctness of the recombination coefficients.

The analytical values for the line emission are obtained from Osterbrock [110]. For optically thin recombination lines one there finds an effective recombination coefficient $\alpha_{H\beta}^{eff}$ for the $H\beta$ line as well as the Balmer line intensities $j_{nn'}$ relative to $j_{H\beta}$. $j_{nn'}$ is the emitted energy per cm^3 per time per unite solid angle and is related to $\alpha_{nn'}^{eff}$ by

$$N_p N_e \alpha_{nn'}^{eff} = \frac{4\pi j_{nn'}}{h\nu_{nn'}}. \quad (6.5)$$

	example 1			example 2		
	theor.	TR3D	rel.error	theor.	TR3D	rel.error
$j_{3,2}$	1729	1387	0.25	1072	767	0.40
$j_{4,2}$	607	500	0.21	362	289	0.25
$j_{5,2}$	285	246	0.16	167	147	0.14
$j_{6,2}$	158	150	0.05	92	86	0.07
$j_{7,2}$	96	87	0.10	57	54	0.06
$j_{8,2}$	64	57	0.12	37	36	0.03
$j_{9,2}$	45	38	0.18	26	24	0.08
$j_{10,2}$	32	25	0.28	19	17	0.12

Table 6.3: Comparison of theoretical Balmer line strengths and line strengths computed by TR3D. Shown are the results for example 1 (left), $T=10000K$, $N=7 \cdot 10^5 \text{ part/cm}^3$, and example 2 (right), $T=5000K$, $N=4 \cdot 10^5 \text{ part/cm}^3$. The deviation is considerable, but can be understood on the basis that the line emission is purely due to recombination and that only the first ten energy levels of the hydrogen atom have been included in the numerical simulations. Note that the theoretical values have been interpolated for the weak density dependence.

From these tabulated values the effective recombination coefficients $\alpha_{nn'}^{eff}$ for any Balmer line transition can then be computed as,

$$\alpha_{nn'}^{eff} = \frac{j_{nn'} \nu_{\beta}}{j_{H_{\beta}} \nu_{nn'}} \alpha_{H_{\beta}}^{eff}. \quad (6.6)$$

For given values of N_p and N_e it is now possible to compute $j_{nn'}$ itself and to compare the result with the line emission obtained with TR3D. The results are listed in Table 6.3. As can be seen, the line emissions produced by TR3D are all too small, by 3 to 40 percent.

That these recombination lines are too weak is not surprising. As already mentioned, the model computed with TR3D lacks part of the total radiative recombination as only the first ten energy levels of the hydrogen atom are considered. Less obvious is why the relative errors show such differences for different line transitions. This point is going to be analyzed more closely in the following. The key for understanding why these results are consistent with the ten level hydrogen atom used in TR3D lies in the so called effective transition probabilities P_{nm} .

P_{nm} gives the probability that a transition starting at upper level n ends at lower level m . Consider now a particular line transition from level m to level l . Using only the first ten levels of the hydrogen atom and considering only cases

where $m, n \leq 10$ the relative error for this line transition is then given by

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_{rel}(j_{ml}) &= \frac{(\alpha_m + \sum_{n=m+1}^{\infty} \alpha_n P_{nm}) - (\alpha_m + \sum_{n=m+1}^{10} \alpha_n P_{nm})}{\alpha_m + \sum_{n=m+1}^{10} \alpha_n P_{nm}} \\ &= \frac{\sum_{n=11}^{\infty} \alpha_n P_{nm}}{\alpha_m + \sum_{n=m+1}^{10} \alpha_n P_{nm}}.\end{aligned}\quad (6.7)$$

The effective transitions probabilities P_{nm} themselves are given by

$$P_{nm} = P_{nm}^d + \sum_{k=m+1}^{n-1} P_{nk}^d P_{km}, \quad (6.8)$$

where P_{nm}^d denotes the transition probability for direct transitions from level n to level m , given by

$$P_{nm}^d = \frac{A_{nm}}{\sum_{k=2}^{n-1} A_{nk}}. \quad (6.9)$$

Here it has been assumed that there are no transitions from level n directly to the ground state level. This is consistent with the above assumption that the Lyman lines are optically thick. Some of the probabilities P_{nm} are listed in Table 6.4.

Although $\epsilon_{rel}(j_{ml})$ in eq. 6.7 cannot be evaluated exactly with the data at disposal, it is possible to give an approximate value for it. If P_{nm} for $n > 7$, the highest value for which P_{nm} is available in this work, were constant P_{nm} could be taken out of both sums in eq. 6.7. Assuming the correctness of the total recombination to the first ten levels as computed by TR3D (see eq. 6.1 and 6.2) and using eq. 6.3 and 6.4, both sums in eq. 6.7 then could be evaluated and an estimate for $\epsilon_{rel}(j_{ml})$ could be obtained. The question is now whether it is indeed possible to assume P_{nm} to be constant in these sums and at which value. Indeed, one may argue that, as the cross-sections α_n decrease rapidly with increasing n , the first few terms of each sum contribute most to the sum. Also P_{nm} decreases with increasing $|n - m|$. Consequently, for a large enough value of i $\sum_{n=i}^k \alpha_n P_{nm}$ may be replaced by $\tilde{P}_m \sum_{n=i}^k \alpha_n$, where $\tilde{P}_m$ is chosen somewhat smaller than P_{im} .

Consider, for example, $\epsilon_{rel}(j_{42})$. With $\tilde{P}_4 = 0.3$ (see Table 6.4) one obtains $\epsilon_{rel}(j_{42}) \approx 0.25$ for 10000K and $\epsilon_{rel}(j_{42}) \approx 0.30$ for 5000K. For $\tilde{P}_4 = 0.25$ one finds $\epsilon_{rel}(j_{42}) \approx 0.22$ for 10000K and $\epsilon_{rel}(j_{42}) \approx 0.27$ for 5000K. For $\epsilon_{rel}(j_{32})$ one may choose $\tilde{P}_3 = 0.45$ or $\tilde{P}_3 = 0.40$. For 10000K this yields $\epsilon_{rel}(j_{32}) \approx 0.21$ and $\epsilon_{rel}(j_{32}) \approx 0.20$ respectively.

Although the choice of the constant value for $\tilde{P}_m$ has some influence on $\epsilon_{rel}(j_{ml})$ this influence is rather moderate. The relative errors change from 25% to 22% or from 30% to 27%. As can be seen, these values agree quite

	m=2	m=3	m=4	m=5	m=6
n=3	1.000	-	-	-	-
n=4	1.000	0.5163	-	-	-
n=5	1.000	0.4838	0.3633	-	-
n=6	1.000	0.4714	0.3223	0.2889	-
n=7	1.000	0.4651	0.3060	0.2457	0.2452

Table 6.4: *Effective transition probabilities P_{nm} computed according to eq. 6.8. P_{nm} gives the probability that a transition starting at level n will end up at level m . As it has been assumed that all Lyman lines are optically thick there are no downward line transitions to $m = 1$, and each radiative recombination must finally end in the $n = 2$ level instead, from where two-photon-decay leads to the ground state.*

well with the relative errors obtained from the computations and the presented analysis provides a qualitative and roughly quantitative explanation of these results.

Conclusion: From what has been said in this section it can be concluded that the integrals for the radiative recombination rates and, therefore, the continuum emission, are computed very accurately by TR3D, at least under nebular conditions, for temperatures between 5000K and 10000K, and for fully ionized matter (higher than 90%). The recombination lines are generally too weak, but it has been shown that this deviation can be traced to missing recombination into higher lying levels. This problem is, however, not particular to TR3D but is common to most optically thick NLTE radiative transfer codes. In the frame of the physics included and for the presented test examples it can further be concluded that the NLTE level populations are computed correctly.

6.1.2 Comparison with an existing code

The continuum absorption exerted by the matter in the entire domain can hardly be computed analytically. The reason is the strong coupling between the radiation field and the number of neutral hydrogen atoms, which is responsible for the continuum absorption below 912 Å. The radiation field determines the number of neutral hydrogen atoms which in turn due to absorption change the radiation field.

Not enough absorption, for example due to a lack of neutral hydrogen atoms, leaves the radiation field too strong. Consequently, there are too many ionizations and the number of neutral hydrogen atoms decreases, leading to an even

increased lack of absorption. It is clear that in the above examples TR3D will underestimate the continuum absorption. The insufficient recombination rate caused by this restricted model atom leads to overionization and a too small amount of hydrogen atoms in their ground state. The back coupling just described makes it also difficult to give an estimate of the error.

Short description of the existing code: Comparison will be made with the code NEBEL, developed at the Institute of Astronomy at ETH Zurich for the computation of nebular emission under the assumption of spherical symmetry. A brief description of the code can be found in Nussbaumer and Schild [103], Vogel [152], and Schild [125]. Here only some additional information on the computation of the continuum absorption is given.

To compute the ionization stage of the matter this code uses tabulated total recombination coefficients. The number of neutral hydrogen atoms is determined with these tabulated recombination coefficients and can therefore be assumed to be rather accurate. The continuum absorption between points x_0 and x_1 is computed as $I(x_1) = I(x_0)e^{-(x_1-x_0)\chi}$. If the ionization structure changes considerably between points x_0 and x_1 the absorption computed in this way depends strongly on whether one takes the atomic populations of point x_1 or x_0 or of an interpolated value. Figure 6.3 illustrates this problem. There, two spectra computed by NEBEL are given, one using the atomic populations of point i the other of point $i + 1$ for the computation of the absorption on the interval $[i, i + 1]$. For the comparison with TR3D it also has to be stressed that the spatial step size used in NEBEL is adaptive and was smaller than the 10^{15} cm used in TR3D. Attempts to use the same step size as in TR3D also in NEBEL were fruitless as the atomic level populations no longer converged for this step size. For the continuum emission direct recombination coefficients are again used in NEBEL. Provided the ionization stage is computed correctly the continuum emission then should be very accurate. For the line emission of recombination lines, effective recombination coefficients are used. They are computed with fit formulae. Their accuracy compared with tabulated values depends on the transition under consideration and ranges between 1% and 15%. Both, continuum emission and emission in recombination lines, do not depend on whether atomic data at point i or point $i + 1$ is used as long as the matter is nearly completely ionized.

Comparison with TR3D, continuum absorption: Looking at the discretization used in TR3D, the absorption coefficient used to compute the absorption on an interval $[i, i + 1]$ is that at point $i + 1$. The results of TR3D simulations, therefore, should be compared to those of NEBEL taking the absorption coefficient χ based on the atomic level populations at point $i + 1$.

For comparison, example 1 described on page 70 is considered. Looking at

Figure 6.3: Comparison of continuum absorption computed with NEBEL for example 1 using the atomic data of point i (left) and point $i + 1$ (right) to compute the continuum absorption on the interval $[i, i + 1]$. The continuum emission is not influenced by the choice of either point i or point $i + 1$, because the matter is nearly completely ionized at both points. Shown is the flux (in $\text{ergs}/\text{cm}^2 \text{ s } \text{Å}$) against wavelength (in Å).

Figure 6.4 and Figure 6.3 shows that the continuum absorption computed by TR3D is too small, as expected. Again now the causes of this differences have to be pinned down.

A first difference lies in the total recombination rate. Looking again at Figure 6.4 it can be seen that the results can be somewhat improved by artificially increasing the total recombination rate in TR3D to the value of $\alpha_{tot} = 4.18$, the value used by NEBEL.

The main cause of deviation is, however, that NEBEL attenuates the radiation field according to

$$I(x_1) = I(x_0)e^{-\Delta x \chi} \quad (6.10)$$

over $\Delta x = x_1 - x_0$ with a *fixed* value of χ computed from the atomic level populations at one particular point in the interval $[x_0, x_1]$. Eq. 6.10 is the correct solution of

$$\frac{\partial I}{\partial x} + \chi I = 0. \quad (6.11)$$

In TR3D, on the other hand, one has

$$I(x_1) = \frac{1}{1 + \Delta x \chi} I(x_0). \quad (6.12)$$

For $\Delta x \chi \ll 1$ both formulae lead to

$$I(x_1) = (1 - \Delta x \chi) I(x_0) + \mathcal{O}(\Delta x^2). \quad (6.13)$$

For bigger values of $\Delta x\chi$ the two results diverge. For $\Delta x\chi = 0.5$ Eq. 6.10 yields $I(x_1) = 0.6065 I(x_0)$ while for Eq. 6.12 one finds $I(x_1) = 0.6667 I(x_0)$. For $\Delta x\chi = 1.0$ one obtains $I(x_1) = 0.3679 I(x_0)$ and $I(x_1) = 0.5000 I(x_0)$ respectively.

Using Eq. 6.12 in NEBEL for the attenuation of the radiation field instead of Eq. 6.10, the agreement becomes much better as can be seen from Figure 6.5. Most of the remaining difference is probably due to the different spatial step size.

Figure 6.4: Continuum absorption computed by TR3D for example 1 with a ten level hydrogen atom (left) and with an artificially enhanced recombination rate (right) to account for the missing higher lying levels. In this second computation, the total recombination rate corresponds to the theoretically expected, whereas in the first computation it is too small by about 11%. Shown is the flux (in $\text{ergs/cm}^2 \text{ s } \text{\AA}$) against wavelength (in $\text{\AA}$).

Comparison with TR3D, continuum emission: Although already analyzed in Section 6.1.1, continuum emission is briefly looked at once more. Looking at Figure 6.4 and Figure 6.3 it can be seen that the Balmer continuum emission produced by the two codes for example 1 is nearly identical. Although not depicted, the same applies to example 2.

On the one side, this agreement is due to the correctness of the direct recombination coefficient into the $n=2$ level, which has already been demonstrated in Section 6.1.1. On the other hand, the agreement is also due to the fact that the matter in this example is nearly completely ionized. If this were not the case, the incorrect continuum absorption discussed above could have considerable influence on the continuum emission as well.

Figure 6.5: Continuum absorption computed for example 1 with NEBEL using $1/(1 + \Delta x \chi)$ for the attenuation of the radiation field (left) and computed with TR3D using artificially enhanced total recombination (right). Shown is the flux (in $\text{ergs/cm}^2 \text{ s } \text{\AA}$) against wavelength (in $\text{\AA}$).

Comparison with TR3D, line emission: Again this topic has already been discussed above in analytical terms. The computed line strengths with NEBEL and with TR3D as well as the relative error for example 1 and 2 are given in Table 6.5. Comparison with Table 6.3 shows that, in particular for higher lying levels or for lower temperatures, the relative error is higher now than it was with respect to the analytically computed line emissions. As NEBEL uses fit formulas for the computation of these emission lines the analytical results are considered to be more relevant.

Conclusions: From what has been shown in this section three main conclusions can be drawn. *First*, the agreement of the results produced by NEBEL and TR3D, if in NEBEL the same attenuation formula is used as in TR3D, shows that the full transfer problem (transfer plus rate equations) is solved correctly in TR3D, at least under nebular conditions and if attenuation can be treated by eq. 6.12. *Second*, even under the assumption of constant χ , λ , and η the attenuation of the radiation field in TR3D is properly calculated only for small values of $\Delta x \chi$, where Δx is the distance between two grid points. If these coefficients are indeed constant, the NEBEL code will give the correct attenuation of the radiation field. *Third*, if χ , λ , and η vary between grid points, as in most applications they will, it can make a considerable difference whether these coefficients are computed from the atomic data at point x_i or at point x_{i+1} . This second problem is present in TR3D as well as in NEBEL.

	example 1			example 2		
	NEBEL	TR3D	rel.error	NEBEL	TR3D	rel.error
$j_{3,2}$	1710	1387	0.23	1114	767	0.45
$j_{4,2}$	611	500	0.22	384	289	0.33
$j_{5,2}$	290	246	0.18	180	147	0.22
$j_{6,2}$	163	150	0.09	102	86	0.19
$j_{7,2}$	103	87	0.18	65	54	0.20
$j_{8,2}$	71	57	0.25	45	36	0.23
$j_{9,2}$	51	38	0.34	33	24	0.37
$j_{10,2}$	38	25	0.52	27	17	0.59

Table 6.5: Comparison of Balmer line strengths computed with NEBEL and TR3D. Shown are the results for example 1 with $T=10000K$, $N=7 \cdot 10^5$ part/cm³ (left), and example 2 with $T=10000K$, $N=7 \cdot 10^5$ part/cm³ (right). For higher lying levels the relative error here is bigger than the one computed with respect to the theoretical line strengths. For details see text.

6.2 Error analysis for optically thick lines

In TR3D optically thick lines are handled by means of Sobolev theory, a brief outline of which has been given in Section 2.3. As stated there, Sobolev theory requires the computation of photon escape probabilities β . They give the probability that a photon produced in a spectral line actually can escape for good from the spatial location where it has been produced. In the following, these probabilities as computed in TR3D are compared to analytical values for one particular test example.

Analytical values for β : Several analytical results for β can be found in Mihalas [96], for example for the case of a uniformly expanding, plane-parallel matter distribution. It is assumed that the density is constant and that the plane extends to infinity. The velocity gradient $\partial v/\partial r$, where r is the direction perpendicular to the plane, is assumed to be constant as well. The escape probability at a particular point is then given by

$$\beta = |\gamma| \int_0^1 \{1 - \exp[-1/(|\gamma|\mu^2)]\} \mu^2 d\mu \quad (6.14)$$

where

$$\gamma = \partial v/\partial r \cdot 1/(\chi_L v_{th}). \quad (6.15)$$

Here χ_L denotes the total absorption coefficient of the line and v_{th} is the thermal velocity, $v_{th} = [8k/(\pi m)]^{1/2} \cdot (T/A)^{1/2}$, where k is the Boltzmann

constant, m the atomic mass unit, and A the atomic number. It should be noted that the line absorption coefficient χ_L in eq. 6.15 is not expressed analytically and has to be supplied otherwise.

β from TR3D: The corresponding test example in TR3D consists of a matter distribution as described above. The computational domain has a size of $1.1 \cdot 10^{13}$ cm, with a grid spacing of $1.1 \cdot 10^{12}$ cm. The ordinate discretization consists of $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (24, 13)$ ordinates. The domain is irradiated by a black body source of $T^* = 10^5$ K and $R^* = 1.96 \cdot 10^{10}$ cm, located at a distance of $1.022 \cdot 10^{13}$ cm from the domain boundary. The matter is assumed to have a temperature of 8000 K, leading for $A = 1$ to $v_{th} = 1.2967 \cdot 10^6$ cm/s. The velocity gradient in the direction perpendicular to the plane is taken to be $\partial v / \partial r = 1.862 \cdot 10^{-6}$ s $^{-1}$. The considered matter densities are given in Table 6.6.

That the domain is finite now instead of infinite causes problems for directions where there is no velocity gradient at all. For the present test problem, these are the directions perpendicular to the normal of the plane. For such directions, the escape probability of a photon is only determined by the total column density (i.e. in some sense the total amount of matter) in that direction. In particular, for an infinitely extended plane the escape probability in such a direction is zero. It turns out that for such directions the size of the computational domain is too small to reproduce the analytical results. The escape probabilities become much too big. Therefore, the total absorption in directions where there is no velocity gradient at all has artificially been enhanced by a factor of ten. This reduces the escape probabilities for these directions and brings the total escape probability β closer to the analytical value.

One may now hope to obtain even better agreement with the analytical result by further enhancing the total absorption for directions where there is no velocity gradient. However, here numerical cancellation effects come into play in the sense that a numerically computed velocity gradient becomes zero (or close to zero) whereas in reality it still would be non-zero. So in reality the interaction region of the photon would still be finite although extended. In the numerical simulation, however, the interaction region is considered to be 'infinite' and the escape probability for this direction is underestimated. In fact, enhancing the total absorption by a factor of 1000 instead of only ten for directions where there is no numerical velocity gradient reduces β slightly below the analytical value.

A comparison of the analytical and computed values of β for the H_α line is given in Table 6.6. While in general the values for β agree quite well it can be seen that β computed with TR3D is generally somewhat too high, due to the finite domain size and despite the artificial enhancement of the total absorption by a factor of ten. To compare β given in eq. 6.14 with the values obtained with TR3D for the test example just described, it is necessary

$\log_{10}(N)$	χ_L	β TR3D	β anal.	rel. error
3.1	1.430 (-14)	0.9108	0.8870	0.0268
3.2	3.604 (-14)	0.8413	0.8252	0.0195
3.2	9.074 (-14)	0.7439	0.7343	0.0131
3.4	2.281 (-13)	0.6109	0.6070	0.00643
3.5	5.724 (-13)	0.4464	0.4449	0.00337
3.6	1.430 (-12)	0.2714	0.2708	0.00222
3.7	3.548 (-12)	0.1314	0.1312	0.00152
3.8	8.696 (-12)	0.05514	0.05504	0.00182
3.9	2.099 (-11)	0.02284	0.02284	< 0.00005

Table 6.6: Comparison of analytical and numerical values of β_{H_α} for the test example of an infinitely extended plane as described in the text. N denotes the constant particle density. χ_L is the total line absorption coefficient as computed in TR3D. The last column contains the relative errors.

to insert χ_L from TR3D into eq. 6.15. Therefore, it is actually merely the quality of the computation of β for a given χ_L which is tested here. As a by product, Table 6.6 shows that the change between 'free escape' ($\beta = 1$) and 'total trapping' ($\beta = 0$) takes place in a rather narrow density range.

Conclusions: The present example illustrates, on the one hand, that the escape probabilities β generally are computed correctly in TR3D. This is noticeable because in TR3D β is obtained as a — numerically evaluated — integral over the sphere S^2 of the directed escape probabilities $\beta(n)$ where each discrete directed escape probability β^m contains a — numerically evaluated — directed velocity derivative. The related problems have been discussed above. In spherical symmetry, as often considered in astrophysics, and for a constant velocity gradient, both tasks can be performed analytically. On the other hand, the fact that intermediate ranged β 's (i.e. not zero or one) depend strongly on the total column density in directions where there is no or hardly any velocity gradient illustrates a general problem of the use of Sobolev theory in full 3D geometry. In a general 3D matter distribution it is very likely that there are directions where there is no velocity gradient. For these directions their total column density becomes important, which is a non-local quantity. Actually, Sobolev theory, which is a local theory, is no longer applicable under such conditions.

6.3 Aspects of parallelization

Due to the huge memory and CPU requirements multidimensional NLTE radiative transfer is a candidate for parallelization, preferably on distributed memory machines. Up to now we have parallelized the transfer part using MPI. In fact, the radiative transfer problem as considered here is very well suited for parallelization. Being decoupled in frequency, the transfer part can be split according to frequency. The rate equation part can be treated by domain decomposition. Load balancing, however, is difficult in real size problems. The coefficients of the transfer equation depend strongly on frequency and so does the number of iterations which can be hardly estimated a priori. The convergence properties of the rate equations can also vary considerably from point to point making an a priori estimate of the work to be done again difficult. Also the practical implementation on distributed memory machines is somewhat delicate. For the present problem the distribution of the memory among different nodes requires that most of the memory has to be communicated twice in each global iteration step, because the solution of the transfer equation for one particular frequency point needs data for this frequency point for all the spatial grid points, while the solution of the rate equation part at one particular spatial grid point needs data for this grid point and for all frequencies. Although the time required for this communication is not too important, as one global iteration step takes much longer anyhow, the 'logistics' of the memory exchange are quite difficult to program. From this point of view shared memory machines seem better suited, but they usually offer less memory.

6.4 Discussion and conclusions

The approach presented here, the code TR3D, differs from other existing approaches in that it uses a generalized mean intensity approach for the solution of the transfer equation. It is the first time that such a generalized mean intensity approach is used in the context of the NLTE radiative transfer problem. At the moment, the code features an advanced solver for the transfer equation, a state of the art solver for the rate equation part, and an iterative coupling between the two. Extended Sobolev theory is used for the treatment of optically thick lines. Its main advantages lie in the transfer part, in its h -independence, the use of a modern, iterative solver, and the modest memory requirements of this part. The code has been successfully tested for some simple NLTE radiative transfer problems and in its present state is on the break of being applied to 'real' problems. So far, there was no possibility to compare TR3D with other codes.

Necessary improvements to be made are the implementation of an adaptive grid, the development of a more elaborate coupling between the transfer and

the rate equation part, and the implementation of other than vacuum boundary conditions.

The *implementation of an adaptive grid* first is a merely technical problem. However, when it comes to automatic grid adaptation things become more difficult as it is not a priori clear which variables should be considered for error estimation. Quite certainly, the radiation field or a few level populations alone will not do. It seems likely that the error estimation for automatic grid generation will have to be 'split' between the transfer and the rate equation part.

In most existing codes, the general idea for the *coupling between the transfer and the rate equation part* is to insert, in some sense, part of the discretized transport operator into the rate equation part. While this general idea is likely to carry over to TR3D it is less clear, due to the use of a generalized mean intensity approach, what exactly has to be inserted into the rate equations.

The question of boundary conditions actually has at least two aspects. First, other than vacuum boundary conditions will have to be formulated in physical terms. For the case where the domain boundary intersects a stellar atmosphere, for example, it has already been discussed earlier in this work that this is no straightforward task. Second, the implementation of the boundaries has to be improved. As demonstrated earlier, even for the case of vacuum boundaries the implementation of a spherical source causes problems right now.

Other improvements concern the solution of the rate equation part, a closer investigation of Sobolev theory when non-local effects are important and of the diffusion limit of the transfer equation, the improvement of boundary conditions for spherical sources, the implementation of a higher order discretization of the transfer equation, the design of another preconditioner for the transfer part, a higher order discretization of the transfer equation, and the parallelization of the code for shared memory machines.

Chapter 7

D3NEBEL: A 3D code for nebular conditions

Although it has been shown that TR3D can handle nebular conditions at least in principle, it is greatly exaggerated and unnecessary to use an optically thick, multidimensional, NLTE transfer code under such conditions. In this chapter a complementary, slimmer approach to multidimensional NLTE radiative transfer is presented which, however, is applicable under nebular conditions only.

The code D3NEBEL to be described below is based on the existing 1D code NEBEL of the astrophysics group at ETH Zürich. For a given 3D density and velocity distribution and for a given central source of radiation, D3NEBEL is capable of computing the temperature, the ionization structure, the emitted spectra, and line profiles due to different Doppler shifts at different spatial locations. The basic idea is to apply the existing 1D code to several rays which all originate from the same central source of radiation, and then to add up the contributions of all rays. The mutual interaction between these individual rays is neglected in this approach and in this sense the approach is not truly multidimensional. However, this objection is justified only partly. For physical reasons, it is usually possible under nebular conditions to just sum up the radiation emitted at different spatial points. Scattering processes, which would couple the individual rays, are mostly unimportant.

D3NEBEL had, in contrast to TR3D, not to be coded from scratch. The aim here was to obtain an applicable code within a short time. And unlike in TR3D, numerical questions were barely touched. What has been obtained in the end is a valuable tool which allows the computation of the emission of a nebular structure computed with 3D hydrodynamical simulations, which then can be compared with observational data.

7.1 Code description of D3NEBEL

Discretization and input data: The input data for D3NEBEL is given in several files and consists of atomic data, information on the central radiation source, and the density and velocity for each ray in 3D space as a function of radius. More accurately, the rays lie in 3D half space only, as at the moment symmetry is assumed with respect to the xy -plane. Their directions are given in terms of ϕ and θ , where $\phi \in [0, 2\pi)$ denotes longitude and $\theta \in [0, \pi/2]$ latitude. The rays are distributed equidistantly in ϕ - and θ -direction with separation $\Delta\phi$ and $\Delta\theta$ respectively. One set of rays lies in the equatorial plane $\theta = 0$, one ray points to the pole at $\theta = \pi/2$. As shown in Figure 7.1, each ray is assigned a solid angle $d\Omega$ with the ray in its center. The values of $d\Omega$ are given by

$$d\Omega = \begin{cases} \frac{1 - \cos\left(\frac{\Delta\theta}{2}\right)}{2} & \text{for } \theta = \pi/2 \\ \frac{\Delta\phi \cos\theta \sin\left(\frac{\Delta\theta}{2}\right)}{4\pi} & \text{for } \theta = 0 \\ \frac{\Delta\phi \cos\theta \sin\left(\frac{\Delta\theta}{2}\right)}{2\pi} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7.1)$$

Within each such solid angle the density and velocity are prescribed as a function of radius only, i.e. they are assumed to be constant as functions of angle within the solid angle element assigned to a particular ray. The values taken are those the density and velocity assume on the ray itself. The rays may have different length. For the computation along each ray the step size in radial direction is chosen adaptively.

For the computation of line profiles a number of observers can be introduced which, however, have to be located on one of the discrete rays.

There exist two discrete frequency arrays. One relatively coarse array is used to compute the radiation field in the rest frame of the present radius point. It should be noted, however, that this coarse array is still much finer than the frequency array used in TR3D. To store the entire computed spectrum including Doppler broadened line profiles, it is necessary to refine this coarse array in the vicinity of the line profiles for which Doppler shifted profiles are desired. As each observer sees a different Doppler shift, each observer has its own locally refined frequency array. The number, extent, and resolution of these high resolution regions can be chosen freely.

The computing process: The computation is carried out ray by ray. Figure 7.2 gives a very crude idea of how D3NEBEL works. The *computation along one ray* is done by the 1D NEBEL code. A description of NEBEL can be found in Nussbaumer and Schild [103], Vogel [152], and Schild [125]. D3NEBEL then

Figure 7.1: Ray and associated solid angle as used in the 3D adaptation *D3NEBEL* of the 1D code *NEBEL*.

Figure 7.2: Schematic representation of the code *D3NEBEL*.

collects the output of the 1D code at each radius point. It does some post-processing to it and then stores it appropriately. This post-processing includes the writing of some radius dependent output to disk, the correction of the computed emission for the correct emission measure, the computation of the correct Doppler shifts for each observer for the present radius point, and the sorting of the Doppler shifted spectrum into the refined frequency arrays of each observer.

After one ray has been computed its *spectrum is added to the spectrum of the previous rays*. If on the ray just computed there sits an observer, the stellar spectrum at the end of this ray is added to the total spectrum as well.

For *the case of double star systems* some additional peculiarities have to be observed. If a ray from the irradiating source intersects the companion star, this ray is followed only to that intersection point. Radius points further outward are not computed. On the other hand, an observer is assumed to 'see behind' the companion star in the sense that it is ignored that the companion star covers a small area of the field of view of an observer.

7.2 Capabilities and deficiencies of D3NEBEL

Capabilities: As mentioned at the beginning of this chapter, D3NEBEL is basically able to compute the temperature, the ionization structure, the emitted spectra, and line profiles due to different Doppler shifts at different spatial locations for a given 3D density and velocity structure. A remarkable amount of atomic data and processes is included. All Together, this makes it a valuable tool for the analysis of, for example, 3D hydrodynamical simulations of double star systems. A first example of such a model computation is shown in Figure 7.3. A more detailed presentation of the capabilities of D3NEBEL for the investigation of binary star systems is given in Chapter 8. If applicable, D3NEBEL is much faster and cheaper to use than its optically thick 'equivalent' TR3D.

Despite the possibilities D3NEBEL offers there are a few points where caution is advised. Some of them, like the 'seeing behind the companion star' have already been mentioned, a few other important points shall be discussed in the following.

Non-interacting 1D rays As far as *the three dimensional character* of D3NEBEL is concerned one may say that D3NEBEL is not 3D at all, as only 1D rays are computed and summed up while their mutual interaction is not considered. However, under nebular conditions this objection is justified only partly. For optically thin emission lines, where a once emitted photon undergoes no further interaction, proceeding as in D3NEBEL is fine. The same

applies for continuum emission at long enough wavelengths, certainly greater than the absorption edge of hydrogen at 912 Å. For physical reasons, 3D for these processes, in fact, does not mean anything more than summing up contributions from all 3D space. However, there are some points where the treatment by independent 1D rays leads to inconsistencies and where caution is advisable.

One of them concerns optically thick line transitions like, for example the hydrogen Lyman and Balmer lines. In principle, photons emitted in such lines could be reabsorbed elsewhere on the same ray or another, leading to mutual interaction between the rays. However, already the NEBEL code applied to a single ray does not take into account that a line photon emitted at radius r_i could be absorbed again at point r_{i+1} . Consequently, the computed strength and line profile of such transitions cannot be trusted. But other quantities are not contaminated by this error. The ground state populations of each ion, which in some sense are the only relevant quantities under nebular conditions, are still correct.

Possibly more important for the general outcome of the computation is the inconsistency related to optically thick continuum emission. The atomic emission of ionizing radiation below 912 Å is still assumed to occur spherically symmetric, which obviously leads to some inconsistency. Moreover, it is assumed to be optically thin with respect to all radius points lying further inwards (i.e. towards the central radiation source) than the point of emission. It seems impossible to improve this point substantially as long as the concept of ray by ray treatment is retained where each ray is treated individually and there is no interaction between the rays. However, again this problem is not too severe as long as the atomic emission at a particular wavelength below 912 Å contributes only a tiny fraction to the total radiation field at the same frequency. This condition is usually fulfilled as long as hydrogen is fully ionized. Otherwise, NEBEL runs into difficulties anyhow (see below).

Catching a prescribed matter distribution: To answer the question of *how well a 3D density and velocity distribution can be caught* by D3NEBEL three computations have been carried out for the same example, each of them with a different number of rays. The example is based on a 3D hydrodynamical simulation of a symbiotic double star system computed with the AMRCART code, briefly described in Section 10.2. The density and velocity distribution are shown in Figure 7.3 where also the corresponding model parameters are given. The radiation source is located at the position of the hot component in the system. It is assumed to be a black body of radius $R^* = 5.32 \cdot 10^9$ cm and temperature $T^* = 7.94 \cdot 10^4$ K. For the abundances the cosmical abundances by Allen [2] have been used. The three computations with D3NEBEL were run with the following numbers of rays in ϕ and θ direction: $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (16, 4)$ for run 1, $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (32, 8)$ for run 2, and $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (64, 16)$ for run 3.

In Figure 7.4 Doppler broadened line profiles for different lines for all three runs are shown. They are probably one of the most sensitive quantities. As to be expected, the computed line profiles depend on the number of rays which have been used. While the results for $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (32, 8)$ and for $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (64, 16)$ are already rather close together, the line profiles computed with $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (16, 4)$ clearly fall off. It has to be stressed, however, that also the wavelength resolution within the line can have considerable influence on the quality of the line profile.

In general, if the density distribution contains regions of high density which are small compared to the separation of neighbouring rays their contribution will be over- or underestimated, depending on whether a ray crosses such a region or not. As neighbouring rays separate more and more when going away from the central radiation source, the problem becomes more severe in more remote regions. Due to the particular choice of rays with its concentration of rays towards the poles the problem is probably also more severe in the equatorial plane than towards the poles. It seems very difficult to estimate in advance how many rays would be needed to achieve a prescribed accuracy. What can be done is to compare the results of two computations using different numbers of rays. However, if the two results agree within a prescribed tolerance this does not necessarily mean that they are within this tolerance with respect to the 'true' result. Some small scale, high density regions may have been missed both times.

Some deficiencies already present in NEBEL In the previous paragraph some points were mentioned where caution is advised and which are mostly specific to D3NEBEL. However, already within the 1D code NEBEL attention has to be paid to some pitfalls. Apart from those already mentioned in the previous paragraph (treatment of Balmer lines, continuum emission below 912 Å) there is at least one more point to be aware of. The NEBEL code is built on the assumption that hydrogen is nearly completely ionized. If this assumption is no longer fulfilled the code still runs but the ionization structure and temperature profiles it produces may no longer be trusted.

Figure 7.3: Density (logarithmic scaling) and velocity distribution of a symbiotic system, obtained from 3D hydrodynamical simulations. Shown are: cut normal to x -axis (top left), cut normal to y -axis (top right), cut normal to z -axis (bottom). Each cut goes roughly through the center of the system. The system parameters are (h =hot component, c = cold component): $M_h = 0.6 M_\odot$, $M_c = 1.4 M_\odot$, $v_h^{wind} = 1000 \text{ km/s}$, $v_c^{wind} = 20 \text{ km/s}$, $v_h^{orbit} = 20.9 \text{ km/s}$, $v_c^{orbit} = 8.93 \text{ km/s}$, $\dot{M}_h = 4 \cdot 10^{-9} M_\odot/\text{year}$, $\dot{M}_c = 3.142 \cdot 10^{-8} M_\odot/\text{year}$. Shown is the flux (in $\text{ergs/cm}^2 \text{ s } \text{\AA}$) against wavelength (in $\text{\AA}$).

Figure 7.4: *Computed line profiles for three runs with different numbers of rays. dotted: $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (16, 4)$ dashed: $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (32, 8)$ solid: $(n_\phi, n_\theta) = (64, 16)$. The lines belong to (from top left to bottom right, line by line) CIV, HeII, CIII, NeIII, H_γ , HEII, H_β , OIII, OIII. For details see text.*

Chapter 8

D3NEBEL as a tool for investigating binaries

An important, but often difficult, task in connection with the simulation of astrophysical objects is the comparison of the models with observational data. The present chapter is intended as an outline of the possibilities D3NEBEL offers as a link between simulations and observations, in particular for binary star systems. As most objects cannot be spatially resolved, the emphasis here lies on spectral data. Although existing 3D hydrodynamical simulations of symbiotic binary star systems are used as examples, the material presented in the following should not be regarded as a contribution to the investigation of symbiotic binaries.

D3NEBEL has been applied to three different, existing 3D hydrodynamical simulations of symbiotic systems using nine different sources of radiation in each model. The ionization structure of the models for different ions has been computed as well as line profiles which take into account Doppler shifts. The computed ionization structure considerably facilitates the interpretation of line profile variations. The results suggest that on the basis of line profile variations over one orbit at least the two most extreme hydrodynamical models should be distinguishable.

In Section 8.1, the three hydrodynamical models as well as the different radiation sources are presented. Some details on the computation of the spectra are given as well. Section 8.2 contains a summary of the computed spectra and ionization structures, along with an estimate of the quality of these results. Conclusions are given in Section 8.3.

8.1 Model examples and computation

The 3D hydrodynamical models: The three hydrodynamical models (*weak*, *med*, and *strong* in the following) have been obtained from R. Walder and are described in more detail in Walder [156]. The parameters of these three models were chosen such that the models represent three different 'mean symbiotic systems'. Figure 8.1 shows the density and velocity distribution in the orbital plane for all three models. The simulations have been done adiabatically, using the 3D version of the AMRCART code (see e.g. [154] or 10.2).

In all models, an orbital period of two years has been assumed, $1.4 M_{\odot}$ for the mass of the red giant (subscript c in the following) and $0.6 M_{\odot}$ for the mass of the white dwarf (subscript h in the following), 20 km/s (Mach 1.09) for the red giant wind and 1000 km/s (Mach 54.4) for the white dwarf wind. Assuming strong enough photoionization throughout the computational domain, the temperature of the gas is assumed to be at least 10^4 K. The three models differ in the mass-loss rates for which the following values have been adopted: $\dot{M}_c = 3.142 \times 10^{-7} M_{\odot}$, $\dot{M}_h = \times 10^{-9} M_{\odot}$ (model *weak*), $\dot{M}_c = 1 \times 10^{-7} M_{\odot}$, $\dot{M}_h = 2 \times 10^{-9} M_{\odot}$ (model *medium*), and $\dot{M}_c = 3.142 \times 10^{-8} M_{\odot}$, $\dot{M}_h = 4 \times 10^{-9} M_{\odot}$ (model *strong*), leading to momentum ratios Π_h/Π_c of 0.16 (model *weak*), 1 (model *medium*), and 6.28 (model *strong*) respectively. These parameters were chosen to represent some average symbiotic systems rather than any particular system. The computational domain has an extension of 10^{15} cm in each direction. In units of 10^{15} cm, the center of mass of the binary star system is located at $(x,y,z)=(0.5, 0.5, 0.3)$.

The different sources of radiation: To each of the three hydrodynamical models nine different central stars are applied. The stars are assumed to radiate like black bodies. Their temperatures and luminosities are fixed to 60000 K, 90000 K, and 120000 K, and $100 L_{\odot}$, $1000 L_{\odot}$, and $10000 L_{\odot}$. Their radii are chosen accordingly.

Computation of spectra: The spectra were computed with the D3NEBEL code, which has been described in Chapter 7. The code makes use of an ensemble of 1D rays emerging from the radiation source to compute the emitted spectrum of a given 3D density and velocity distribution. The density and velocity distribution along the individual rays was interpolated from the 3D hydrodynamical data. With regard to the present application it seems worthwhile to emphasize again two aspects of the code. First, along rays pointing from the radiation source (here the hot white dwarf) through the companion star (the red giant) the computation is stopped once the companion star (i.e. its boundary in the hydrodynamical simulation) is reached. There is no irradiation of the matter lying 'behind' the companion star. Second, the shielding

Figure 8.1: *Density (logarithmic contours) and velocity distribution of the three symbiotic models used as examples in this chapter. Shown are cuts through the orbital plane. The models are: strong (top left), medium (top right), and weak (bottom).*

of part of the emission region by the companion star, as seen by a distant observer, is neglected. An observer 'sees behind' the red giant.

In order to fit the computational domain of the hydrodynamical simulations, the maximum length of each ray was set to $4.65 \cdot 10^{14}$ cm. The computation was terminated at this distance, or even earlier if no more ionizing photons were present. Therefore, not all the computed rays really extended to $4.65 \cdot 10^{14}$ cm. It should be stressed already here that for certain models and ions this computational domain is much too small, reflecting only the innermost, possibly insignificant, part of the system.

The abundances (by number) relative to hydrogen have been set to 0.1 for helium and, omitting a factor 10^{-4} , to 2.4 (C), 3.0 (N), 7.5 (O), 0.741 (Ne), 0.257 (Mg), 0.302 (Si), 0.186 (S), 0.0355 (Ar), 0.061 (Fe).

8.2 Ionization regions, profile variations, and line fluxes

In the following, a summary of the 27 computed models (three hydrodynamical models times nine different radiation sources) is going to be given. A first part focuses on the ionization regions, then some line profile variations are presented. Next, model line flux ratios are compared to some observed line flux ratios, illustrating a possible, relatively simple, plausibility test for the models. Finally, the quality of the simulations is discussed.

The knowledge obtained in this way on the connection between different models, ionization regions, and line profile variations may be used to deduce possible (but usually not unique) ionization and matter distributions from given line profile variations. For the test models under consideration, it seems, for example, possible to distinguish at least between model *weak* and model *strong* on the basis of line profile variations.

Extension of ionized regions

Although not directly observable, the analysis of the computed shape and extension of different ionization regions is of great importance. First, the extension of the ionization region gives a rough estimate of whether the model line fluxes of an ion can be trusted or not. If an ion is hardly present in the entire computational domain the corresponding line fluxes may be doubted. Second, in order that a certain line may be used to probe the characteristic matter distribution of a region, in the present examples in particular the interaction region of the two winds, the corresponding ion has to dominate in that region. Third, if a certain ion is indeed present in the right place, the knowledge of the

exact shape and location of the ionization zone helps to interpret the modeled line profiles.

OIII as an example: Consider the distribution of the OIII ion in the orbital plane. Figure 8.2 shows the portion of the OIII ion with respect to the total amount of oxygen for four different situations: model *weak* and model *strong* with a central star of $L = 100 L_{\odot}$ and $T = 90000$ K, model *weak* with a central star of $L = 1000 L_{\odot}$ and $T = 90000$ K, and model *strong* with a central star of $L = 100 L_{\odot}$ and $T = 60000$ K. Obviously, the temperature and luminosity of the central star, as well as the hydrodynamical model have a strong influence on the distribution of OIII in the orbital plane. Here it should be remembered, however, that, as far as the dependence on the hydrodynamical model is concerned, these models differ not only in the shape of their interaction zones but also in the density of their winds. In all four models shown in Figure 8.2 OIII is dominantly present along several rays. The line fluxes, therefore, may basically be trusted. More remote regions outside the computational domain may also contribute but due to the lower density only marginally. However, for high temperatures or luminosities (or both together) compared to the density, the occurrence of OIII is restricted to rays lying close to the red giant (see Figure 8.2 top right and bottom left). Hence, here most of the OIII emission comes from the undisturbed red giant wind and does not contain any information about the matter distribution in the interaction zone of the two winds.

For low enough temperatures and luminosities compared to the density, the OIII region covers wide parts of the colliding winds interaction zone (see Figure 8.2 top left and bottom right). In these cases, the OIII lines indeed contain information about the matter distribution in the interaction zone, although not exclusively. Comparison between the top left picture in Figure 8.2 and the picture at the bottom right in Figure 8.2 shows a different extension of the OIII region towards the red giant in these two cases, which has to be taken into account when interpreting the corresponding profile variations.

Although not shown in Figure 8.2, which is restricted to the orbital plane, the colliding winds interaction zone in the models under investigation dominates the ionization region also in full 3D space.

The same statements as just made for the case of OIII apply to other ions as well. However, for a given hydrodynamical model, the temperature and luminosity range of the central radiation source where the occurrence of an ion covers the colliding winds interaction zone will differ from ion to ion. This different 'sensitivity' of different ions can be used to find an appropriate ion for a given temperature, luminosity, and hydrodynamical model. While, for example, OIII in Figure 8.2 probes the interacting winds region quite well for model *strong* with a central star with $L=100 L_{\odot}$ and $T = 60000$ K it fails if for the same model the temperature of the central star is raised to 90000 K.

Figure 8.2: Abundance of the OIII ion relative to the total oxygen abundance, shown in the orbital plane for four different models. **top left:** $L=100 L_{\odot}$, $T=90000$ K, weak, **top right:** $L=100 L_{\odot}$, $T=90000$ K, strong, **bottom left:** $L=1000 L_{\odot}$, $T=90000$ K, weak, **bottom right:** $L=100 L_{\odot}$, $T=60000$ K, strong. The x - and y -axis are given in units of 10^{14} cm, the abundance is plotted along the computed rays. The regions without any rays correspond to the 'shade' of the red giant star.

In this latter case, NV or NeV would be suited to probe the interacting winds region instead.

Line profile variations

For most binary star systems, and in particular for symbiotic systems, there are usually no images resolving the system. Here line profile variations possibly provide the closest link between hydrodynamical models and observations. Ideally, one would like to be able to distinguish between different models, or even to deduce the matter distribution in the system, on the basis of observed line profile variations. In the following, the question shall be addressed whether it is possible to distinguish between the two hydrodynamical models *weak* and *strong* on the basis of line profile variations. In fact, it turns out that given the right line, its profile variation indeed can be used to distinguish at least between model *strong* and model *weak*.

Phases are given with respect to an observer located at the top of the page in Figure 8.1. This observer sees the hot component (white dwarf) lying between him and the cold component (red giant), corresponding to phase 0.5. The phase increases as the hot component wanders further along its orbit.

Which line to probe the model? As has been seen in the previous paragraph, only some ions are suited at all to probe the matter distribution in a particular system. Which ion is suited depends on the temperature and luminosity of the radiation source as well as on the density in the interaction zone. In fact, the profile variation itself indicates whether the line variation reflects at least part of the interaction zone.

Figure 8.3 illustrates the influence of different luminosities of the central star on the line profile variations of OIII at 5008 Å. The hydrodynamical model was model *weak*. The central star had a temperature of $T = 90000$ K, and three different luminosities, $L = 100 L_{\odot}$, $L = 1000 L_{\odot}$, and $L = 10000 L_{\odot}$, were assumed. While between phase 0.5 and phase 0 the line profile in the case $L = 100 L_{\odot}$ shows a clear red shift, the line profile for $L = 10000 L_{\odot}$ shows a clear blue shift.

The latter case, this is the blue shift between phase 0.5 and phase 0, is typical for high luminosity and temperature compared to the density, where the occurrence of OIII and the corresponding emission are restricted to rays passing near the red giant, which leads to a maximum blue shift close to phase 0. The line profile variation does not contain any information on the colliding winds interaction region. For increasing temperature and luminosity the line profile variation of any ion will follow this pattern, before the ionization stage finally vanishes.

In the former case ($L = 100 L_{\odot}$), comparison of Figure 8.2 and Figure 8.1 shows that OIII is present in wide parts of the colliding winds interaction zone. The strong red shift in the profile variation between phase 0.5 and phase 0 is possible only if the profile variation is dominated by the density distribution in the colliding winds interaction zone, which at phase 0.5 is located between the radiation source and the observer.

Keeping the temperature and luminosity of the central star constant but changing the hydrodynamical model produces a similar change in the line profile variation. Figure 8.4 shows line profiles of OIII at 5008 Å for the three hydrodynamical models. The central star has $L = 100 L_{\odot}$ and $T = 90000$ K. Model *strong*, which has the lowest density of the red giant wind, shows again an increasing blue shift between phase 0.5 and phase 0. At the same time, model *weak* shows an increasing red shift.

In summary, an increasing blue shift between phase 0.5 and phase 0 reaching its maximum close to phase 0 indicates that the line stems from the vicinity of the red giant. The radiation source is too hot or too luminous for the given density and the line is not suited to probe the interaction zone. An increasing red shift between phase 0.5 and 0 indicates that the line stems from a region between the radiation source and the observer and contains some information about the interaction zone. However, the line may mirror only part of the interaction zone in which case additional lines have to be investigated as well. This question is addressed again in the next paragraph.

Figure 8.3: Line profile variation as observed in the orbital plane for the OIII line at 5008 Å for model *weak* with a radiation sources of $T = 90000$ K and different luminosities. From left to right: $L = 100 L_{\odot}$, $L = 1000 L_{\odot}$, $L = 10000 L_{\odot}$. From bottom to top: increasing phase starting at $p = 0.25$, with $\Delta p = 0.125$. While for $L = 100 L_{\odot}$ the profile variation stems from the interaction zone it merely reflects the undisturbed red giant wind for $L = 10000 L_{\odot}$. For details see text.

Figure 8.4: Line profile variation as observed in the orbital plane for the OIII line at $5008 \text{ \AA}$ and a radiation source with $L = 100 L_{\odot}$ and $T = 90000 \text{ K}$. From left to right: model weak, med, and strong. From bottom to top: increasing phase starting at $p = 0.25$, with $\Delta p = 0.125$. While for model weak the profile variation stems from the interaction zone it merely reflects the undisturbed red giant wind for model strong. For details see text.

Different hydrodynamical models, different profile variations? Having seen that the profile variation itself contains information about whether a line is suited to probe the colliding winds interaction region of the three hydrodynamical models, now the question shall be considered whether it is possible to distinguish between the models *weak* and *strong* on the basis of line profile variations. In fact, this is a comparatively easy task. First, one has to distinguish between only three known density distributions and, second, one can make use of profile variations over an entire orbit of several different lines.

Taking, as an example setting, a central star of $L = 100 L_{\odot}$ and $T = 60000 \text{ K}$, the ionization region of OIII is suited for both, model *strong* and model *weak*. The variations of the OIII line at $5008 \text{ \AA}$ are shown in Figure 8.6. And indeed, the variations show a slight difference between model *strong* and model *weak*. The maximum blue shift in model *strong* is reached later in the orbit (around phase 0.75) than in model *weak* (between phase 0.5 and 0.625).

From this one might be tempted to conclude that observing a maximum blue shift around phase 0.75 is characteristic of model *strong*. However, as can be taken from Figure 8.3, model *weak* also shows a maximum blue shift at 0.75 for $L = 1000 L_{\odot}$, $T = 90000 \text{ K}$.

On the other hand, observing a maximum blue shift at phase 0.5 seems indeed to be characteristic for model *weak*. Figure 8.1 shows that the high density region consisting of red giant wind material in model *strong* extends

Figure 8.5: Probing the colliding winds interaction zone. The right ion makes it possible. From left to right: $L=100 L_{\odot}$, $L=1000 L_{\odot}$, $L=10000 L_{\odot}$ for model weak and $T = 90000 K$. The lines are 5008 OIII, 1242 NV, and 1031 OVI.

roughly from phase 0.5 to phase 1.0. It is this material which, if correctly ionized, contributes most to the computed emission lines. The fast material from the hot white dwarf is too tenuous for this purpose. To produce a maximum blue shift at phase 0.5 with this matter distribution the ionization region would have to be restricted to a very narrow region around the direction given by phase 0.5. This seems highly unlikely as the maximum blue shift for this matter distribution is rather to be expected at a later phase.

To make sure one sees either a profile variation of model *strong* or model *weak* it is necessary to look at the profile variations of several different lines of different ionization stages. If in some of these line variations the maximum blue shift is found to occur around phase 0.5, like in Figure 8.5, one observes model *weak*. If in none of the profile variations, not even for the lowest ionization stages, it occurs at phase 0.5 this is an indication although not a proof for model *strong*.

Line ratios from models and observations

Several different line ratios have been computed for the 27 different models considered in this chapter. They are not suited to distinguish between different hydrodynamical models, as can be seen from Figure 8.8. However, they provide a valuable test of the plausibility of the presented models. For the examples under consideration a comparison between model line ratios and observed line ratios is shown in Figure 8.7. The observational data has been kindly gathered from the literature by Hans Martin Schmid and is listed in Table 8.1.

Ratios where either NIII or CIII is involved show strong deviations from

Figure 8.6: *If the correct ion is considered, the phase at which the maximum blue shift of the line profile is reached allows to distinguish between model strong and model weak. Shown are model weak (left) and model strong (right) for a radiation source with $L = 100 L_{\odot}$ and $T = 60000$ K. The maximum blue shift for model weak occurs around phase 0.5, for model strong it occurs around phase 0.75.*

observations for some models, whereas higher ionization states of the same elements fit the observational data. It turns out that all models which fit the observations only poorly in these line ratios are high luminosity models, with $L \geq 1000 L_{\odot}$. For these ions and such high luminosities the computational domain is too small, in particular towards the red giant star. In these models, nearly all of the flux in NIII and CIII is emitted right on the surface of the red giant. However, the computational domain in this direction ends even before NIII and CIII become the dominant ions of their chemical species.

Quality of the simulation

Here only some technical aspects shall be considered. Physical questions, like which abundances to take, are not touched. The following points are basically a concrete illustration of the general deficiencies of D3NEBEL already discussed in Section 7.2.

The too small NIII and CIII line fluxes as just discussed are due to the too small computational domain, in particular towards the red giant. This is, however, an isolated problem in the sense that it affects only certain ions.

Another point already mentioned is the fact that in the presented models an observer can 'see behind' the red giant. For lines which originate mainly close to the surface of the red giant, on the side facing the hot white dwarf this definitely causes wrong results. Up to now there is no quantitative analysis of

Figure 8.7: Model line ratios (boxes) for 26 models compared to observed line ratios (crosses) of 15 symbiotic systems. Model strong with $L = 10000 L_{\odot}$ and $T = 120000 K$ has been omitted as it lies even much further off the observational data.

Figure 8.8: Line ratios for the three different hydrodynamical models weak, strong, and med (boxes) for a central star with $L = 100 L_{\odot}$ and $T = 90000$ K. Crosses denote observed line ratios. For all lines under consideration, the different hydrodynamical models produce very similar line ratios which, therefore, are not well suited for a distinction between different hydrodynamical models.

Obj.	NV	NIV	CIV	HeII	OIII	NIII	CIII	$E_{(B-V)}$	Ref.
1	2.0	0.91	51.0	8.2	1.41	0.46	11.5	0.3	129
2	2.8	0.80	9.4	5.3	0.75	0.54	2.05	0.34	104
3	11.0	3.3	38.1	18.8	5.9	1.6	1.9	0.45	115
4	4.1	3.4	15.9	9.0	1.6	2.0	6.5	0.60	107
5	126.	53.5	546.	204.	56.	20.5	116.	0.09	50
6	312.	111.	385.	218.	67.	18.1	21.3	0.10	71
7	9.5	2.4	9.0	20.4	1.7	1.6	0.3	0.05	100
8	1.7	1.5	18.4	7.8	2.7	1.1	3.6	0.03	38
9	1.08	1.84	6.58	1.35	8.75	7.63	12.14	0.35	47
10	0.5	7.00	56.	1.64	11.62	2.69	6.11	0.05	139
11	18.8	48.8	432.9	28.2	49.1	7.8	6.0	0.05	70
12	2.1	7.6	29.1	3.6	8.6	2.2	3.8	0.15	28
13	1.1	2.6	13.2	3.1	4.3	2.3	6.3	0.27	99
14	4.88	2.74	13.59	15.42	1.50	1.52	1.90	0.35	39
15	49.3	18.5	131.	62.1	17.1	8.9	53.3	0.36	126

Table 8.1: Observed UV line fluxes for 15 symbiotic system, kindly gathered from the literature by Hans Martin Schmid. The fluxes are given in units of 10^{-12} erg. References to the observations are given in the last column. The objects, numbered in the first column, are: AS 210 (1), HBV 475 (2), SY Mus (3), HM Sge (4), RR Tel (5), AG Peg (6), AG Dra (7), Hen1242 (8), BF Cyg (9), EG And (10), RW Hya (11), V443 Her (12), AX Per (13), Z And (14), V1016 Cyg (15).

this feature. As far as line profiles are concerned, the geometrical constellation suggests that they should be influenced by this feature only at red shifts of around 20 km/s, the velocity of the red giant wind.

As there are no very filamentary, high density structures in the considered hydrodynamical models the main effect of the increased spatial resolution in this example is noise reduction. For one model, Figure 8.9 illustrates changes in the line profile variation due to a better spatial discretization of $(n_\theta, n_\phi) = (16, 64)$ instead of $(n_\theta, n_\phi) = (8, 32)$ for the case of NeV at 3426 Å.

Finally, the diffuse radiation field is negligible compared to the stellar radiation field, and so are the problems related to the diffuse radiation field as described in Section 7.2.

Figure 8.9: Computed line profile variation for Ne V at 3426 Å for $(n_\theta, n_\phi) = (8, 32)$ (left) and $(n_\theta, n_\phi) = (16, 64)$ (right). For the models under consideration increased spatial resolution merely reduces the noise.

8.3 Discussion and Conclusions

For a given density and velocity distribution D3NEBEL provides information about ionization structures and line profile variations. In the frame of the different hydrodynamical models considered, line profile variations as observed in the orbital plane over one orbit allow a distinction between model *weak* and model *strong*. Looking at different ionization regions reveals that only some ions and their corresponding lines are suited for such a distinction between different models. Which ion is suited depends mainly on the temperature and

luminosity of the central star and on the density of the red giant wind in the hydrodynamical model. The line profile variation itself gives a hint on whether the corresponding ion is suited or not. Apart from providing a link to observational data these results contribute to a better understanding of the hydrodynamical models themselves.

However, thinking of comparison with observational data several problems come to mind. Coming from observations one usually will not have that much data at disposal. It has been shown that, for a given model system, many line profiles merely mirror the undisturbed red giant wind. From an observational point of view this means that either one has to observe several different lines or one has to find out in advance which lines might be best suited for a particular system. If the system parameters are known well enough numerical models may provide some insight into the latter question. Next, although only two very simple hydrodynamical models have been considered and lots of line profile variations were available, their distinction already posed difficulties. Also, while some real systems may essentially be the same as these model systems, one generally expects a much greater variety of physical processes to take place: Radiative cooling, heat conduction, magnetic fields, accretion. How such processes influence the velocity and density distribution of a system, and therefore the emitted line profiles, has yet to be investigated. Starting from an observed profile variation it seems, however, likely that one has several possible models for selection, all of them fitting the observed profile variation. Also, the presented models are restricted to the innermost part of the system while the observational data covers the entire system.

Part III

Radiative colliding flows

Chapter 9

Introduction

This chapter is intended as an introduction to the topic of radiative colliding flows. Our own research on this topic, to be presented in Chapter 10 and 11, is built mainly on numerical simulations. Here, in contrast, a survey shall be given of the most important analytical results in the field. Most of this introduction has been taken from Walder & Folini [158].

9.1 Why studying radiative colliding flows?

Colliding hypersonic flows and associated strong radiative shocks are a common, however not well understood phenomenon in astrophysics. Such shocks appear, for example, in wind driven structures like Planetary Nebulae or superwind bubbles around star burst regions, in the atmospheres of hot stars, in binary systems, in active galactic nuclei, and in the interstellar medium. Nowadays, more and more interest is being paid to the stability properties of radiative shocks. It has become clear that the formation of planetary knots, flyers, filaments, pillars and even stars and galaxies can be triggered by the combination of (magneto-)hydrodynamical instabilities and radiative cooling. On the other hand, the turbulence excited by some of the instabilities can contribute to the explanation of observed peculiarities of optical and UV-line profiles and of the production rate and spectral distribution of X-rays and radio emission.

9.2 Basic physics of some instabilities in radiative shocks

Whenever two stationary flows collide hypersonically, the interaction zone obeys some basic pattern. In the **adiabatic case** (Figure 9.1a), the zone

Figure 9.1: Schematic structure of the collision zone of adiabatic (left) and radiative (right) colliding hypersonic flows. All velocities are given in the rest frame of the interaction zone.

is confined by two shocks S_1, S_2 . A contact discontinuity C forms where the two media actually meet. *In planar geometry*, the mathematicians call this constellation a Riemann-problem. For astronomers, when identifying flow 2 with the ISM, it may be a 1D model for the propagation of a jet. *In spherical geometry*, the constellation is a model for wind-driven structures. The wind from the central star may be identified with flow 1, the ISM with flow 2. Here the shocks are curved, which, however, does not affect the stability as long as the curvature is small. *In binaries*, where the two winds interact between the two stars, a transverse flow in the interaction zone is maintained. In all three cases, the pattern is stable as long as it is not accelerated.

If **radiative cooling** is applied, one still observes a basic, however different pattern (Figure 9.1b). Already cooled gas is collected in a layer of cold, dense gas (CDL) near the contact interface. This layer – cold and without any bulk momentum – is squeezed between the two hypersonic flows. Two extreme cases can be distinguished: the *symmetric case*, where both shocked flows cool approximately on the same time-scale, and the *asymmetric case*, where the cooling scales of two flows are highly different. In the former case, the CDL is squeezed by the ram-pressures of the flows, while in the later case the CDL is squeezed by ram pressure from one side and by thermal pressure from the other side. In both cases, the CDL may be subject to thin shell instabilities of several types. The cooling layers L_i themselves may be affected by a strong, oscillatory instability.

Classical hydrodynamical instabilities

A description of the classical hydrodynamical instabilities – Kelvin-Helmholtz, Rayleigh-Taylor, Richtmyer-Meskov (Richtmyer [117], Meskov [94]) – can be found in many standard textbooks like Landau & Lifschitz [84] or Chandrasekhar [124]. Many new results of the non-linear evolution can be found in *Physical Review Letters* and *Physics of Fluids*, as well as in the proceedings of workshops of compressible turbulent mixing (e.g. [64]).

The thermal cooling instability

Figure 9.2: Left: Typical parameterized radiative loss function $\Lambda(T)$ with different stability regions. Right: Cooling overstability shown in the size of the cooling layer. Mode-transition of the catastrophic first overtone mode to the catastrophic fundamental mode (Figures from Walder & Folini [196]).

Consider now the stability of the cooling layers L_i downstream of the shocks, which contribute to thermal X-ray emission. Radiative energy loss of an ideal gas can be treated by a term $\dot{\epsilon} = -N^2\Lambda(T)$ (N : number density; $\Lambda(T)$: radiative loss function, left panel of Figure 9.2). A typical cooling time τ of the plasma is then $\tau \propto T^{1-\beta}/N$ where β is the slope of the function $\Lambda(T)$ on a log-log scale. If β is small enough, any slight reduction of the post-shock temperature leads to even faster (local) cooling and vice-versa, resulting in an overstability: the cooling layer and its characteristic parameters, like post-shock temperature and X-ray emission, begin to oscillate in several different modes (Figure 9.2b). Linear stability analysis yields an upper limit of $\beta < 0.8$ (Chevalier and Imamura [19]). For $\beta \lesssim 0$, the overstability is of the catastrophic type; the post-shock gas eventually completely cools to pre-shock temperatures on a very short time-scale. Compressed by the ram-pressure, the cooling layer collapses completely. Then, it will be reconstructed. In its catastrophic form, the cooling overstability introduces strong pressure waves or even shocks in the CDL (see Walder and Folini [157] for a survey).

It should be noted that more complex two-temperature models, performed by Wolff et al. [162], including also heat conduction, give the same qualitative results. Multidimensional analysis of the overstability (Bertschinger [12], Strickland and Blondin [143]) reveals weak transverse effects.

Thin shell instabilities

The layer of already cooled, dense gas (CDL in the right panel of Figure 9.1) contributes most to the emission in optical and UV. For example, in PNe the visible nebula mainly coincides with this layer. The fact that the CDL is squeezed between the two flows, leads to new, interesting effects known as *thin*

Figure 9.3: *Left: Nonlinear thin shell instability (NTSI) of an isothermal, shock-bound slab. Right: Overstability of a decelerating (DI) thin shell bound by a shock and by isotropic pressure. For details see text.*

shell instabilities. In this Section, an idealized situation is looked at where the dynamics of the CDL are isolated and not coupled with other layers shown in Figure 9.1. It seems worth mentioning that also classical instabilities like KH or RT are modified if the size of their spatial growth scale is comparable to the thickness of the thin shell.

Nonlinear thin shell instability (NTSI)

For the beginning, the presence of the cooling layers L_i is neglected and an isothermal, shock-bound slab is considered instead, as shown in the left panel of Figure 9.3. Vishniac [151] has extensively discussed an analytical model of a completely symmetric situation. In the frame of his model, he has shown that non-accelerated, shock-bound slabs are linearly stable but, due to non-linear effects, unstable to disturbances of the size of the slab thickness. As indicated in Figure 9.3, left, momentum is transported within the rippled slab from its trailing to its leading edges, leading to unbalanced momenta in the leading edges. Counteracting forces which linearly stabilize the flow are: the ram pressure on the growing edges of the slab is larger and, more important, the postshock flow tends to converge on convex surfaces, filling in this way the ripples with freshly accreted material.

Using numerical simulations, these analytical results have been qualitatively confirmed by Blondin and Marks [14]. In addition, they find that the ripples finally are indeed filled up and that eventually turbulence within the slab leads to a much smaller average density than at the beginning.

Recently, we performed simulations which include the cooling layers. Here the flow is now *be collimated within the cooling layers* into the trailing edges of the rippled CDL, leading to a significantly enhanced growth rate of the instability.

For spherically symmetric situations and high Mach number flows the excited modes do not decay, the ripples are filled in less, and the growth of the turbulence is suppressed (Walder [154], Garcia et al. [45]).

Decelerating thin shell instability (DI)

Consider now a thin shell of cold, dense gas (CDL) which is driven against the interstellar medium by the isotropic thermal pressure of an either hot or cold interior gas (Figure 9.3, right). A decelerating expansion of such a nebula (CDL) will be oscillatory unstable due to the unequal nature of the isotropic driving pressure and the directed ram-pressure of the ISM. Assuming a rippled, isothermal shock, the Rankine-Hugoniot conditions imply a net flux of mass from the leading peaks to the trailing valleys of the thin shell. Mass is collected in the valleys (black dots in Figure 9.3b). These regions of enhanced density are now less decelerated by the ram-pressure of the ISM than the rarefied regions (white dots) and the lagging valleys become leading peaks.

Vishniac [150] gave a first description and linear stability analysis. Further details are given by Bertschinger [12] and Ryu and Vishniac [121]. Interestingly, Grun et al. [48] successfully prepared such systems in the laboratory (laser-facility). They confirmed the linear analysis and gave bounds for the saturation of the instability due to non-linear effects. MacLow and Norman [88] performed 2D numerical simulations and showed that the saturation is mainly due to the appearance of weak transverse shocks. The numerical results fit fairly well with those of the experiments. By including non-linear terms Vishniac [151] further elucidated the situation. Stationary slabs bound on one side by a shock and on the other by isotropic gas are stable, slabs which are accelerating in the direction of the shock are RT unstable (Vishniac [151]). As will be discussed later on, these results may considerably change when the shock is treated radiatively rather than isothermally.

Global instability of infinitely thin shells

Dgani et al. [26] pointed to a global instability to explain the instabilities observed in numerical simulations of colliding winds in binaries by Stevens et al. [141]. They looked at a pure advection model of the highly supersonic wind-wind interaction in binaries, neglecting any pressure effects. The interaction zone then collapses into an infinitely thin sheet. Material and momentum from the colliding flows enter the sheet, accelerating the material already present in the sheet. In this sense, the instability is governed by non-local or global effects. A linear analysis reveals two unstable modes: a breathing and a bending mode. Breathing modes depend on the accretion of matter, are an instability within the sheet, and have basically the same physical reason as a traffic jam. Bending modes depend on the accretion of momentum and lead to a displacement of the sheet. Dgani et al. [24] have extended this model to bow-shocks and found that strongly curved sheets couple the two modes by the effect of centrifugal acceleration.

Chapter 10

Unstable behaviour: One dimensional results

The material presented in this chapter has been published already by Walder and Folini [157]. In order to adapt the layout of the paper to that of the thesis, some minor changes had to be made to a few tables and figures. The text itself, however, is unaltered. Consequently, a few points discussed in the previous chapter will be briefly touched again.

Radiative shocks

Shock waves become radiative if the dynamical time of the flow exceeds the cooling time of the shocked matter. Radiative shocks are present in a variety of astrophysical objects: e.g. in supernova remnants, in colliding winds of binary star systems, in accretion processes, in all wind driven structures, in young stellar objects, in galactic and extragalactic jets, in star burst galaxies, in active galactic nuclei. Usually, such shocks are sufficiently strong to substantially ionize and heat the matter. As the heated matter cools, it is compressed into thin dense layers. The radiative cooling itself and the presence of a dense layer of cooled gas greatly influence the emitted spectrum. Radiative cooling of shock heated matter leads to emission mostly in the frequency range between X-ray and UV. The cold layer emits mostly in the radio, IR, optical, and UV. Therefore, a better understanding of radiative shock waves is crucial for the interpretation of the observed spectra.

Of similar significance is the influence of radiative shock waves on the dynamical shaping of their environment. The cold layer is much denser than the surrounding matter and often prey to instabilities of various types. In addition,

the neighboring shock heated zones are often subject to thermal instabilities. Such effects can be crucial for the distribution and the state of the matter in the vicinity of radiative shocks.

In this chapter, we study the thermal instability of radiative shock waves in the context of colliding flows. Radiative cooling is included as $\dot{\epsilon} = N^2 \Lambda(T)$, where $\Lambda(T)$ is piecewise linear on a log-log scale. The necessary spatial resolution to resolve all the relevant length and time scales is provided by an adaptive mesh refinement algorithm. In contrast to previous investigations, we follow the long term evolution of the entire interaction zone. In the case of a decelerating interaction zone this leads to an automatic scanning of wide ranges of the steady state shock velocity. This enables us to make a systematic study of the cooling instability. It also allows us to investigate the mutual influence of the cooling layer and the cold dense layer. In agreement with other authors, we find that for smooth flows the system is overstable: the instability is oscillatory and two different modes are important. The phenomenology of the overstability, however, may be very different within one mode which leads us to the introduction of phenomenological types. In the case of density disturbances upstream of the interaction zone, a temporarily aperiodic evolution can result for which we give constraints. Finally, we emphasize the importance of the cold dense layer for the thermal instability of the cooling layer.

The thermal cooling instability

Catastrophic cooling and the overstability of radiative shock waves due to thermal instability of radiative cooling have been known for several decades. First numerical investigations of catastrophic cooling in shock heated plasmas were carried out by Falle [35], [36]. First numerical investigations of the overstability of radiative shock waves were made by Langer et al. [81], [82] for the case of accretion flows onto compact objects.

Chevalier and Imamura [19] (CI in the remainder of this chapter) performed a linear stability analysis for a planar flow against a wall as a model for accretion flows. They applied a cooling law of the form $\dot{\epsilon} = N^2 T^\beta$, and found the cooling layer between the accretion shock and the wall to be thermally unstable for $\beta < \beta_c$. An infinite number of modes with successively higher eigenfrequencies were found, among them a fundamental and a first overtone mode, for which $\beta_c \lesssim 0.4$ and 0.8 respectively. Numerical simulations carried out by Imamura et al. [60] were in agreement with these results. Wolff et al. [162] and Imamura and Wolff [59] extended these investigations to two-temperature models with heat conduction and different cooling processes such as Compton cooling and relativistic Bremsstrahlung. They still found the same modes of the overstable oscillation of the radiative accretion shock.

In a beautiful analytical paper, Bertschinger [12] extended the analysis to

interstellar shocks. He showed that under certain conditions there exists a piecewise self-similar solution in spherical symmetry. The flow pattern is more complex than for accretion flows: a leading shock, a cooling layer behind the shock, a hot or cold interior, and a thin layer of already cooled, compressed gas between the interior and the cooling layer. Performing a linear stability analysis on this solution that allowed for disturbances in all three spatial directions, he found two types of instabilities, a thermal and a dynamical one. For the thermal one he found the same unstable modes in the radial direction as Chevalier and Imamura [19]. Surprisingly, he found that no new modes are introduced by nonradial disturbances. But modes stable to radial perturbations can be unstable to nonradial perturbations.

On the numerical side, significant progress has been made by including detailed radiation processes into the analysis. Innes et al. [62] (IGF in the remainder of this chapter) and Gaetz et al. [44] (GEC in the remainder of this chapter) considered ionization and recombination processes as well as time-dependent non-equilibrium cooling. They agreed on the onset of the instability for shocks having velocities above 130 km/s – 150 km/s. GEC found this instability to be oscillatory which is in agreement with further investigations presented by Innes [61].

Recently, Plewa [116] studied strong shock waves ($v_S > 1000$ km/s) running into dense material and found overstable behavior also under these conditions.

In spherical symmetry, stability analyses of radiative shocks were performed by Imamura and Wolff [59], Houck and Chevalier [52], and Dgani et al. [25]. Spherically symmetric cooling shells have significantly different stability properties as long as their size is comparable to the relevant radius. For small cooling shells, the stability behavior approaches the planar limit behavior. Attempts to analyze the thermal cooling instability of two-dimensional planar shocks have been made by Strickland and Blondin [143].

The organization of the article is as follows: In Section 10.1 we briefly describe our physical model. In Section 10.2, this is followed by some notes on the applied numerical methods. In Section 10.3 the basic flow patterns are described and the sample of computations is presented. The thermal cooling instability for the case of smooth flows is analyzed in Section 10.4, and in Section 10.5 the same is done for the case of disturbed flows. The evolution of the cold dense layer is investigated in Section 10.6. In Section 10.7 we discuss our results, and, finally, we present the conclusions in Section 10.8.

10.1 The physical model

The governing equations

Our physical model is based on the Euler equations and the use of parameterized radiative loss functions (RLFs in the following). We numerically solve the Euler equations in spherical symmetry:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho v_r}{\partial r} = -\frac{2v_r}{r} \rho, \quad (10.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\rho v_r)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\rho v_r^2 + p)}{\partial r} = -\frac{2v_r}{r} \rho v_r, \quad (10.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial [v_r (E + p)]}{\partial r} = -\frac{2v_r}{r} (E + p) - \dot{\epsilon}(T, N) + q(T). \quad (10.3)$$

Here, ρ denotes the mass density, v_r the radial velocity, p the pressure, $\dot{\epsilon}(T, N)$ the cooling term, and $q(T)$ the heating term. The last two are discussed below. The total energy density E is the sum of the thermal energy density U and the kinetic energy density:

$$E = U + \rho v_r^2 / 2. \quad (10.4)$$

ρ and the number density N are connected by

$$\rho = N \mu m_H, \quad (10.5)$$

where m_H denotes the mass of the hydrogen atom and μ the mean atomic weight. In our calculations we always use $\mu = 1.3$.

This set is closed by a polytropic equation of state (with $\gamma = 5/3$ in all our calculations),

$$U = \frac{p}{\gamma - 1}. \quad (10.6)$$

The temperature is given by the ideal gas law as

$$T = \frac{p \mu m_H}{\rho k_B}. \quad (10.7)$$

This model excludes heat conduction which is probably important for strongly shocked astrophysical plasmae.

The cooling model

We describe the radiated energy density per time, $\dot{\epsilon}$, by a temperature dependent RLF $\Lambda(T)$ times the number density squared,

$$\dot{\epsilon}(T, N) = N^2 \cdot \Lambda(T). \quad (10.8)$$

For the RLF $\Lambda(T)$ we use the approximation

$$\Lambda(T) = \Lambda_{0_i}(T)T^{\beta_i}, \quad T \in [T_i, T_{i+1}]. \quad (10.9)$$

RLFs have been published by several authors. The functions vary significantly depending on the different physical processes which are included. The assumed elemental abundances are of great importance for the RLF. The first radiative loss function (RLF1) we used is a fit to an optically thin, time independent RLF taken from Cook et al. [23] which uses solar photospheric abundances. The second loss function (RLF2) is a fit to an optically thin, time dependent radiative loss function taken from Schmutzler and Tscharnuter [132] which uses Allen's abundances. This RLF has been obtained by a thermally self-consistent, time-dependent computation of the cooling of a plasma from 10^9 K to 10^2 K. Both RLFs are shown in Figure 10.1 and their exact values are given in Tables 10.2 and 10.3 in the appendix. In all our calculations $\dot{\epsilon}$ is set to zero for temperatures below a threshold temperature T_C .

Our cooling model neglects processes which cool only linearly in the density, e.g. cooling by inverse Compton scattering. The use of RLFs also completely neglects ionization and recombination processes. Therefore, we probably overestimate the post-shock temperature as the kinetic energy converted by the shock is only used to heat the matter. Moreover, in reality, the newly shocked matter is likely to be underionized whereas gas on its cooling track tends to be overionized. Consequently, the gas may radiate at a considerably different rate from the equilibrium value used for RLF1. It probably also radiates at a considerably different rate than computed by the time-dependent RLF2, since the two cooling histories and thus the ionization structures do not correspond. The consequences of these simplifications are discussed in Section 10.7.

Figure 10.1: *The two RLFs used: Cook et al. [29] (solid line) and Schmutzler and Tscharnuter [158] (dashed line).*

Therefore, our physical model is more approximate than the models of IGF and GEC. However, the use of an RLF has the big advantage to be simple

enough to allow an analysis of the connection between the RLF and the response of the system. At the same time, it exhibits already most of the features which are characteristic for radiative cooling processes behind shocks. Moreover, the computational costs are sufficiently low to allow a systematic study.

For later use we give the expression for the cooling time τ (by use of eqs. 10.8, 10.9 and $U = 3/2kT$),

$$\tau(T, N) = \frac{T}{|dT/dt|} = \frac{3k}{2\Lambda_{0i}} \frac{T^{1-\beta_i}}{N}. \quad (10.10)$$

The heating model

To account for radiative heating of the flow we have introduced a heating term which, for temperatures below a certain threshold temperature $T_H \leq T_C$, sets the gas temperature to T_H .

10.2 The numerical methods

The AMRCART code

Equations 10.1–10.4 and 10.6 are solved by the spherically symmetric version of our AMRCART code on the basis of a Cartesian discretization. AMRCART combines a modern high resolution Eulerian MUSCL scheme developed by Colella and Glaz [21] with the adaptive mesh refinement algorithm by Berger [6]. It automatically refines the spatial grid and the time-step when the local truncation error is estimated to be bigger than a given threshold. This code was originally designed by Berger and LeVeque [7] for pure gas-dynamics in two space dimensions. It was adapted by Walder [154] to compute complex astrophysical problems, including reactive flows and arbitrary physical source terms in one, two, and three space dimensions.

The mesh refinement algorithm is crucial to the quality of our simulations. Figure 10.2 shows how finer meshes are created to improve the spatial resolution where it is needed. In regions with refined meshes the time-step is reduced by the same factor as well. Thus, each time-scale which is dynamically important can be resolved numerically. We emphasize that even in regions with extreme high densities, and at temperatures at which the RLF $\Lambda(T)$ is at its maximum, the radiative energy loss of each cell during one time step Δt is at most one percent of the current thermal energy in this cell in all our calculations.

Figure 10.2: Illustration of the mesh refinement algorithm. Shown are a computed density profile and the numerical mesh. Three levels (out of five) of refinement are shown. The mesh size is automatically refined by the code.

Some technical details

In all presented results the center of symmetry is located outside the left boundary of the computational domain. At the left boundary we use reflecting (supernova remnant) or inflow boundary conditions (wind bubble and colliding winds). We use free outflow conditions at the right boundary.

A note on the numerical error

Numerically obtained solutions are approximate solutions. Therefore, one should always convince oneself that the numerical solution is sufficiently close to the correct one. Figure 10.3 shows the significant, even qualitative difference between a *high-* and a *low-resolution* numerical solution of an unstable wind bubble (model WB1 of Table 10.4). They have been calculated with a finest spatial discretization of about $2.4 \cdot 10^{13}$ cm and $1.92 \cdot 10^{14}$ cm respectively. The size of the computational domain is 10^{20} cm. In both calculations the cfl-number has been fixed to 0.2. Thus, the time-steps differ by a factor of 8 as well. Note that even the low-resolution calculation has still a remarkably good resolution compared to most computations given in the literature.

This large error can be pinned down to the numerical smearing of the boundary interface between the cooling layer and the cold compressed layer. In connection with stiff source terms (radiative cooling in our case), a too broad smearing of the interfaces can cause unphysical wave speeds (see e.g. LeVeque and Yee [87], Colella et al. [22] or Klingenstein [73]). This problem is inherent to each numerical algorithm which is based on interface capturing by finite volumes.

We estimate the errors of our calculated interface speeds to be at most a few percent.

Figure 10.3: High- (top) and low-resolution (bottom) simulation of the wind bubble model WB1. Shown is the computed size of the radiative shock. The high-resolution simulation shows a bigger oscillation amplitude and the oscillation lasts nearly twice as long as in the low-resolution simulation. Note that in the high-resolution case the oscillation continues after 110'000 years but is substantially smaller after having undergone a mode-transition (see Figure 10.7).

10.3 Investigated flows

Simulations of wind bubbles (WB), supernova remnants (SNR) and colliding winds (CW) are the basis for our study. These flows are well documented in the literature and we give here only the characteristics needed for this work. A WB (see Figure 10.4) is the structure which results when a strong stellar wind blows into the uniform interstellar medium. Similarly, a SNR is the result of a strong explosion driving expelled gas against the uniform interstellar medium. In the case of CW, a fast wind sweeps up a slower predecessor wind from the same star. In the *adiabatic case*, all three flows are self-similar. The leading shock decelerates in the WB-case according to $v_s \propto t^{-2/5}$ (v_s denotes the shock velocity, t the time) and in the SNR-case according to $v_s \propto t^{-3/5}$. Ryu and Vishniac [121] give a nice overview of these flows. In the CW-case, the velocity of the leading shock is constant ([20]). If *cooling is included* the flows are no longer self-similar. However, Bertschinger [12] shows that under certain conditions radiative SNR and WB can be described by piecewise self-similar solutions.

Figure 10.4: *Leading part of the interaction zone in the radiative case. For details see text.*

We are interested in flows where the cooling layer is small against the radius of the structure. In this case – despite their different driving mechanisms – WB, SNR and CW have a similar leading part of the interaction zone where the two flows collide. The leading part of the interaction zone is illustrated in Figure 10.4 at the example of the WB. In all three cases, it consists of a leading shock (LS), a hot leading shell in which the shocked material cools (HLS) and a ‘cold’ dense layer with compressed, already cooled shocked material (CDL). The HLS is subject to the cooling instability, the CDL can play an important role for the evolution of this instability. We are interested in these two parts. The contact discontinuity (C) marks the rear end of the leading part of the interaction zone. Notice that in our study the reverse shock is nearly adiabatic since – due to the much lower density and the much higher temperature – the cooling time is considerably longer than the dynamical time. In the following we do not discuss this reverse, driving part of the flow.

We list the exact settings of all our calculations in Table 10.2 in the appendix. We performed SNR and WB simulations with different parameters up to the time where the thermal instability ceased (see Figure 10.3). CW were performed over a dynamical time which is equal to approximately 600 cooling times of the leading shell. All three flows have been calculated with both RLFs given in Section 10.1 and in the appendix. The results presented below are the quintessence of all these calculations. Of major importance is the WB calculation. Since the structure moderately decelerates, it is possible to scan a wide range of post-shock temperatures (in our case from $T \approx 10^{6.5}$ K to $T \approx 10^5$ K) while the global conditions remain nearly constant over one oscillation period of the instability.

10.4 The cooling instability of the leading shell for smooth flows

In this section we present the results for the case where two smooth flows collide. In Section 10.5 we investigate the instability for disturbed flows. At present, smoothness means that during one oscillation cycle the conditions for the radiative shock remain nearly constant. In Section 10.5 we give more thorough constraints.

In agreement with earlier investigations, our systematic study shows that the cooling instability for smooth flows – if present – manifests itself as an overstability: All quantities, e.g. the size of the cooling layer or the radiated energy, evolve in a periodic way with fixed period and amplitude. The linear stability analyses of CI and Bertschinger [12] show that the period of the overstability of the radiative shock is determined by dimensionless quantities δ_i ($i = 0, 1, 2, \dots$) which are eigenvalues of the boundary value problem describing the flow between the radiative shock and the rear end of its cooling layer. One usually speaks of the fundamental mode (F-mode, $i = 0$) and of overtone modes (1O-mode, 2O-mode, etc). The governing eigenvalue δ is related to the steady state position of the shock, x_0 , the velocity of the inflowing matter relative to the shock, u_{in} , and the oscillation period, T , by the relation $\delta = x_0/u_{in} \cdot 2\pi/T$. Previous investigations have shown that even in the non-linear regime the period is in good agreement with the fundamental (F) and the first overtone (1O) mode determined by linear stability analysis.

However, our analysis shows – also in agreement with earlier investigations – that the overstability can show different phenomenological manifestation when oscillating in one particular mode. Therefore, we propose to introduce an additional classification of the overstability, namely the notation of types.

Different types of oscillations

Following phenomenological criteria, we propose five different oscillation types. The most striking differences between the different types are: the oscillation amplitude, which we express as $\mathcal{A} = (q_{max} - q_{min})/q_{min}$ where q is a characteristic quantity of the cooling layer, whether the oscillations are sinusoidal or not, and the oscillation mechanism. Figure 10.5 and Figure 10.4 illustrate the characteristics of the different types. In the following, we give only a brief description of some aspects of these types and refer to earlier authors (see Section 10) for more detailed descriptions.

The *catastrophic C-type* is characterized by a dramatic collapse of the temperature at a certain moment of the oscillation cycle. In wide ranges of the cooling layer the temperature drops nearly to nebular temperature on a very

Figure 10.5: (Previous double page.) Time-series over one oscillation cycle (from left to right) for each different type of the overstability. Shown are the density- (solid line) and temperature-profiles (dashed line) of the cooling layer. From top to bottom: S1-type (F-mode with superimposed 1O-mode), I-type (F-mode), C-type (F-mode), M-type (1O-mode), and S2-type (1O-mode). The series correspond to the cycles shown in Figure 10.6. They start approximately at the minimum extent of the shell (phase $\phi = 0$) and end at the next minimum ($\phi = 1$). The length of the cooling layers are measured in units of the lengths of their first minima ($\phi = 0$). Notice the large difference in amplitude between the different types of oscillation for the F-mode. For the 1O-mode, the amplitude is generally small. Note that the cooling layers may have different sizes at phases $\phi = 0$ and $\phi = 1$. This is due to the influence of the dynamics in the cold dense layer (see Section 7) and the general deceleration of the structure. Although the types are independent of the particular flows we give in brackets the model from which we have taken the example: S1-type (CW), I-type (WB1), C-type (WB1), M-type (WB2f) and S2-type (WB1).

short time-scale. The density is hardly affected despite the rapid change in pressure due to the strong cooling (snapshots 4 and 5). A huge pressure cavity evolves and a secondary shock forms at the boundary to the cold layer as the pressure equilibrium starts to be re-established (visible in snapshots 3 – 6). The renewed growth sets in when the secondary shock in front of the cold layer hits the undisturbed medium again (snapshot 1). The amplitude $\mathcal{A}$ is large and can reach up to two orders of magnitude. None of the quantities oscillates sinusoidally. In particular, the radiated energy is rather peaked. For the RLF1 we find a C-type oscillation for stationary post shock temperatures $T_{st}^{ps} > 4 \cdot 10^5$ K. The upper limit probably lies higher than $T_{st}^{ps} \approx 4 \cdot 10^6$ K, the highest limit post shock temperature we have investigated for RLF1. For the RLF2 the C-type is present between $3 \cdot 10^5$ K $< T_{st}^{ps} < 5 \cdot 10^5$ K. We observe the C-type only in the F-mode.

As another extreme, we observe the *smooth S-types*. There, the shell remains hot during the entire oscillation cycle and no pressure cavity evolves. No secondary shocks are observed. All quantities oscillate rather sinusoidally. The S1-type can be associated with the F-mode, the S2-type with the 1O-mode. $\mathcal{A}$ is always of order one, but is generally smaller for the S2-type. In the case of the S1-type, as the shell shrinks, a pressure gradient evolves between the cold layer and the leading shock. The force it exerts leads to the renewed acceleration of the leading shock. In the case of the S2-type, on the other hand, a pressure wave evolves at the boundary to the cold layer which later hits the leading shock and accelerates it. This leads to the phase-shift between the energy loss and the size of the shell (see Figure 10.4). The differences between the S1-type

(F-mode) and the S2-type (1O-mode) correspond to the results of the linear analysis of CI which predict knots and phase-shifts for overtone modes. In the RLF1 we find the S2-type for temperatures $1.7 \cdot 10^5 \text{ K} < T_{st}^{ps} < 2.5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ K}$. Note that the stability limit is determined by the insufficient spatial resolution in the simulation and may be somewhat lower in reality. We find no S1-type in the RLF1. For the RLF2, we find the S1-type for temperatures between $1.8 \cdot 10^5 \text{ K} < T_{st}^{ps} < 2.2 \cdot 10^5 \text{ K}$ and the S2-type for temperatures $6.6 \cdot 10^5 \text{ K} < T_{st}^{ps} < 8.5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ K}$.

The *intermediate I-type* occurs during the transition from C-type to S-types. The leading shell always remains rather hot, but – as in the C-type – the shell vanishes apart from the secondary shock. The amplitude of the oscillation is still rather big. We find the I-type for temperatures in the range of $2.5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ K} < T_{st}^{ps} < 4 \cdot 10^5 \text{ K}$ for the RLF1 and in the range of $2.2 \cdot 10^5 \text{ K} < T_{st}^{ps} < 3 \cdot 10^5 \text{ K}$ for the RLF2. Also the I-type is observed only in connection with the F-mode.

In the *mixed M-type* the leading shell is divided into two parts, namely a high density part near the cold layer and a low density part behind the leading shock. While the low density part remains hot the high density part strongly cools (snapshots 2 and 3). When this cooled dense matter is swallowed by the cold dense layer a pressure wave or a weak shock is generated (snapshot 4) which travels through the leading shell towards the leading shock (snapshots 4, 5 and 6). On its way it enhances the density of the areas it passes. Finally, it hits the leading shock and accelerates it (snapshot 6). By now the shell is again divided into a high density and a low density part (snapshot 6 and 1). The oscillation amplitude is of order one. Most of the energy is released during a very short time. We find the M-type for the temperature range between $5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ K} < T_{st}^{ps} < 6.6 \cdot 10^5 \text{ K}$ of the RLF2, we do not observe it for the RLF1. The M-type oscillates in the 1O-mode. Like the S2-type, the M-type shows knots and phase-shifts.

The phenomenology of the overstability and, in particular, the amplitudes of the oscillations are essentially determined by the non-linear terms. Each of the modes lives mainly in two different forms, a weak and a strong one. The *weak form* of the F-mode corresponds to the S1-type, the *strong form* to the C-type, while the *weak form* of the 1O-mode to the S2-type and the *strong form* of the 1O-mode to the M-type.

Figure 10.6: (Next double page.) *The different types and modes of the cooling overstability shown in some characteristic quantities. The graphs correspond to the cycles shown in Figure 10.5. From top to bottom: Size of the leading shell, radiated power (of the entire leading shell), post shock temperature, shock-velocity, average density of the leading shell and mass-flux from the leading shell into the cold compressed gas layer. Notice the highly different amplitudes of the oscillations in the different types.*

What determines the modes and the types?

We do not yet have a final answer to this question. However, we present some observations. They are mostly based on mode-transitions which occur in WB-simulations when the post-shock temperature slowly decreases due to the deceleration of the entire interaction region. We begin with two general observations.

- 1) According to our experience, for a given radiative loss function, the type of the overstability is fixed by the post-shock temperature T_{st}^{ps} of the (unstable) stationary solution alone: Different forms of excitation of the instability at the same T_{st}^{ps} result – after a certain relaxation time – in the same mode and the same type. *We detect no sign of multiple solutions or a bifurcation of the solution.*

- 2) Linear theory predicts that whenever the F-mode is present the 1O-mode is present as well. However, *in the strong forms of the F-mode we do not observe any sign of a superimposed 1O-mode.* Only at the transition from the I-type to the S-type a slight trace of a superimposed 1O-mode shows up. At this point, we observe no phase shift between the modes due to the non-

Figure 10.7: *Mode-transition in WB1 from the F-mode (I-type) to the 1O-mode (S2-type) for the RLF1. Shown are the time-evolution of the size of the leading shell (top) and the post-shock temperature (bottom).*

rational ratio of the eigenfrequencies. The phase shift only sets in when the overstability is already very smooth (Figure 10.7). The physical reason for the absence of overtone modes in the strong forms may be the total destruction of

Figure 10.8: Model WB2f: Stability behavior when applying RLF2 for $1 \cdot 10^6 > T_{st}^{ps} > 5 \cdot 10^5$. Shown is the size of the leading shell (top) and the post-shock temperature (bottom). Above $T_{st}^{ps} \approx 7 \cdot 10^5$ the (artificially excited) F-mode (C-type) is strongly damped, below this temperature a 1O-mode is growing. The further evolution is shown in the next figure.

the leading shell and, therefore, the history after each oscillation cycle.

The next two points are dealing with the transition of types and modes when scanning RLF1 in the temperature range where the logarithmic slope changes from a negative to a positive value (see Figure 10.7).

- 3) We observe a mode and type-transition from the F-mode (I-type) to the 1O-mode (S2-type) at $T_{st}^{ps} \approx 2.5 \cdot 10^5$ K when applying RLF1. That is approximately the temperature where β jumps from a strongly negative value to a moderately positive value. *For this transition, the change of β associated with the post-shock temperature seems to be critical.*

- 4) The absence of the F-mode below $T_{st}^{ps} \approx 2.5 \cdot 10^5$ K for RLF1 is surprising. The post-shock temperature varies over the entire oscillation cycle between $1.9 \cdot 10^5$ K and $2.3 \cdot 10^5$ K and even most parts of the shell have always temperatures above $7.9 \cdot 10^4$ K. For these temperatures, β is equal to 0.15 while below $7.9 \cdot 10^4$ K it becomes strongly positive. Linear analysis predicts for $\beta = 0.15$ the F- and the 1O-mode to be present. Indeed, when using a RLF assuming a constant $\beta = 0.15$ we observe both modes. We conclude that *the mode is not governed by the β which is associated with the stationary post-shock temperature alone.* The entire cooling layer and, in particular, the rear boundary interface may be of similar importance. The strongly positive β for $T \leq 7.9 \cdot 10^4$ K reduces the cooling efficiency as compared to $\beta = 0.15$ and in

Figure 10.9: *WB2f: Mode-transition from 1O-mode (M-type) to F-mode (C-type) at $T_{st}^{ps} < 5 \cdot 10^5$ when applying RLF2. Shown is the size of the leading shell (top) and the post-shock temperature (bottom). (The evolution at earlier times is shown in the previous figure.)*

this way seems to damp the F-mode.

The next three points summarize the transition of modes and types when scanning RLF2 in the temperature range $1 \cdot 10^6 \gtrsim T_{st}^{ps} \gtrsim 4 \cdot 10^5$ K (see Figs. 10.8 and 10.9). This is exactly the range where RLF2 forms a 'valley'. For $T < 4 \cdot 10^5$ K the logarithmic slope of the RLF2 is equal to -1.92, for $4 \cdot 10^5 < T < 5.37 \cdot 10^5$ K it is zero and above $5.37 \cdot 10^5$ K it is equal to 1.12. The planar models, CPF_55 to CPF_25, prove that the different modes and types observed in this 'valley region' of the RLF2 are not merely transition phenomena but persist if the structure does not slow down.

- 5) The excited F-mode (C-type) at $T_{st}^{ps} \gtrsim 9 \cdot 10^5$ K is very strongly damped when RLF2 is applied. This suggests a stable situation for this temperature, and indeed the planar model CPF_55 with $T_{st}^{ps} = 9 \cdot 10^5$ K is stable. At this temperature we have $\beta = 1.12$ which is in the stable range according to linear theory. However, large parts of the cooling layer have temperatures associated with an unstable β . Despite this fact, *in this case the β associated with the post-shock temperature seems to determine the stability.*

- 6) Below $T_{st}^{ps} \approx 8.5 \cdot 10^5$ K a 1O-mode of the S2-type grows for RLF2 (CPF_45 for $T_{st}^{ps} \approx 8.25 \cdot 10^5$ K shows S2-type behavior). The post shock temperature does not leave the region with $\beta = 1.12$ over the entire oscillation cycle. Interestingly, nearly in the entire cooling layer the temperature is in the range where $\beta = 1.12$! With decreasing T_{st}^{ps} , the type of the overstability

slowly changes to the strong form of the 1O-mode (M-type) (CPF_35 for $T_{st}^{ps} \approx 6.1 \cdot 10^5$ K is clearly of the M-type). β associated with T_{st}^{ps} is still 1.12! *This again indicates that the RLF for temperatures below T_{st}^{ps} plays a significant role.*

- 7) As can be seen from Figure 10.9, at $T_{st}^{ps} \approx 5 \cdot 10^5$ K another mode-transition takes place for RLF2, this time from the 1O- (M-type) to the F-mode (C-type). This temperature corresponds approximately to a change in β from the stable value 1.12 to zero, a value at which – according to linear theory – both modes should be present. *The change of β corresponding to the post-shock temperature seems to be important for the mode-transition.*

The emerging picture is not homogeneous. Sometimes, the β associated with T_{st}^{ps} seems to play an outstanding role. More often, however, the presence, the mode, and the type of the overstability cannot be determined on the basis of the local characteristics of the RLF at this temperature. We come back to these points in Section 10.7

10.5 The cooling instability of the leading shell for disturbed flows

The set of disturbed flows

We now discuss the cooling instability for disturbed flows. We disturb the flow upstream of the interaction zone between position r_0 and $r_0 + \lambda_0$ by setting the density to

$$\rho(r) = \rho_0 \left[1 + \xi \sin \left(\pi \frac{r - r_0}{\lambda_0} \right) \right] \text{ if } r_0 \leq r \leq r_0 + \lambda_0 \quad (10.11)$$

where ρ_0 is the density of the undisturbed flow. The disturbance is applied after the system has evolved into a limit cycle. The leading shock can hit it at an arbitrary phase $0 \leq \phi_0 \leq 1$ of the oscillation cycle (where $\phi = 0, 1$ are the phases of minimum extent of the leading shell). Note the difference to the setting of IGF who let the shock in its stationary position run against a, however similar, density disturbance.

We performed a systematic investigation of disturbed I-type systems on the example of WB1. All disturbances were applied around 69'000 years. The exact settings of these models can be taken from Table 10.5 of the appendix. Except for two models (WB1_d0 and WB1_d1) the amplitude of the disturbance, ξ , is never bigger than 1. The ratio of the mass of the disturbance, M_d , to the mean mass (over a period) of the hot leading shell, M_{ls} , varies from 0.017 to 73, the ratio of M_d to the mass of the subsequent cold dense layer, M_{cdl} , from $1.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ to 0.6155. The ratio of the length of the disturbance, λ_0 , to the characteristic length of the limit cycle, $\ell = T \cdot v_{st}^{sh}$, varies from 0.05 to 8.8 (T denotes the

oscillation period and v_{st}^{sh} the stationary shock velocity). The shock hits the disturbance at phases between $\phi_0 = 0.07$ and 0.52 . The results presented in this section are a summary of the analysis of this set.

Noisy, original periodic, aperiodic, and modulated periodic evolution

We found five clearly different responses of the I-type system to disturbances. The time-evolutions of three of them are shown in Figure 10.10 and a schematic representation of all possible responses is given in Figure 10.11. If the disturbance is small (in which sense we see below), one observes a rapid, aperiodic,

Figure 10.10: *Noisy original periodic, aperiodic and modulated periodic evolution of the radiative shock after being disturbed at time 68'893 years. Shown are post-shock temperatures of models WB1-d4.0.1, WB1-d4.1 and WB1-d6 (from top to bottom).*

much smaller scaled variation of only one cycle of the original oscillation. We call this a *noisy, original periodic evolution (np)*. If the disturbance is appropriately scaled, the periodicity of the limit cycle is completely destroyed and we

have an *aperiodic evolution of the radiative shock (ap)*. However, after a certain time, the system relaxes to the original, periodic evolution. Disturbances on a larger length scale and not too big amplitude ξ result in a modulation of the limit cycle, governed by the slowly changing pre-shock conditions. In this case, we speak of a *modulated periodic evolution (mp)*. On the other hand, if we have a very massive disturbance on a relatively short length-scale, the leading *shell*

Figure 10.11: Schematic representation of the different responses versus mass and length of the density disturbance.

collapses nearly immediately (co). The history of the leading shell is destroyed and the shell behaves according to the new global conditions. For example, in model WB_d0 the accumulation of the mass of the disturbance by the cold dense layer leads to a slow down of the entire interaction zone and the leading shock becomes stable. Finally, if we encounter a small mass disturbance on a large length scale, the system shows nearly *no reaction (nr)*. We note already here, that big disturbances may significantly disturb the cold dense layer downstream of the radiative shock wave (see Section 10.6).

The aperiodic evolution

The oscillation mechanisms of the np- and the mp-cases are similar to the mechanisms described in Section 10.4. Here we describe the aperiodic response of the radiative shock at the example of model WB1_d4.1. It evolves very similar to what was described by IGF. We concentrate on some aspects important to the understanding of the constraints for the evolution of disturbed shocks.

The size of the initial density disturbance is crucial for the time evolution illustrated in Figs. 10.10 and 10.12. As the density disturbance passes through the leading shock it shrinks in size while being compressed. Cooling of the hot shell starts in the region with enhanced density. In fact, cooling is so fast that the flow cannot maintain pressure balance and a pressure cavity forms in the cooled region. A sheet of cold and initially over-compressed matter is

Figure 10.12: *The aperiodic evolution of the radiative shock and its cooling layer from example of WB1_d4.1. Shown are density- (solid line) and temperature-profiles (dashed line) of three successive times. The evolution is governed by the fast partial cooling and the waves which are created during this process. Details can be taken from Section 6.3.*

then created within the hot leading shell (snapshot 1 of Figure 10.12). The relaxation of the over-compressed sheet generates two pressure waves or weak shocks traveling forwards and backwards in the hot shell. Their strengths are a direct measure of the violence of formation of this second dense sheet. The dynamical consequences of these waves are twofold. Firstly, temperature and density increase again in those regions where the waves pass. The consequence for the cooling scale cannot be estimated easily, since in this region of the radiative loss function the increase in temperature and density are working in opposite directions. For RLF1 and in this temperature range the cooling scale likely is to decrease behind weak waves, it is likely to increase behind strong waves. In our example, the first possibility applies. A second important consequence of these waves is encountered when they eventually hit the leading shock. The pushing wave transfers part of its energy to the leading shock which is accelerated. As a consequence of the shock jump conditions, the post-shock temperature is higher and the density is lower in the freshly shocked part than in the older parts of the shell (compare snapshot 2). The further development can hardly be followed in detail. The older, denser parts cool faster than the newer parts. Further cold, compressed sheets are formed, usually near the boundary to the cold layer. Their formation creates again new waves and the process continues (snapshot 3).

Our investigation proves – for the I-type range and for parameterized cooling – that this process does not last forever and that the limit cycle finally recovers.

The constraints for the evolution and relaxation times

As can be seen from Table 10.5 in the appendix, models having a length of the disturbance between 5 and 20 percent of the characteristic length of the limit cycle and having masses between 10 and 40 percent of the mass of the leading shell react with an aperiodic evolution to the disturbance (case ap).

To achieve the most efficient aperiodic evolution, the region of enhanced density has to be *moderately smaller* than the hot shell, since otherwise the entire leading shell would be affected nearly similarly and we would encounter a modulation of the original oscillation (case mp) or a collapse of the shell (case co). On the other hand, the region with enhanced density has to be large enough to be able to create *secondary waves* as powerful as possible, since these waves are driving the aperiodic evolution.

For the aperiodic evolution, we define the *relaxation time*, τ_{rel} , as the difference between the time when the aperiodic evolution first sets in and the time when the regular periodic evolution starts again. τ_{rel} can be taken from Table 10.5. The biggest ratio of τ_{rel}/τ_0 (τ_0 being the period of the limit cycle) we measured is 3 (model WB1_d4.1). In this case, the ratio of the characteristic lengths, λ_0/ℓ_c , is 0.2, the mass ratio, M_d/M_{hls} , is 0.4. Comparing models

WB1_d3, WB1_d2.2 and WB1_d4.1 we notice the influence of the different masses. A larger mass of the disturbance leads to the generation of stronger pressure waves, and the relaxation time increases.

10.6 The cold dense layer (CDL) and the hot leading shell (HLS): An interacting system

Downstream of the radiative shock and its cooling layer, a thin layer of cold, compressed gas is established (see Figure 10.4). In this section we study the dynamics of this layer, in particular its interaction with the thermally unstable radiative shock.

Mass feeding of the CDL

We define the boundary between the cold dense layer and the hot leading shell to be at the surface where cooling is balanced by heating. Through this boundary interface, there is a net mass-flux from the cooling layer of the radiative shock into the cold dense layer which is shown in the last row of Figure 10.4.

It is interesting that for smooth flows the five different types of the overstability manifest themselves also in these mass-fluxes (Figure 10.4). Most remarkable, there is a very significant difference between the strong and the weak form of the overstability. For S-type instabilities the mass-fluxes are smooth and vary only moderately over one cycle. In the strong forms of the overstability, most of the mass enters the CDL during a very short time-interval of the cycle. This is a direct consequence of the sudden collapse of large amounts of the hot shell. Again we note a significant difference between the modes: In the IO-mode (M-type), the peak of the mass-flux is correlated with the largest, in the F-mode (I- and C-types) with the smallest extension of the cooling layer. Note also that in the I- and C-type overstability the onset of the mass-flux at approximately one third of the period is accompanied by the formation of the secondary shock which is attached to the CDL. Obviously, the irregularity of the mass flux is enhanced in disturbed flows.

Response of the CDL to the cooling overstability of the leading shell

The non-steady mass-flux through the interface between the HLS and the CDL introduces disturbances into the CDL, even when smooth flows collide. Assuming that the size of the CDL is much bigger than the HLS, Bertschinger [12] has shown by linear stability analysis that the disturbances damp on a scale

Figure 10.13: Density distribution of the CDL of WB1 (*I*-type instability) immediately after the leading shell has collapsed and the overcompressed sheet of freshly cooled matter is swallowed by the CDL (left) and half a period later in the limit cycle (right).

which is much smaller than the size of the CDL. When we encounter the same conditions, our numerical study shows indeed this behavior. However, there are many cases where the size of the CDL and the HLS are comparable, e.g. in the period after the transition of the shock from the adiabatic to the radiative regime. Moreover, the analysis in Section 10.6 shows that in strong forms of the overstability the mass feeding into the CDL – and, therefore, the introduced disturbance – is extremely pulsed with a large pulse height. When disturbed flows collide, these disturbances can become even larger. Such disturbances are clearly beyond the scope of linear analysis. Therefore, it is not surprising that under these different circumstances the disturbances can survive for a significant time.

Traveling waves and density variation

As described in Section 10.5 the sudden cooling of large parts of the hot leading shell leads to the formation of an initially overcompressed sheet of cold matter. Apparently, the same mechanism also works in the strong forms of the limit cycle of the overstability when smooth flows collide, with the difference that the newly cooled, overcompressed sheet is in contact with the already present CDL. The swallowing of such an overcompressed sheet by the CDL is shown on the left of Figure 10.13. The thin sheet at the very right boundary of the CDL, having approximately twice the density of the rest, contains the freshly cooled matter. At this time, the density variance in the shell is greatest (see Figure 10.14). In the following, relatively quiescent phase of the limit cycle, the overcompression relaxes by a wave traveling through the CDL (right graph

Figure 10.14: *Oscillating size (top) and density-variance σ (bottom) of the CDL. Shown are 18 cycles after the transition from the adiabatic to the radiative regime of model WB1. The overstability of the leading shell is of the C- and I-type.*

of Figure 10.13). Eventually, the propagating wave is reflected at the rear interface of the CDL and interacts with the other waves. As a result, the density structure of the CDL is rather complicated in the presence of strong forms of the overstability of the radiative shock. The evolution of the density variance shown in Figure 10.14 exactly mirrors the cycle of the overstability of the leading shell. It shows peaks every time a new, overcompressed sheet is incorporated into the CDL. The figure demonstrates that the density variance is rather high as long as we encounter I-type instability. Not visible in the figure, the CDL rapidly smooths after the instability changes to S-type. Note also, that we do not find a significant difference between the density variance of an isothermal CDL (model WB1c) and an adiabatic CDL (model WB1).

Oscillations of the CDL

The CDL is expected to become compressed when it pushes the shock after the collapse. This should lead to a considerable shrinking of the size of the CDL, at least as long as there is not too much mass in the CDL. Indeed, we observe such oscillations (see Figure 10.14). However, the traveling, reflecting, and interacting waves disturb the basic oscillation cycle remarkably. Periods of nearly no oscillation are followed by periods of nearly regular oscillation and vice-versa. When smooth flows collide, we find changes in the size of the CDL

up to 15 percent as long as we encounter I-type instability in the WB and SNR simulations. Much larger oscillation of the CDL can be excited in disturbed flows as will be shown in the next paragraph.

The back-coupling to the cooling layer

We now investigate how the dynamics of the CDL affect the radiative cooling overstability of the hot leading shell. Of course, the oscillation of the CDL changes the rear boundary conditions of the cooling layer with time, which influences the evolution of the radiative shock. This back-coupling can be strong in disturbed flows as will be demonstrated below. When smooth flows collide, the effect is present but never large (See Figure 10.3). Only immediately after the transition from the adiabatic to the radiative phase it is considerable. In this phase the amplitude of the overstable oscillation can change up to 15 percent from one period to the next. Although weaker, the effect can be observed as long as the overstability is of the I-type.

The evolution of model WB1_d7

WB1_d7 is a disturbed model with a modulated periodic behavior (see Table 10.5). The disturbing mass is 7.3 times the average mass of the hot leading shell and 6.18 percent of the mass of the CDL. The encounter of the interaction zone with this density disturbance excites an oscillation of the CDL with an amplitude of about 15 percent. The period of the oscillation approximately corresponds to the length of the density disturbance. As demonstrated in Figure 10.15, this oscillation of the CDL significantly influences the further evolution of the cooling overstability.

Note also the direct consequence of the density disturbance for the overstability (see again Figure 10.15). The leading shock slows down. The oscillation period becomes smaller due to the decreasing cooling time. However, the radiative energy release increases due to the density enhancement which overcomes the decrease of the emitting volume due to the smaller size of the shell. When the interaction zone has passed the density peak, it accelerates again. At 73'500 years the oscillation of the leading shell has nearly recovered the state it had before the disturbance. However, the absorbed mass has led to a general slow down of the interaction zone and to the oscillation of the CDL.

Switch on, switch off system

The onset of the cooling instability is very sensitive to the post-shock temperature. Thus, the instability can switch on and off under the influence of an oscillatory cold dense layer as we will demonstrate with a CW calculation. At

Figure 10.15: Time evolution of the model WB1_d7 after running into a disturbance having 6.18 percent of the mass of the CDL. **1. line:** Size of the CDL, **2. line:** Velocity of interface between CDL and HLS, **3. line:** Size of HLS, **4. line:** Radiated energy per time from the HLS.

the beginning of the evolution shown in Figure 10.16 a strong wave is traveling backwards and forwards in the CDL. Due to the oscillation of the CDL, the velocity of the rear boundary interface of the cooling layer is trans-critical: If the velocity falls below the critical value, the cooling instability stops, if the interface is again pushed over the critical value, the instability reappears. The overstability is of the S1-type. The instability immediately becomes periodic if the critical post-shock temperature is exceeded.

The third instable time period is most interesting. The instability is excited by a very small overshooting of the shell over the stationary value. Although the excitation is small, the amplitude of the oscillation is growing up to a value which is inherent to the system and the applied cooling function. Note that the velocity of the rear boundary of the cooling layer is approximately

Figure 10.16: The overstability switches on and off under the influence of an oscillating CDL. **Top:** Size of the CDL. **Middle:** Velocity of the interface between the CDL and the HLS. **Bottom:** Post-shock temperature of the leading shock.

constant or is even decreasing while the amplitude of the oscillation is growing. The stationary amplitude of this oscillation is nearly the same as the one in

the second instable time period. The period of the limit cycle increases with time due to the decreasing density in the slow wind.

10.7 Discussion

What determines the types and modes?

The large sample of computations presented in this chapter strongly indicates: If parameterized loss functions are applied to smooth colliding flows, a differently disturbed radiative shock wave always relaxes to the same asymptotic solution, whether this solution is stable or overstable. However, the time scale of the relaxation may strongly depend on the size and the sign of the excitation. The stationary post-shock temperature T_{st}^{ps} completely fixes the stability properties (stability limit, mode, type) of a radiative shock for a *given* RLF.

The cooling overstability in a *C-type (I-type)* manifests itself as runaway cooling. This requires that a significant amount of the thermal energy of the cooling layer is radiated on a time-scale which is short compared to the hydrodynamical time-scale. Thus, β has to be sufficiently negative at T_{st}^{ps} and in a sufficiently wide temperature range below. For example, this condition may be fulfilled at temperatures where line cooling of a strong coolant just sets in and abruptly enhances the cooling efficiency. *For these types, the stability properties are completely determined by the strongly negative logarithmic slope of the RLF around T_{st}^{ps} .* At least, we see hardly any difference between RLF1 and RLF2 even though the two loss functions are different for lower temperatures, except for the absolute values of the oscillation period which are due to the shift in Λ -direction by half a magnitude.

Runaway cooling and, therefore, negative β are also necessary for the occurrence of the *M-type*. Here, however, only the low temperature part at the rear end of the shell collapses. To prevent the shell from complete collapse (as in the C-type), the cooling time in the hotter front part of the shell has to be sufficiently longer than the time needed to collapse and reconstruct the rear part. This requires a sufficiently positive β at temperatures $T \approx T_{st}^{ps}$. These conditions may be fulfilled at temperatures between regions with efficient line cooling for different ions. *For this type, not only the shape of the RLF at T_{st}^{ps} is important for the stability properties, but the entire shape of the valley region.*

For the *S-types* it is necessary that the cooling time-scale at every point of the cooling layer remains of the same order as the hydrodynamical time-scale. *With the exception of the rear boundary layer, the cooling layer must have temperatures associated with moderately positive β .* For the temperatures we encounter in the rear boundary layer, the shape of the RLF may be arbitrary. In particular, it can be strongly negative (e.g. for smooth types with post-shock

temperatures in a valley region). This does not necessarily mean that the shape of the RLF for temperatures in the rear boundary layer is unimportant for the properties of the instability. On the contrary, we notice *the importance of the conditions in the rear boundary layer for the stability limit and the mode* in many examples.

For the modes the situation seems even more puzzling. We notice the absence of the overtone modes in the strong form of the F-mode oscillation. We ascribe this to the total destruction of information associated with each collapse of the shell. Overtone modes just have no time to grow. We emphasize the existence of a strong form of the 1O-mode which is able to radiate a substantial amount of energy. Therefore, the 1O-mode is potentially as important as the F-mode even though the temperature range of its appearance is considerably smaller. Finally, we find it remarkable that, despite the highly nonlinear character of radiative cooling, we find weak and strong forms of the overstability which, while appearing phenomenologically so differently, are governed by the same modes.

From the insight into the working mechanism of the different types one may find constraints for the transitions between them. However, there is certainly no simple way to exactly determine the stability properties at every T_{st}^{ps} .

Temperature regions with different stability properties

Based on the above discussion we propose five different stability regions for RLFs. In Figure 10.17 we sketch a RLF which shows the typical behavior of most high-temperature RLFs (see e.g. [132] or GEC). We note again that the boundaries between the different regions can be given only approximately, since they cannot be derived by a simple rule.

- Region I: There is always a *low-temperature stable region*, which is also present for fully time-dependent cooling. IGF and GEC found that shocks with speeds below about 130 km/s are stable.

- Region II: Here we encounter *smooth types of the overstability*. In this region, we expect the shape of the entire cooling function to be important for the stability properties. In particular, the rear boundary layer attached to the cold, compressed sheet can play a significant role. The upper boundary of this region lies at a temperature which is slightly above the point where the logarithmic slope of the RLF becomes strongly negative.

- Region III: We find strong *runaway instabilities* (C- or I-type, always F-mode) when T_{st}^{ps} lies in a region of the RLF with negative logarithmic slope **and** T_{st}^{ps} is sufficiently above the low-temperature edge of the negative slope region. Under these conditions, the overstability is nearly independent of the shape of the RLF at lower temperatures.

Figure 10.17: Sketch of a typical radiative loss function $\Lambda(T)$ on a log-log scale. The solid line denotes the region we have extensively investigated, the dashed line denotes the high-temperature region we have not investigated. Shown are the five qualitatively different stability regions. region I: stable; region II: smooth types; region III: runaway cooling; region IV: valley region; region *: behavior not known; region V: Bremsstrahlung region.

- Region IV: This region is associated with a *valley in the RLF* which determines the stability properties. Note, that the valley is larger than stability region IV (e.g. between $1.6 \cdot 10^5$ and $1 \cdot 10^6$ K in RLF2). The shape of the RLF below the valley seems of minor importance. The strong form of the 1O-mode (M-type) can only occur in such a region. In addition, we find in this region the strong form of the F-mode as well as the smooth form of the 1O-mode and even stable behavior. For this region it seems hardly possible to predict whether or not, and in which mode and type, the overstability is present. Any real shock which is slightly disturbed can abruptly change into any of these types. In this sense, the shock reacts truly chaotic in this region.

- Region V: *High-temperature Bremsstrahlung region* with $\beta = 0.5$. Although we have not done any experiment in this region we predict a smooth S2-type oscillation if we are sufficiently far away from the low-temperature boundary where the logarithmic slope flattens to $\beta \lesssim 0.5$. Near the low-temperature boundary the existence of a F-mode may be possible. Also in this region the rear boundary layer of the hot shell may be important for the stability property.

Radiative cooling overstability in colliding flows							
types		characteristics					
F	1O	streng.	ampli. F-mode	$\tau_{\text{cool}} /$ τ_{hydro}	collaps. shell	temp. $T_{\text{neb.}}$	second. shocks
S1	S2	weak	$\mathcal{O}(1)$	≈ 1 always	no	no	none
I		mod.	$\mathcal{O}(10)$	temp. $\lesssim 1$	slowly	no	weak
C	M	strong	$\lesssim \mathcal{O}(100)$	temp. $\ll 1$	yes	yes	strong

Table 10.1: Schematic summary of the classification and the characteristics for the spherically symmetric cooling overstability. Note, the oscillation amplitude of the 1O-mode is always of order one, also for the strong form. F and 1O denote the modes, S1, S2, I, C, and M denote the types. $T_{\text{neb.}}$ stands for nebular temperature, streng. for strength, temp. for temporarily, mode. for moderate, collaps. for collapsing, second. for secondary, and ampli. for amplitude.

Parameterized radiative loss function versus more elaborated models

IGF and GEC emphasize the need for fully time-dependent radiation hydrodynamical calculations which explicitly include ionization, recombination and non-equilibrium line-cooling, and we completely agree with them. However, such computations are very costly. At present and even in the near future, systematic longtime evolution and multi-dimensional computations cannot be done using such an approach. One has, therefore, to deal with the use of parameterized loss functions. Some of the major short comings of parameterized RLFs compared to fully time dependent computations have already been mentioned in Sect 10.1, and were discussed in some more detail by GEC and IGF. A key point is that the ionization structure of the plasma does not necessarily correspond to the gas temperature. The cooling history is often crucial for the determination of the ionization structure. Consequently, the correct cooling rate cannot be described by a function of the temperature alone as in the case of a RLF.

In the runaway cooling range ($u_{in} \approx 200$ km/s), GEC directly compare one example of the fully time-dependent model with simulations applying two differently parameterized models (their Figure 3). The global dynamics resulting from the two different approaches qualitatively coincide. The oscillation period and amplitude differ by some percent. *For the runaway cooling range* this result is not surprising. However, in cooling regions II and IV we assume that the correct shock dynamics is less well mirrored when using a RLF. Here, the

stability properties cannot be pinned down to the shape of the loss function around T_{st}^{ps} . A time dependent computation in this regime may yield different overall dynamics.

Generally, newly shocked matter is likely to be underionized, whereas gas on its cooling track tends to be overionized. *In regions II and III underionization tends to stabilize the shock* since the effective cooling function flattens compared to the parameterized function at this temperature (see Figure 2 of GEC). The influence of a possible overionization at lower temperature will not change this picture, because lower temperatures are of minor importance for runaway cooling. On the other hand, *in the valley stability region IV, underionization tends to decrease the logarithmic slope of the effective loss function at T_{st}^{ps} , and has probably a destabilizing effect.* Overionization along the cooling track may slightly reduce the size of the collapsing part at the rear end of the cooling layer.

Partly based on the global similarity between fully time dependent computations and RLF computations GEC suggested that the overall stability properties of a radiative shock can be determined by the local β at the high temperature end of the recombination zone, at least if only small perturbations of the steady state shock are considered. As has been demonstrated in this chapter, this local condition applies only in runaway cooling regions. For other stability types we assume that the importance of the cooling behavior at lower temperatures persists also in a time-dependent computation.

Also GEC have shown that *some important details are missed or are different in the parameterized model*, even in cases where the overall dynamics are relatively well captured by parameterized cooling. In addition, IGF have found *considerable differences between calculated spectra for equilibrium and non-equilibrium cooling shocks*. In general, we feel that the question of how well the use of parameterized radiative loss functions can replace fully time-dependent calculations badly needs further investigation. Not only as far as the global dynamics are concerned but also with regard to diagnostics. A future perspective may be the use of improved parameterized models, e.g. the use of several different radiative loss functions, to better account for the different cooling histories

10.8 Conclusion

Before drawing conclusions from this systematic study of the long-term evolution of the radiative cooling instability in colliding flows we emphasize that these results hold for parameterized cooling of the form $N^2 \cdot \Lambda(T)$. Possible relevances for fully time-dependent cooling are discussed in Section 10.7. Even though most of the results are obtained by computing spherically symmetric

flows, the conclusions are only reliable for planar flows, since the size of the radiative shock is much smaller than the radius of the structure.

We emphasize the many *different manifestations of the cooling overstability*. For both practically important modes, the fundamental and first overtone mode, we find a strong and a weak form of the overstability. The key point for the distinction between these two forms is the ratio of the two governing time scales, $\eta = \tau_{\text{cool}}/\tau_{\text{hydro}}$, which in the strong forms may be temporarily very small but which is always of order one in the weak forms. We, therefore, propose the introduction of different phenomenological types as summarized in Table 10.1.

The system always relaxes to the *same asymptotic oscillatory or stable solution* which only depends on the stationary post-shock temperature. This asymptotic solution is independent of the sign and the size of the disturbance. It is possible to distinguish five qualitatively different stability regions with different stability properties. Even though the importance of the different shapes of the RLF in different temperature regions can be roughly estimated, we find no easy criterion which determines the stability properties, neither the stability limit, nor the mode, nor the type. In particular, we find many examples in which the logarithmic slope of the RLF at the stationary post-shock temperature is not the only relevant parameter for the stability behavior.

Probably *not all radiative shocks are unstable above a certain threshold velocity* of the stationary shock. Due to the existence of 'valleys' in the radiative loss function we find stable islands or smooth types of the instability even for high velocities. A necessary but not sufficient condition for their occurrence is a logarithmic slope of the radiative loss function which according to linear theory is stable at the stationary post-shock temperature. We also find a strong form of the first overtone mode, which exists in such valley regions.

We find different *evolutionary scenarios when radiative shocks run into a single density disturbance*. The system reacts aperiodic only if the length and the mass of the disturbance are appropriately scaled. If they are too small we find only a moderate, short reaction but the system remains in the original limit cycle. If the length is too big the system has time to adjust itself and the oscillations are modulated according to the new pre-shock conditions. If the mass is too large, the shell collapses immediately and its history is destroyed.

The *cold compressed gas* downstream of an interstellar radiative shock can be important for the stability of the shock. When smooth flows collide, this layer is to a minor degree (ten percent effects) dynamically important in the strong forms of the instability. However, a density disturbance in the flow on the order of a few percent of the mass of the layer leads to a significant dynamical influence of the layer. As long as we encounter strong forms of the overstability, the cold dense layer shows a rich internal structure.

The *numerical method* and the *coarseness of the numerical grid* can significantly influence the computed solutions. The entire instability or any particular mode can vanish only due to a too coarse mesh combined with an inappropriate numerical method. This effect is most probably present in all multidimensional calculations.

10.9 Details on models and cooling functions

number	range	β	$3k_B/2\Lambda_0$	$\tau \cdot N$
1	0.70 – 1.35 (4)	4.64	4.6 (25)	4.2 (10)
2	1.35 – 2.00 (4)	2.43	3.4 (16)	2.5 (10)
3	2.00 – 2.69 (4)	-0.30	6.3 (4)	3.7 (10)
4	2.69 – 7.94 (4)	1.48	4.8 (12)	2.2 (10)
5	0.79 – 2.63 (5)	0.15	1.5 (6)	6.0 (10)
6	2.63 – 4.17 (5)	-2.23	1.9 (-7)	2.7 (11)
7	4.17 – 5.62 (5)	0.16	5.4 (6)	3.5 (11)
8	0.56 – 2.00 (6)	-0.56	4.0 (2)	9.7 (11)
9	2.00 – 3.31 (6)	-2.27	1.9 (-8)	3.8 (13)
10	0.33 – 10.0 (7)	0.00	1.2 (7)	1.2 (15)
11	0.10 – 5.00 (9)	0.50	1.2 (11)	8.2 (15)

Table 10.2: RLF1 based on the loss function by Cook et al. [29].

number	range	β	$3k_B/2\Lambda_0$	$\tau \cdot N$
1	0.79 – 1.82 (4)	4.06	7.2 (23)	6.9 (10)
2	1.82 – 2.51 (4)	1.71	7.6 (13)	5.5 (10)
3	2.51 – 3.80 (4)	0.56	6.1 (8)	6.5 (10)
4	0.38 – 1.58 (5)	0.79	7.1 (9)	8.8 (10)
5	1.58 – 2.19 (5)	-0.50	1.4 (3)	1.4 (11)
6	2.19 – 3.98 (5)	-1.92	3.5 (-5)	8.2 (11)
7	3.98 – 5.37 (5)	0.00	2.1 (6)	1.1 (12)
8	5.37 – 9.55 (5)	1.12	5.4 (12)	1.0 (12)
9	0.95 – 1.41 (6)	-0.82	1.3 (1)	2.1 (12)
10	1.41 – 2.40 (6)	-2.35	5.4 (-9)	1.2 (13)
11	2.40 – 3.98 (6)	-0.77	6.1 (1)	3.1 (13)
12	3.98 – 8.91 (6)	-0.09	2.1 (6)	7.3 (13)
13	0.89 – 1.74 (7)	-0.45	2.0 (10)	2.0 (14)
14	1.74 – 3.02 (7)	0.13	8.9 (7)	3.1 (14)
15	0.30 – 1.00 (8)	0.39	7.9 (9)	6.5 (14)
16	0.10 – 5.00 (9)	0.50	6.5 (10)	4.6 (15)

Table 10.3: RLF2 based on the time-dependent loss function by Schmutzler and Tscharnuter [158].

Model	Wind bubble (WB)							
	geometry				wind of CS		ISM	
	$r_{\min}$	$r_{\max}$	Δr	Λ	M	v	N	v
	cm (17)	cm	cm(12)		$M_{\odot}/y$	km/s	cm^{-3}	km/s
WB1	1.6	1 (20)	24	1	1 (-4)	1600	1.5	0
WB1e	1.6	1 (20)	24	1	1 (-4)	1600	1.5	0
WB2	1.6	1 (20)	24	2	1 (-4)	1600	1.5	0
WB1f	1.6	1 (19)	0.3	1	1 (-4)	3000	75	0
WB2f	1.6	1 (20)	24	2	1 (-4)	2800	15	0
	Supernova remnant (SNR)							
	geometry				stellar blast		ISM	
	$r_{\min}$	$r_{\max}$	Δr	Λ	M	E	N	v
	cm (17)	cm	cm (12)		$M_{\odot}$	ergs	cm^{-3}	km/s
SNR1	0.1	1 (21)	490	1	50	1 (51)	1	0
SNR2	0.1	1 (21)	61	2	50	1 (51)	1	0
	Colliding winds (CW)							
	geometry				present wind		earlier wind	
	$r_{\min}$	$r_{\max}$	Δr	Λ	M	v	M	v
	cm (17)	cm	cm (12)		$M_{\odot}/y$	km/s	$M_{\odot}/y$	km/s
CW	0.05	1 (17)	0.023	2	1.1 (-7)	2500	2 (-6)	20
	Colliding planar flows (CPF)							
	Inst.	geometry			driving wind		ISM	
	type	dom.	Δr	Λ	N	v	N	v
		cm	cm (12)		cm^{-3}	km/s	cm^{-3}	km/s
CPF_25	C	1 (20)	24	2	0.025	2800	15	0
CPF_35	M	1 (20)	24	2	0.035	2800	15	0
CPF_45	S2	1 (20)	24	2	0.045	2800	15	0
CPF_55	stab.	1 (20)	24	2	0.055	2800	15	0

Table 10.4: Sample of computed colliding smooth flows. As a representative for the wind bubble flow we take NGC 6880 (WR 136) with model parameters as derived by Schmutz et al. [157]. In addition, we compute models with faster winds (models .f). For the supernova remnant we assume the same parameters as Bertschinger [17]. 80 percent of the initial energy is thermal in our models. For the colliding winds we take the same parameters as Icke et al. [71] took for their (2D) model of a planetary nebulae. $r_{\min}$ and $r_{\max}$ denote the minimum and maximum extent of the computational domain. Δr denotes the finest spatial discretization, Λ the radiative loss function. The cooling limit is $1.5 \cdot 10^4 K$ except for WB1e with $10^4 K$. The heating limit is $10^4 K$ except for CW with $1.5 \cdot 10^4 K$. The ISM has a temperature of $10^4 K$, the earlier wind in the CW case is $1.5 \cdot 10^4 K$. CS stands for central star.

n	model WB1	ξ	λ_0	$\frac{\lambda_0}{\ell_c}$	M_d	$\frac{M_d}{M_{\text{hls}}}$	$\frac{M_d}{M_{\text{cdl}}}$	ϕ_0	r	$\frac{\tau_r}{\tau_0}$
0	d0	64	30	880.	7000	1170	1000	1.7	co	
1	d2.1	0.75	0.67	20.	1.83	0.305	0.26	0.7	ap	2.4
2	d2.2	0.75	0.67	20.	1.83	0.305	0.26	1.4	ap	2.4
3	d2.3	0.75	0.67	20.	1.83	0.305	0.26	5.2	ap	2.5
4	d3	0.5	0.67	20.	1.22	0.203	0.17	1.4	ap	1.6
2	d2.2	0.75	0.67	20.	1.83	0.305	0.26	1.4	ap	2.4
5	d4.1	1	0.67	20.	2.44	0.407	0.34	1.4	ap	3.0
6	d4.0.2	0.5	0.028	0.83	0.10	0.017	0.014	1.4	nop	
4	d3	0.5	0.67	20.	1.22	0.203	0.17	1.4	ap	1.6
14	d5	0.5	4.34	128.	7.91	1.318	1.11	1.4	mp	
7	d4.0.1	1	5.66	1.66	0.20	0.033	0.028	1.4	nop	
8	d4.0.0	1	0.17	5.	0.61	0.102	0.086	1.4	ap	1.6
9	d4.0	1	0.33	10.	1.22	0.203	0.17	1.4	ap	1.7
5	d4.1	1	0.67	20.	2.44	0.407	0.34	1.4	ap	3.0
10	d4	1	1.34	40.	4.88	0.813	0.69	1.4	mp	
11	d6	1	4.02	118.	14.6	2.433	2.06	1.4	mp	
12	d7	1	12.06	355.	43.9	7.317	6.18	1.4	mp	
13	d1	4.14	30.00	880.	437	73	61.55	1.7	mp	
14	d5	0.5	4.34	128.	7.91	1.318	1.11	1.4	mp	

Table 10.5: Sample of the disturbed flows discussed in Section 6. We disturb model WB1 (see Table 10.4) according to Eq. 13 at a time of approximately 69'000 years where we encounter typical I-type overstability. The period of the limit cycle, τ_0 , is approximately 1100 years. The mean mass M_{ls} of the leading shell is approximately $6 \cdot 10^{33}$ gram. The rear boundary of the leading shell has a mean velocity of $9.95 \cdot 10^6$ cm/s. Multiplication with the period of the limit cycle yields a characteristic length $\ell_c \approx 3.4 \cdot 10^{17}$ cm. The mass M_{cdl} of the cold dense layer is $7.1 \cdot 10^{35}$ gram. M_d denotes the mass in 10^{33} gram, λ_0 the length in 10^{15} cm, ξ the amplitude of the disturbance, and n the number of the model. ϕ_0 denotes the phase of the limit cycle at which the leading shock hits the disturbance, r the reaction to the disturbance. τ_r denotes the relaxation time for the aperiodic cases (ap). The other cases are: nop: noisy original periodic evolution, mp: modulated periodic evolution, co: collapse of the leading shell. Note that some models may be listed several times to better illustrate dependences.

Chapter 11

Two dimensional results: Asymmetric case

As in Chapter 10, the material presented in this chapter has already been published. (Walder and Folini [159]). The following text and the figures are identical with the published version, except for some minor changes made to adapt the original paper to the rest of this thesis.

11.1 Introduction

In classical nebulae like SNRs, PNe, WR ring nebulae, and symbiotics, the main emission region in optical, UV and X-rays coincides with radiative shocks. Presumably, radiative shocks play an important role for the structure formation of the universe and for the star formation in the galactic disk (see the review of Draine and McKee [29]).

Two shocks confine the interaction zone of two supersonically colliding flows. Dense, already cooled gas is collected near the contact surface. Here we discuss the asymmetric case where one shock is quasi-adiabatic and the other is overstable due to the thermal cooling instability. A survey of overstable shocks in 1D can be found e.g. in Walder and Folini [157] (WF in the remainder of this chapter) and references therein; 2D results are given by Bertschinger [12] and Strickland and Blondin [143]. Thin, decelerating layers of cold gas, driven against the interstellar medium by a hot gas bubble, are linearly (Vishniac [150], Ryu and Vishniac [121], Bertschinger [12]) as well as nonlinearly overstable (Vishniac [151], Mac Low and Norman [88], Grun et al. [48]). Under the same conditions, accelerated cold thin shells are Rayleigh-Taylor (RT) unstable (Vishniac [151]). On the other hand, decelerating SNRs with a radiative

reverse shock are RT unstable (Chevalier and Blondin [18]).

The aim of the paper this chapter is taken from was to draw attention to a previously unknown mechanism present in radiative shocks leading to small scale structures like filaments and knots even in globally non accelerated shocks. The mechanism also establishes a zone of turbulent mixing of cold and hot material leading to efficient X-ray emission. In Section 11.2 we describe our model parameter. In Section 11.3 we discuss the underlying physics and in Section 11.4 the astrophysical significance of our results. The results are computed with the two dimensional version of our AMRCART-code, briefly described in Section 10.2.

11.2 Physical model and numerical method

We study the collision of two flows whose momentum fluxes are balanced ($\rho_l = 0.14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $v_l = 1763 \text{ km/s}$, and $\rho_r = 14 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $v_r = -176 \text{ km/s}$). The temperature in both flows is set to the cooling limit of 8000 K. The gas of the left shock has a temperature of $1.3 \cdot 10^8 \text{ K}$, that of the right shock $1.3 \cdot 10^6 \text{ K}$. The cooling time on the left side is more than 100'000 years. The right shock is overstable with a period of about 900 years. Radiative cooling is applied in the same way as described in WF, using the radiative loss function of Cook et al. [23]. We use a two-dimensional domain of $10^{19} \text{ cm} \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}$ with planar geometry. The free flows are directed parallel and anti-parallel to the x-axis. The boundary conditions in y-direction are periodic; in x-direction we use inflow conditions. Two runs are performed with different initial conditions: first, an initially 10^{16} cm thick layer of 8000 K cold gas at rest is placed between the two flows. This corresponds to the accumulated matter of about 13 cycles of the overstability. In a second run, there is initially no cold layer. At initial time, no shock is present. This mimics the saturated overstability of the radiative shock. No disturbances other than numerical rounding errors are present.

11.3 Physics of asymmetric radiative flow collision

We summarize our results: young radiative shocks of colliding winds with asymmetric cooling, no global acceleration, and with an overstable shock form a pattern which consists of (from right to left in Figure 11.1):

- a) UCL: the *unstable cooling layer* of a moderately strong, overstable shock (right in Figure 11.1, 11.2, and 11.3),
- b) CDL: the *cold, dense layer* of already cooled gas, being complexly shaped and temporarily varying in size, its highly turbulent gas having a large velocity

and density dispersion,

c) TMZ: the *turbulent mixing zone* where filaments and knots of cold, dense gas are embedded in the very hot gas of the reverse shock and the two components are mixed,

d) SHTS: the *stable, high temperature shock*.

In wind driven bubbles and SNRs, the CDL would form the classical optical and UV nebula, the TMZ would contribute to the X-ray emission, and the SHTS would drive the structure. The TMZ does not emit in the UV or optical, but the knots and the filaments do.

Vishniac [151] has shown that stationary, asymmetric slabs are stable. However – and this is crucial – the overstable shock causes the CDL to oscillate and triggers powerful pressure waves bouncing from one interface of the CDL to the other (see Figure 11.2 and Figures 13, 14, 15 of WF). Similar acceleration of the confining interfaces and similar pressure waves can also evolve when the upstream flow contains inhomogeneities (WF, Figures 15 and 16). This has far reaching consequences.

1. As the interfaces are accelerated against the heavy material of the CDL they become Rayleigh-Taylor (RT) unstable. On the side of the overstable shock (interface I1) this happens when the shock expands nearly adiabatically, using the cold gas as an abutment. The other interface (I2) – binding the CDL against the very light gas of the SHTS – becomes RT unstable due to the sudden pressure loss in the cooling phase of the shock. Moreover, the described pressure waves in the CDL can efficiently generate Richtmyer-Meshkov (RM) instabilities. Consequently, spikes (filaments) grow out of the CDL and bubbles of hot gas sink into the CDL. The Atwood number $A = (\rho_h - \rho_l) / (\rho_h + \rho_l)$ (h=heavy, l=light) is very different at the two interfaces. A is moderate at I1: the spikes and bubbles grow slowly, they have a round shape and roughly the same size. A is large at I2: thin spikes and square-shaped bubbles develop rapidly (see e.g. Alon et al. [3]). Note that the inertia in the spikes and bubbles of the RT and RM instabilities let them survive and even grow after the acceleration has stopped.

2. The growing instabilities and the mechanisms described below excite turbulence in the CDL. Compressible effects are important, and the gas moves partially supersonic. The turbulence is not isotropic. On the contrary, a pattern is formed of regions having different characteristics. The velocity dispersion is larger than sonic, and the density dispersion ranges over nearly one magnitude (see Figure 11.2), corresponding to factors of tens in emissivity.

3. The knots embedded in the zone of turbulent mixing (TMZ) broke off from the filaments under the influence of dynamical drags. Another source of knots which is not considered here, are overtaken density condensations possibly floating upstream of the structure. Through ablation in the boundary layers the hot stream around the knots is loaded with cold material from the

knots. Downstream of the knots the two materials turbulently mix. In the TMZ we find temperatures well above 10^6 K together with significantly enhanced densities: it is a source of X-ray emission. Dynamically important, the hot stream of gas reaches velocities well above 100 km/s. It is mostly driven by the turbulent cooling in the TMZ and slightly modulated by the overstability of the shock (Figure 11.4).

4. Now the stage is set for the subtle interplay between the turbulent flows in the different layers and zones. Occasionally, very collimated high speed streams from the TMZ act on I2 (Figure 11.3), shaping it, eventually breaking off pieces of the filaments, and supporting the growth of the hot gas bubbles. These are partly re-integrated into the CDL, powering its turbulence. Strong vortex rings in the hot stream near I2 can support or suppress the growth of spikes and bubbles, as already discussed by Jun et al. [65]. At I1, another process of structure formation is active. Occasionally, due to the RT-instability and the turbulence within the CDL, pillar-like structures grow out of the CDL, bending I1. The stagnation flow in the UCL is deflected around these pillars, depositing its concentrated momentum at the basement of the pillars. Deep valleys are formed on both sides of the pillars through which the very collimated flow of the UCL penetrates the CDL. Secondary accretion shocks strongly support this mechanism. If the penetrating flow can deposit enough pressure under the basement of a pillar, the pillar can even – very rapidly – grow. By the interplay described in this paragraph, the structure is self-sustained to a certain degree.

The structure formation is not fully saturated at the time we stopped the integration after three cycles of the shock overstability (2650 y). The velocity of the hot stream, the size of the TMZ, the number of spikes and knots, and the velocity and density dispersion in the CDL are still changing in an irregular way. Also, the overstability of the shock is affected by the formation of the structure; its strength has decreased during the simulation. Thus the question remains open whether certain statistical quantities will reach a quasi-steady state or will grow in a self-similar or even unpredictable way or whether the process will stop after a certain period of time.

Obvious physical shortcomings of our model are the neglect of thermal conduction by free, relativistic electrons, and of magnetic and radiative fields. Thermal conduction eventually evaporates the knots and filaments. This will increase the mass-loading in the TMZ which in turn will favor the growth of the structure. Numerical viscosity mimics the effect of thermal conduction. But we cannot estimate whether our simulations over- or underestimate this process. Magnetic fields can support or suppress the growth of RT instabilities and turbulent mixing. The outcome is very sensitive to the initial field (Jun et al. [66]). Kimoto and Chernoff [72] have shown that radiative shocks remain overstable in the presence of a magnetic field whenever the power exponent of the cooling law is negative. Less is known about the influence of ionization

fronts. In 3D, the same driving mechanisms are present. However, one expects quantitative differences, such as a faster growth rate of the RT- and the RM-instability and a different character of the turbulence.

11.4 Astrophysical implications and conclusions

Our results are of direct relevance for those (non-accelerated) PNe and ring-nebulae where a fast wind collides with the wind from an earlier phase of the stellar evolution. We assume that the process is still relevant for weakly accelerated and decelerated structures, e.g. SNRs expanding in an earlier wind or wind bubbles expanding into a uniform medium. In strongly decelerated structures like SNRs expanding into the uniform ISM, the growth of RT-spikes into the driving gas is likely to be completely suppressed. However, in this case the cold sheet is subject to the DI (deceleration instability, e.g. Vishniac [151], Mac Low and Norman [88]), which can provide ideal seeds for the growth of the RM instability, and we probably end up with a similar structure. In any case, the presence of an overstable shock or fluctuations in the ISM are necessary to excite the described mechanism. However, as discussed above, the developed structure may survive for a considerable time after the excitation mechanism has ceased.

Our result may also be of relevance for the excitation of the instability appearing in asymmetric colliding radiative flows in binaries (Stevens et al. [141]). As discussed by Walder [155], the excitation mechanism of this instability is unclear and may be polluted by a numerical effect known as carbuncle.

An observational implication of the mechanism is the appearance of knots and filaments at the inner rim of ring-nebulae, PNe and SNR as observed e.g. in the Helix nebula (NGC 7293) (O'Dell and Handron [109]) and in the WR ring nebulae RCW 58 (Smith et al. [135]). The turbulence in the CDL should lead to broadened emission line features as observed e.g. in RCW 58 (Smith et al. [135]). The model also gives a natural explanation of the measured X-ray emission of such nebulae (see e.g. Kreising et al. [76] for PNe) which, in particular for PNe, can hardly be explained by the emission of the leading shock alone.

Certainly, this newly described physical process is just another part in the complex puzzle of structure formation in the wake of shocks. It shows, however, that small scaled structures like filaments and knots can be generated without significant global acceleration or deceleration. It can explain to a certain degree the existence of (micro-) turbulence in nebulae and in the ISM, and it provides an efficient source of X-ray emission.

Figure 11.1: *Interaction zone of asymmetric wind collision at 2081 years shown in temperature (K, logarithmic scale). From right to left: Cooling layer of radiative, overstable shock (UCL), cold, dense gas layer (CDL), filaments and knots embedded in the turbulent mixing zone (TMZ), hot gas of the adiabatic shock (SHTS). The horizontal extension is 10^{17} cm.*

Figure 11.2: Zoom ($3.75 \cdot 10^{16}$ cm vertically) into the structure shown in density (cm^{-3} , logarithmic scale). The UCL is to the right, the SHTS to the left. Top panel: Collapsing period of the overstable radiative shock (1782 y). The CDL has expanded. Its rear interface, accelerating to the right, is RT unstable. Bottom panel: Boosting phase of the overstable radiative shock (2081 y). Additional knots have formed. Due to the boost, bubbles and spikes start to form at the front interface as well.

Figure 11.3: Velocity field and density of the TMZ at 2081 y. Due to the interaction with the knots and the CDL, the hot stream (Figure 11.4) concentrates its momentum in some areas, in others it forms vortex rings.

Figure 11.4: Time-evolution of the uniform velocity of the hot stream upwind of the TMZ (at the left edge of Figure 11.3). The velocity grows with the onset of turbulent mixing. The growth is modulated by the influence of the overstability of the radiative shock.

Epilogue

Before coming to an end it seems appropriate to quickly glance at some more general issues barely touched so far. First, however, the rather diversified contents of this thesis shall be briefly summarized.

Red thread and corner stones

The red thread of this thesis is the numerical treatment of radiation and its interaction with matter in astrophysics. The corner stones of this thesis are the portation of a method for multidimensional radiative transfer suggested by applied mathematicians to a real application, the extension of a one dimensional, optically thin radiative transfer code to three dimensions, and the new results regarding the stability properties of radiative colliding flows.

The TR3D code provides a new approach to multidimensional, optically thick, NLTE radiative transfer. It is the first time that a generalized mean intensity approach is used for the solution of the transfer equation in the context of the NLTE radiative transfer problem. For the treatment of optically thick lines extended Sobolev theory is used. Its main advantages lie in the transfer part: Its h -independence, the use of a modern, iterative solver, and the modest memory requirements of this part. The code has been successfully tested for some simple problems and in its present state is on the break of being applied to 'real' problems.

Somewhat complementary to TR3D is *the code D3NEBEL*. It is applicable under nebular conditions only and catches the three dimensional structure by a set of one dimensional rays, all of them originating from the same central radiation source. To each of these rays an existing 1D code which includes detailed atomic data is applied. If applicable, D3NEBEL is much faster than TR3D and includes much more atomic data. To demonstrate the possibilities of D3NEBEL for the investigation of binary star systems it has been applied to several model symbiotic systems.

The results on the *stability of radiative colliding flows* show that unstable behaviour of the collision zone of two radiative flows is rather the rule than the

exception. The subtle interplay between different kinds of instabilities leads to supersonic turbulence in the interaction zone and to the formation of high density knots and filaments. From an astrophysical point of view, new light is shed on structure formation, X-ray emission, and optical and UV emission lines in different kinds of astrophysical objects like supernova remnants or planetary nebulae.

A view back stage

Numerical simulations are a valuable tool in astrophysics and they become more and more important. They allow to learn a great deal about basic physical processes as well as about entire objects, although they are not capable of reproducing reality in all its facets. However, this path to new physical results is more stony than it may seem.

In order to do numerical simulations in this area, a solid knowledge of physics and astronomy is certainly required. With regard to the ever increasing complexity of the physical models, the codes involved, and the computer resources at disposition, also some knowledge in numerical mathematics and computer sciences is necessary, even for just running numerical simulations. For high quality code development, the knowledge in these areas has to be rather detailed and an intense exchange of knowledge between people working in the different fields is absolutely necessary. The use of different terminology and different ways of thinking in the different fields does not exactly facilitate this task. Obviously, the price for acquiring the necessary knowledge in so many different fields is that one usually will not become a top specialist in any of these fields on their own. Nevertheless, people with this kind of knowledge are very important in many areas of nowadays research.

Code development itself is a rather time consuming enterprise. Not only has a program to be coded and debugged for coding errors, it also has to be tested for physical correctness and numerical errors. Even for relatively simple physical models this testing can be quite intricate.

While it is rather obvious that developing a code is a time consuming enterprise the effort of performing numerical simulations is often underestimated. Typically, a numerical simulation will leave you with a huge heap of numbers. To convert this heap into something that can be digested can be quite time consuming. Post-processing of the output includes, among others, visualization, an error analysis, and possibly also a statistical analysis. For each of these processes software has again to be developed or at least adapted for the present purposes. In particular, for the visualization of the results of multidimensional numerical simulations it is essential to have some exchange with people being specialized in that field.

Once this technical equipment is present, the output of a simulation can

be brought into a more handy form. Having done this, it is time to remember that both, the numerics and the physical model, can be deceptive and that it is not always easy to judge which parts of a result are hard, physical facts and which parts are merely artifacts.

Physical model and numerical method or: How far can a result be trusted?

Pretty colour pictures of simulated data look seductive but they can also be deceptive and one has to be a bit cautious about them. The physical model and the numerical method can lead to various artifacts. While some aspects of a result will reflect a natural, physical behaviour others are rather special features or artificial at all. To tell the difference between them is often not easy, even for relatively simple physical models.

Some purely numerical artifacts are relatively easy to detect. A standard trick, for example, to check for any significant dependence on the numerical grid is to run the same simulation several times on different grids. This includes different mesh sizes as well as different orientations of the problem with respect to the grid to test for alignment effects. Such techniques have also been applied in some of the previous chapters of this thesis. There it could be seen that such effects can significantly influence the solution. Other numerical artifacts are harder to detect, especially as one does often not exactly know what one is looking for. An analytical error estimation is usually impossible for the kind of problems studied here.

As far as the physical model is concerned the problem is not so much the obvious inaccuracies and drawbacks of the model. It is, for example, easy to notice that a ten level hydrogen atom is not reality. Much more difficult to estimate are the consequences of these obvious inaccuracies. To come back to the ten level hydrogen atom, it is, for example, not a priori clear how this will influence the strength of a particular emission line.

Having performed a numerical simulation the art is to find out which parts of the result, despite all shortcomings, reflect a real, physical behaviour.

A glimpse into future

In the field of radiation and its interaction with matter more and more effort is spent on the multidimensional aspects of the problem and on bringing closer together the extreme cases — matter dominated problems versus radiation dominated problems in the sense described in Chapter 1. Also the interaction of different codes is pushed forward, either for pure post processing purposes, as in the example of D3NEBEL in this thesis, or in the sense of real integration. For example, it may be possible in future to include D3NEBEL into the AMRCART

code, which would probably allow to treat the temperature and ionization structure of the matter more consistently.

In general, the increase in computer power and the improved numerical techniques will allow to increase the complexity of the physical models to be investigated by numerical simulations. It should be stressed here that improving a physical model not necessarily means to include more physics. It can also mean to stick to the physics one already has but instead to go to higher dimensions. Either way will open new insights into basic physical processes as well as into the physics of entire objects. On the other hand, the increased complexity of the physical models will make it more and more difficult to estimate the quality of the numerical results. Connected to this point is the danger that, seduced by the possibility of nowadays computers, more complex physical models are attacked before the more basic situations have been understood well enough. Just including more complex physics into a model does not necessarily mean to gain deeper insight. Nevertheless, numerical simulations of complex, non-linear systems will gain more and more attention not only in astrophysics. However, in this field they have a somewhat special place as hardly any laboratory experiment can be carried out and numerical simulations tend to substitute for this lack.

With regard to these future perspectives and to what has been said earlier on in this chapter, it remains to be hoped that also in future there will be institutions and people who dare to support a project like this one here, which tries to achieve new insights by bringing together pieces from different disciplines.

Curriculum vitae

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1975 – 1981	Elementary school in Schlieren, ZH
1981 – 1987	Freies Gymnasium Zürich, Maturität Typus C
1987	Certificate of Proficiency in English, University of Cambridge
1988 – 1993	Studies in physics at ETH Zürich, diploma in theoretical physics with the thesis <i>'The stability and structure of radiative colliding winds'</i> under the supervision of Prof. H. Nussbaumer
1993 – 1998	Assistant at the Institut für Astronomie, ETH Zürich
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